

**AN EVALUATION OF IVORIAN TRUTH COMMISSION
THROUGH RESTORATIVE JUSTICE**

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Dedication

To the thousands of victims of the conflicts in Cote d'Ivoire,

To my father, my mother, and my wife,

To my immediate and extended family,

To my friends who supported me in this doctoral project.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AFISMA: Africa-led International Support Mission to Mali

AMIB: African Union Mission in Burundi

APDH: Action for the Protection

AU: African Union

CDVR: Dialogue Truth and Reconciliation Commission

CECOS: Elements of the Security Operations command Centre

CEI: Independent Electoral Commission

CERAP: Centre for Research and Action for Peace

CDP: Permanent Dialogue Framework

CJPVG-CI: Coalition for justice and forgiveness for war victims in Côte d'Ivoire

CNE: National Commission Inquiry

CONADEP: National Commission on the Disappeared

CONARIV: National Commission for Reconciliation and Compensation of Victims

COVICI: Confederation of Victims of Ivorian Crises

CVCI: Collective of Victims in Cote d'Ivoire

CVJR: Truth, Justice, and Reconciliation Commission, Mali

DDR: Disarmament, Demobilisation and Reintegration

DVG: War Victims Directorate

ECOWAS: Economic Community of West African States

FDS: Defence and Security Forces

FN: New Forces

FRCI: Republican Forces of Côte d'Ivoire

GPA: Comprehensive Political Agreement

HRC: Human Rights Committee

HRW: Human Rights Watch

ICJ: International Court of Justice

ICTJ: International Centre for Transitional Justice

LIDHO: Ivorian League for Human Rights

MARWOPNET: Women's Network of Mano River for Peace

MIDH: Ivorian Human Rights Movement

MIPT: Memorial Institute for Prevention of Terrorism

OHCHR: Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights

PAC: Civilian Self-Defence Patrols

PNCS: National Social Cohesion Programme

RAIDH: Ivorian Human Rights Actors

RCT: Randomised Controlled Trial

RRC: Reparation and Rehabilitation Committee

SCSL: Special Court for Sierra Leone

TC: Truth Commission

TM: Military Tribunal

TOC: Theory of Change

TRC: Truth and Reconciliation Commission

UN: United Nations

UNOCI: UN Operations in Côte d'Ivoire

WANEP: West African Peace Network

WHO: World Health Organisation

Abstract

Following the conflicts that took place in Côte d'Ivoire between 1990 and 2011, the question arises of how to build lasting peace in the country while providing justice for the thousands of victims. As part of responses aimed at repairing the damage caused by the armed conflicts that devastated the country, the Ivorian government established a Truth Commission (CDVR) in 2011. Although the main objectives of a truth commission are to uncover the truth and promote reconciliation, it is necessary to critically question its establishment and operation. To address this concern, this doctoral thesis used restorative justice to evaluate the transitional justice mechanism that is the Ivorian CDVR. The analysis of the design and activities of the CDVR therefore provided a better understanding of its capacity to enable Côte d'Ivoire to overcome the trauma of conflicts and build a just future. To accomplish this task, this dissertation utilised a qualitative case study research design. Through a literature review and semi-structured interviews, I collected critical data to design the evaluation criteria and present evidence of the existence of peace and reconciliation relationships in the CDVR process. The study found that although the CDVR demonstrated many restorative justice values (solidarity) and principles (reparation), it failed to be restorative and conciliatory.

Thus, the study argues that for transitional justice mechanisms to respond as effectively as possible to the Ivorian crisis, initiatives implemented by the government should include all stakeholders, civil society, and a safe and respectful environment. Since many conflicts that the country has experienced are due to the poor organisation of the political apparatus, it will be necessary to organise so that the victims of all political parties are integrated. The study also argued that the lack of independency and political neutrality, international influence, inadequate reparations, lack of accountability, the absence of national consultations and voluntary participation in the peace process and the way in which human potential was not properly exploited in the reconciliation process in Côte d'Ivoire partly explain the limited impact of transitional justice mechanisms. Indeed, according to the study, there has never been mediation between the victims and the executioners. Also, victims were treated based on their political, religious, or ethnic affiliations. The failure of mediation and the exclusion of CDVR are therefore supported by the results of the study.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 Case Study: Justification of Côte d'Ivoire	1
1.2 Post-colonial Côte d'Ivoire	3
1.3 The context of the problem	4
1.4 The mandate of the CDVR	6
1.5 Statement of the problem	10
1.6 Research questions and objectives.	11
1.7 The significance of the study	12
1.8 Structure of the thesis.....	16
CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW.....	18
2.2 The impact of document destruction on accountability and legalism	28
<i>Holistic strategies for sustainable peace and development.....</i>	<i>29</i>
2.3 Truth commissions.....	31
2.4 Truth commissions and evaluating impacts.	39
2.5 Restorative justice: A space for dialogue	42
2.5.1 Centred on the victim.	47
2.5.2 Inclusiveness and engagement.....	48
2.5.3 Mediation and Negotiations of restoration processes	50
2.5.4 Restoration of the identity, respect, and dignity of victims.....	51
2.5.5 Symbolic / material reparations	53
2.5.6 Seeking the truth and overcome the denial of injustice.	57
2.6 Restorative Justice as a Framework for Evaluating TRC.....	58
2.7 Enhancing the discussion of complex victimhood in restorative justice.....	64
Conclusion	68
CHAPTER THREE: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK.....	69
3.2 Reconciliation: A prerequisite for the building of the nation	72
3.3 Restoration social ties and reconciliation	85

3.4 Differentiation of justice.....	86
3.5 The relational orientation of restorative justice	88
3.6 The Relationship Between Reconciliation, Non-Recurrence, and Nation-Building	91
3.7 Recognition: Towards the development of a formal ethics	94
3.8 Recognition and transitional justice	97
Conclusion	101
4.1 The research paradigm.....	102
4.2 Research design.....	103
4.3 Criteria for evaluating the truth commission.	106
4.3.1 Restoring social ties and reconciliation: before the Commission	106
4.3.2 Restoring social ties and reconciliation: during the mandate.....	109
4.3.3 Restoring social ties: following the final report	112
4.4 Researcher positionality and its impact on the thesis	113
<i>Influence on research topic selection</i>	114
<i>Impact on research interaction.....</i>	114
<i>Challenges in data interpretation</i>	115
<i>Methodological triangulation</i>	116
4.5 Ethical approval.....	116
4.6 Purposive sampling.....	119
4.7 Snowball sampling	120
4.8 Primary data sources.....	120
<i>Data collection tools interviews and the interview guide</i>	121
4.9 The sample	122
<i>Assumptions and types of the study sample</i>	124
4.11 Trust and interviewing	127
<i>Painful truths and fidelity to the information gathered.....</i>	128
4.12 Secondary data sources	128
Conclusion	129

CHAPTER FIVE: EVALUATION FRAMEWORK DESIGN	131
5.1 Theories of recognition	131
5.2 Evaluation of impact through theory-based approach.....	137
5.3 A theory of change (TOC)	139
5.4 Criteria to evaluate the Truth Commission	142
5.4.1 Criterion 1 (CR-1): CDVR as a Negotiated Institution	143
5.4.2 Criterion 2 (CR-2): CDVR as an Inclusive Process	143
5.4.3 Criterion 3 (CR-3): Focused on the victim and Empowerment in the TRC's Context.....	144
5.4.4 Criterion 4 (CR-4): CDVR and Truth-Telling	144
5.4.5 Criterion 5 (CR-5): Recognition of Survivors' identities and overcoming denial of injustice	145
5.4.6 Criterion 6 (CR-6): Restoring Survivors' Dignity and Self-respect.....	145
5.4.7 Criterion 7 (CR-7): Flexibility of reparations programmes	145
Conclusion	146
CHAPTER SIX: IMPLEMENTING THE FRAMEWORK.....	147
6.1 An overview of the Ivorian commission.....	147
6.1.1 Context of establishment and legal status of the CDVR	148
6.2 Evaluation of the CDVR	149
6.2.1 Restoring Social Ties and Reconciliation Before the Establishment of the Commission .	149
Criterion 1 (CR-1): TRC as a Negotiated Institution.....	149
<i>The early stages of the CDVR design</i>	<i>149</i>
<i>The TRC organisational operations.....</i>	<i>152</i>
6.2.2 Restoring Social Ties and Reconciliation During the Commission's Mandate	153
Criterion 2 (CR-2): CDVR as an Inclusive Process.....	153
<i>Inclusion and the CDVR Mandate</i>	<i>153</i>
<i>Inclusion and TRC events.....</i>	<i>155</i>
<i>CDVR events: challenges to inclusion.....</i>	<i>156</i>
<i>CDVR events: perpetrators and exclusion</i>	<i>158</i>
Criterion 3 (CR-3): Focus on the victim and Empowerment in the CDVR's Context.....	158
<i>CDVR events: empowerment.....</i>	<i>159</i>
Criterion 4 (CR-4): CDVR and the search for truth	160
Criterion 5 (CR-5): Overcoming denials of injustice and victim identities	161
Criterion 6 (CR-6): Restoring Survivors' Dignity	163
Criterion 7 (CR-7): Flexibility of the reparations programme:.....	168

6.4 Comparative study of interviews by category	177
Conclusion	178
CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSION.....	180
7.1 Transitional Justice in the Ivorian Context: key findings.....	180
7.1.1. Truth-seeking efforts were limited	181
7.1.2. The commission lacked independence and political neutrality	182
7.1.3. Reparations and victim support were inadequate	182
7.1.4. Lack of accountability undermined reconciliation.....	183
7.1.5. Community-based reconciliation mechanisms were underutilised	184
7.1.6. Approach of restorative justice: recognition and reparation	184
7.1.7. National reconciliation: Process and challenges.....	185
7.1.8. International influence on the Ivorian Truth Commission	186
7.1.9 Restorative Justice and Complex Victimhood.....	187
7.2 Contributions to transitional justice scholarship	188
7.2.1 Methodological contribution to knowledge	188
7.2.2 Theoretical Contributions to knowledge.....	191
7.2.3 Empirical contribution to knowledge	193
7.3 The evolving framework of transitional justice.....	196
7.5 Limitations of the Study and future research directions.....	199
7.6 Final remarks.....	201
REFERENCES.....	205

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

Established on May 13, 2011, by the President of the Ivorian Republic Mr. Ouattara, the Dialogue, Truth, and Reconciliation Commission (CDVR) is both a series of transitional justice mechanisms and a driver of dialogue between the populations of Côte d'Ivoire. Thus, the mission of the commission:

“Consisted of highlighting the underlying causes of the Ivorian crisis in order to better understand it, of identifying the victims and perpetrators of human rights violations that occurred in Côte d'Ivoire in the past, of proposing reparations which promote the healing of the wounds suffered by the victims, to propose measures to avoid the repetition of violations and to ensure the training of citizens in respect for human rights and democratic culture”

(CDVR, 2014, p.23).

In a word, the mission assigned to the CDVR was that of promoting the reconciliation process. It therefore had to be inclusive, to proceed so that all the stakeholders in the post-electoral crisis were united, with a view to a profound resolution of the problem, guaranteeing peace. At the end of this commission's mandate, evidence will show whether it is succeeding in its mission.

The aim of this research being to examine the impact of truth commissions (TC) in general and that of Côte d'Ivoire, this chapter first presents postcolonial Côte d'Ivoire, the historical context conflicts, and transitional justice, then the establishment and operation of the CDVR. Additionally, the overall research question as well as the specific research questions that guide the study are clarified. Finally, the remaining chapters of the thesis are described. This is done to provide the logical sequence of the search.

1.1 Case Study: Justification of Côte d'Ivoire

To undertake the actual evaluation of the CDVR, a case study is used. Deciding to conduct a case study is a choice of what to study. Doing a case study is not a methodological choice (Bassett and Straus, 2011; Thomas, 2011). The choice of case study presented in this research is essential to better understand how the CDVR, created in 2011 by President Ouattara, contributes to promoting peace and

reconciliation. The reason for choosing the CDVR as a case study is that firstly, reports from international organisations as well as experts in transitional justice refer to this commission as a “truth commission”(Hayner, 2002, 2010; Freeman, 2006; Backer). Second, following the post-electoral crisis in 2010, the establishment of a CDVR constituted a strong axis of the new rolling party. The CDVR was set up on May 13, 2011, by the government, and began its work in September 2011. It is responsible for establishing the causes of successive crises and shedding light on all serious violations of human rights committed between 1990 and 2011, the return of the multiparty system in the country to the post-electoral crisis. Thus, to be able to contribute to reconciliation and social cohesion, this administrative authority has been entrusted with a mission comprising four components. Firstly, the Commission had to carry out investigative work consisting of the one hand of developing an appropriate typology of human rights violations, and on the other hand of seeking the truth and locating responsibility for national events. Then it was up to the CDVR to consider the suffering of the victims and try to remedy it. To do this, the commission had to hear the victims, reconstruct, and obtain recognition of the facts by the perpetrators of the violations and the resulting pardon, but also, propose means likely to help heal the trauma suffered by the victims. A third aspect concerns the power of recommendation of the Ivorian Commission which was to identify and make proposals for the implementation of actions likely to strengthen social cohesion and national unity; to identify the causes of conflicts and make proposals aimed at combating injustice and inequalities of all kinds. Finally, it was incumbent on the CDVR to work directly to raise awareness and educate the population. To this end, the ordinance of July 13 enjoined it to educate for peace, dialogue, and peaceful coexistence; to contribute to the emergence of a national conscience and to the adhesion of all to the primacy of the general interest; to promote respect for differences and democratic values.

This very ambitious roadmap given to the CDVR included several missions generally entrusted to truth commissions. Indeed, the fact of seeking the truth, which can be perceived as "the clarification of serious acts of violence which took place" (Garibay, 2007, p. 63), is in no way a specific feature of the Ivorian commission. Truth is often erected in reconciliation processes as a supreme value with cathartic virtues for victims (Ross and Lachartre, 2003). The perpetual quest for forgiveness is also present in the context of post-conflict policies (Lefranc, 2002). However, the missions

devolved to the CDVR raise some questions about a situation of neither peace nor war in the country compared to what is said in the local and international press. (Auerbach, 2005).

Indeed, since April 2011, many agreed that the situation has improved rapidly. In particular, the President Ouattara's insistence on an economic revival has garnered massive support from international partners. At the same time, these partners persist in calling for in-depth national reconciliation. And yet, reconciliation is stalling, relative peace remains very fragile and capital from international financial institutions is pouring in. Despite the declarations of intent by the Ivorian leaders, the political obstacles to reform and reconciliation are numerous, if not in contradiction with the stated objective of reconciliation. What about this reconciliation? It is in this situation that this study examines the CDVR process to find solutions to the obstacles it encounters. Additionally, this study examines the restorative potentials of the CDVR design. Indeed, the study seeks to understand the conditions in which the CDVR was set up and its operation.

Snape and Spencer (2003) suggest that, under the above conditions, it is necessary to adopt a flexible stance to understand the contexts of the communities studied. In the reflection of Straus and Corbin (1990), qualitative methods in studies make it possible to discover and understand what is hidden behind a specific phenomenon. In our context, the study seeks to discover, through semi-structured interviews, the conditions for the creation and operation of the CDVR. Additionally, this qualitative method used in this research helps provide complex details of the CDVR process. which are "difficult to convey with quantitative methods" (Straus and Corbin, 1990: 19). The study interviews showed that there was emotion and mood among the participants because their responses brought awareness to the tragedy they experienced. It was important to consider the conditions in which the respondents live even if they are elite agents (Willis, Jost, & Nilakanta, 2007).

1.2 Post-colonial Côte d'Ivoire

Coming out of the colonial system, peace and stability were two of the main challenges that African states had to face, due to their political and institutional history. It is in this sense that the first president of Côte d'Ivoire, Félix Houphouët-Boigny, established a single party system in the country. Houphouët-Boigny was elected to the supreme

office on November 7, 1960. He took on the dreams of a West African territory, the leading exporter and importer of goods among the former French colonies. Côte d'Ivoire, a country with undeniable potential, nevertheless has weaknesses, such as its fragmentation into around sixty ethnic groups, or due to well-defined union and student opposition (Simonet, 2010, p403). Thus, the objective with the single party was not only to fight against regional disparities inherited from colonisation by creating schools and jobs within the country, by organising anniversary celebrations of the Republic respectively in the different administrations and prefectures; but also, to facilitate an integration policy, favourable to the emergence of a national consciousness. This, through the presentation of a cultural and economic heritage common to all the communities of the territory. According to Eyraud (1965, pp.11), thanks to this far-sighted policy of President Houphouët, Côte d'Ivoire offered the image of a country in full expansion. However, it must be recognised that its implementation very quickly revealed the limits of national ties. There was therefore no visible link between the state and the community. This situation ended up forging resolute opposition from the ruling classes to any supranational approach. And discrimination during appointments to high public functions barely concealed the ethnicization of collective life. These abuses of power had serious repercussions on Ivorian society. We then witnessed the emergence of violent struggles and inter-ethnic and inter-regional conflicts. It was unfortunately in this deteriorated political and social climate that Félix Boigny died on December 7, 1993.

1.3 The context of the problem

Henri Konan Bedié constitutionally succeeded Houphouët-Boigny at the end of 1993. He was overthrown on December 24, 1999, by a coup d'état led by General Robert Guei, who became the new Ivorian head of state. However, President Henri Konan Bedié, before the overthrow of his power, had developed an approach to the concept of "Ivoirité", which offended the sensitivity of the Ivorian populations, made up mainly of foreigners. "Ivoirité", a harmonious and fruitful synthesis of Ivorian cultural values, can be considered a paradoxical concept. The true creator of the word is the sum of those who, today, fight and divide Côte d'Ivoire: Niangoranh Porquet was born in Korhogo in 1948, to a father N'zima from Grand-Bassam (South) and of a Malinké mother from Boundiali (North). Aware of this biological mix, he wanted to be a cultural

link between these two parts of Côte d'Ivoire. And the concept he put on "the market" was originally a cultural concept (Boa, 2003:7).

Further, he states that

The word "Ivoirité" and its cultural content were clarified for the first time in 1974. It appeared in the pen of Pierre Niava and in the mouth of Niangoranh Porquet. One is a literary critic and the other an artist.

(Boa, 2003 p7).

Such reasoning, added to the socio-political atmosphere, cannot promise tender cohabitation or social cohesion. The deepening of the concept of "Ivoirité" by Henri Konan Bédié, also consisted of asking to exclude from any consultation the Burkinabè, to whom Houphouët-Boigny had granted the right to vote in Côte d'Ivoire, their territory having a time merged with that of Côte d'Ivoire under French colonisation (Gaulume, 2001).

Subsequently, the presidential election of October 2000 pitted General Guei against the leader of the Ivorian Popular Front (FPI), Laurent Gbagbo. Let us also note that this election took place, to say the least, in a peaceful atmosphere. What followed was a challenge to Laurent Gbagbo's victory, which led to a political crisis with deadly clashes. This crisis was followed by the rebellion of 2002. This rebellion or attempted coup d'état of September 19, 2002, was presented as a mutiny of the army, especially of soldiers from the North who contested the power of Laurent Gbagbo (Rayal, 2005, p112).

Very quickly, the movement attracted the sympathy of the populations of the north of the country, who were made up of many foreigners. However, they were all combined into a single name of "dioulas". The frustrations of the concept of "Ivoirité" had left people very sensitive and manipulable. The rebellion was therefore a means of recovering their dignity or their lost rights. Hence the clashes which caused several losses of human life.

Eight years later, when the presidential elections pitted Alassane Ouattara, the opposition leader, against President Laurent Gbagbo, there was a repeat. As Alassane

Ouattara's victory was contested by the outgoing power, it was the start of an armed conflict. This deadly crisis of 2010, which caused more than three thousand (3,000) deaths, was this time the result of all the tensions accumulated since the power of President Houphouët-Boigny. Since, several people saw in the contestation of Alassane Ouattara's victory, an ideology of ethnic exclusion, an act of xenophobia.

1.4 The mandate of the CDVR

The general mission of the CDVR was to reconcile all communities living in Côte d'Ivoire. As a national authority, CDVR had to analyse the causes of crises through hearings, assess their effects, and seek solutions to restore social cohesion in the long term. This involved proposing specific actions to avoid the repetition of crises detrimental to Côte d'Ivoire and its populations in the future. The tasks assigned in this capacity to the CDVR are listed as follows:

1. Develop an appropriate typology of human rights violations likely to be the subject of deliberations.
2. Seek truth and situate responsibilities on past and recent national socio-political events.
3. Hear the victims, obtain recognition of the facts by the perpetrators of the alleged violations and the consequent pardon.
4. Propose all kinds of means likely to help heal the trauma suffered by the victims.
5. Identify and make proposals for their implementation of actions likely to strengthen social cohesion, and national unity.
6. Identify and make proposals aimed at combating injustice, inequalities of all kinds, tribalism, nepotism, exclusion as well as hatred in all their forms.
7. Educate for peace, dialogue, and peaceful coexistence.
8. Contribute to the emergence of a national conscience and the support of all for the primacy of the general interest.
9. Promote respect for differences and democratic values.

(CDVR, 2014).

The government had set the term of the CDVR at two years. On September 28, 2013, the mandate expired. The work of the commission was extended by the President of

the Republic for a year (Abidjanet, 2013). Following this extension, which noted that several tasks remained to be accomplished, the new mission prescribes the accomplishment of the following tasks:

1. Seek the truth and situate responsibilities on past and recent national socio-political events.
2. Hear victims, perpetrators, and witnesses in public sessions.
3. Propose to the government reparations and means of any kind likely to help heal the traumas suffered by the victims.

(CDVR, 2014).

From its establishment on September 28, 2011, the Commission has endeavoured to adopt the texts and create the bodies necessary for its operation. This is how internal regulations were drawn up, adopted in December 2011, which determine its internal organisation. The President of the CDVR directs and coordinates the activities of the Commission. He is assisted in his work by an Executive Committee which includes, in addition to the president, the three vice-presidents. The decision-making body of the CDVR is the Plenary Assembly of Commissioners. For the practical execution of the mission, four specialised commissions were created: the heuristic commission, the Hearing and Investigations commission, the Reparations commission, and the Memorial commission. An advisory board, made up of eminent personalities such as Drogba Didier, international footballer and other personalities from the political, religious, military, or civil society world, advises on issues relating to the execution of the powers of the CDVR. Furthermore, to achieve its objectives of a participatory, consultative, and inclusive process, the CDVR has established decentralised structures called local commissions in all regions of the country. From 19 local commissions in 2011, they rose to 37 during the term of office in 2013. The administration of the CDVR is placed under the responsibility of a Secretary General who manages an administrative and financial director and a general resources director. Two support services, the legal service, and the communication service, have been set up to provide technical support to the Commission (CDVR, 2014).

Article 11 of the establishment Ordinance n° 2011-167 of the July 13, 2011, lists the organs of the Commission: The President directs and represents the CDVR,

coordinates its activities and ensures that the decisions of the Plenary Assembly and the Executive Committee are carried out (art. 12 of the Ordinance). The Plenary Assembly is the orientation and decision-making body of the CDVR, in that it adopts the rules of procedure, the budget, the work schedule and the reports of the CDVR (art. 13 of the Ordinance). The Executive Committee assists the President of the CDVR in the exercise of his functions and supervises the activities of the specialised and local commissions (art. 14 of the Ordinance). The General Secretariat assists the President of the CDVR in the administrative, financial, and technical management of the CDVR (art. 15 of the Ordinance). Local Commissions were responsible for raising awareness among citizens of the different phases of the transitional justice process in Côte d'Ivoire; organised and conducted community dialogues; took statements from victims in listening centres; built a local and regional database on victims, damaged suffered, crimes and violations of human rights.

In its final report published in 2016, the CDVR made several recommendations for achieving reconciliation. This section presents the most important of these recommendations.

CDVR looked at the root causes of recent Ivorian crises, namely the issue of land, poverty and the instrumentalization of local or national identity. CDVR recommended the effective application of the law on rural land, the consideration of gender in the general policy of the country, the reduction of inequalities in regional development, the in place of a republican army endowed with appropriate and modern means, good governance, and the fight against impunity as well as the strengthening of democracy and reparations for the victims. This section focuses on reparation recommendations. The CDVR has adopted two forms of reparations for victims: financial reparations (individual and/or collective), and non-financial reparations (moral or symbolic, community rehabilitation, psychological care). The CDVR considered victim and injury respectively to be:

“Any natural or legal person having directly or indirectly suffered one or more damages and any physical (bodily), material, moral or psychological harm suffered as a result of the various crises experienced by Côte d'Ivoire during the period from 1990 to 2011 (period retained by the CDVR) on the Ivorian situation)”

(CDVR, 2016).

At the end of the hearings and investigations, the CDVR retained the following crimes for reparations: murders, disappearances, serious sexual violence, torture, destruction of production tools, looting of property, physical damage and psychological factors leading to total or partial disability (CDVR, 2016).

For individual reparations for victims, the Commission recommended restitution (of movable or immovable property) and financial compensation (pensions, scholarships, allowances for income-generating activities, etc.). In addition, the Commission recommended that a programme of emergency physical reparations or psychological care be implemented for specific cases such as victims with serious after-effects or victims of serious sexual violence. Regarding the deceased, the Commission recommended that compensation be extended to their beneficiaries. As for the missing, the concept is not yet legally defined in Côte d'Ivoire (CDVR, 2016).

The CDVR also recommended moral or symbolic reparations and collective reparations such as community rehabilitation programmes, provision of socio-economic services and reconstruction of infrastructure. The meaning of these reparations is to convey a message of dignity and recognition of the victims. To remind its citizens of the tragedies in the country, Côte d'Ivoire could build a national memorial and regional memorials. The national memorial would be both a museum of the horrors of war and a receptacle for all the data available on the Ivorian crises. It is about making public and accessible the information collected and stored in what will become the place of memory of the Ivorian Nation. Just as significant as physical memorials are intangible memorials. The CDVR would like to propose, as such, the idea of annual festivals of memory which would be the fruit of a script of the lived tragedy and the desire for redemption.

The CDVR offered conferences and competitions. The projects will derive their substance from the collective work of Ivorians who have a certain competence in the matter. Their contribution will be solicited through a conference and two competitions. The CDVR also recommended a draft national ritual of memory. As in all rituals, the argument will be the representation of the passage from a situation of social imbalance to redemption. The CDVR proposed November 15, each year for performing the ritual. This date is already a public holiday due to the celebration of the National Day of Peace (CDVR, 2016). The effective implementation of these measures requires the establishment of an Advisory Committee attached to the structure responsible for reparations and which ensures that victims receive what is promised to them by the government. This Committee should be composed of representatives of the Ministries concerned (for example, the Ministries of Solidarity, Health, Education, Economy and Finance, Defence, Interior, etc.), civil society organisations and victims' associations to ensure transparency and participation (CDVR, 2016).

1.5 Statement of the problem

On April 11, 2011, Laurent Gbagbo was arrested and Alassane Ouattara's victory recognised by the international community. Despite this crack in social cohesion, Ivorians must live together and collaborate. To achieve this, or to pass this difficult test, the new government of Alassane Ouattara has taken various measures, including the establishment of transitional justice mechanisms, a non-criminal justice approach to respond to the after-effects of serious and massive violations of human rights. With the beginning of reconciliation, President Ouattara took the initiative to create, by order no. 2011-167 of July 13, 2011, an extrajudicial mechanism: the Dialogue, Truth, and Reconciliation Commission (CDVR), which is supposed to lead to the restoration of the social bond deeply affected by the political violence of 1990 until the post-electoral crisis of 2011 (Akindès, 2017 p8). The mandate of this first Commission included the search for truth, dialogue, and hearing from victims. The CDVR approach was holistic, as it attempted to target both the national level and the level of communities and individuals (Piccolino, 2017, pp.17). Indeed, Piccolino explains that at the national level, the CDVR was supposed to reconstruct the history of political crises since 1990. At the community and individual level, it collected the testimonies of community leaders and victims of the crisis, through its regional offices. However, after three (3) years, the president of the CDVR submitted his final report including an action plan for

national reconciliation to the President of the Republic (Calame and Hubrecht, 2015, pp.22). The CDVR made many recommendations, including the effective application of the rural land law, better consideration of the situation of women, reduction of inequalities in regional development (CDVR, 2014, pp. 104). Despite these recommendations, the CDVR's actions leave a taste of unfinished business. On Tuesday March 24, 2015, another order of the President of the Republic created a new institution, which is the National Commission for Reconciliation and Compensation of Victims (CONARIV). The objective of the latter is to complete the work of the CDVR, both through research and identification of victims and beneficiaries of unidentified victims, and through relevant proposals for compensation for damage resulting from attacks on persons and real estate crises in Côte d'Ivoire. Despite the establishment of the second commission and the reconciliation measures put in place by the government and non-governmental organisations since 2011, the forecasts are not optimistic because not only are peacebuilding efforts at a standstill, but games and political issues favour a certain freezing of peace. National and international observers such as the UN and Human Right Watch note that the situation at the national level, a certain political status quo, contradicts the official objectives of lasting peace and reconciliation (Charbonneau, 2013, pp. 10). If transitional justice mechanisms are effective, evidence should show a return to normal and lasting peace in the country.

A study aimed at understanding the restorative potential of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission could explain why peacebuilding efforts have stalled. This research is important because it aims to fill this gap in knowledge.

1.6 Research questions and objectives.

The central aim of this research is to examine the impact of the Truth Commission (TC) in Cote d'Ivoire. The thesis focuses on the impact of the Ivorian Truth Commission in the contexts of civil war and protracted social conflicts, and through a case study of the Ivorian truth commission, it seeks to answer the following overarching question:

What is the impact of the CDVR in promoting reconciliation by/through restorative justice?

From this question come the following subsidiary research questions:

RQ 1: How effectively has the ideal of consensus been operationalised within the CDVR?

RQ 2: How can an assessment of strengths and limitations be used to show the extent to which the CDVR has succeeded in its reconciliatory mission?

RQ 3: How could restorative justice methods be employed to further strengthen the work of the truth commission?

The key objectives of this research in service of these questions are:

Obj 1: To establish a framework for assessing the impact of TC on reconciliation through restorative justice to evaluate the impact of TC as a process and offer insight into causal mechanisms for supporting peacebuilding and reconciliation. [RQ 1; RQ 2; RQ 3].

Obj 2: Having designed the framework, to conduct targeted interviews to examine perceptions relating to the creation of the CDVR, the issue of consensus and gain additional insight into how the CDVR mandate has been operationalised in practice [RQ 1; RQ 3].

1.7 The significance of the study

The choice of restorative justice as the framework for assessing the legitimacy and effectiveness of the Commission for Dialogue, Truth, and Reconciliation (CDVR) stems from a crucial understanding that justice systems must encompass more than just punitive actions. In societies that have experienced conflict, such as Côte d'Ivoire, characterized by a history of political violence and significant social rifts, it is vital to adopt an approach that emphasizes healing, restoration, and transformation (Cohen, 2013). Restorative justice facilitates this shift by moving the focus from punishment to repair and from exclusion to inclusion, thereby paving the way for reconciliation (Zupančič, 2019).

Conventional justice systems typically prioritize prosecution and punishment, which may prove insufficient in post-conflict settings where widespread human rights violations have taken place. In the context of Côte d'Ivoire, a purely punitive strategy could deepen existing community divisions, making it both impractical and

counterproductive (Hamber, 2018). Conversely, restorative justice offers a more inclusive framework that reframes essential inquiries: Who has suffered, and what measures can be taken to address that suffering? This approach promotes a comprehensive strategy aimed at healing societal rifts rather than merely attributing blame (Braithwaite, 2002).

Restorative justice emphasizes the needs of victims, positioning them at the heart of the justice process. Unlike traditional legal systems that often sideline victims by treating them as passive observers focused on legal technicalities, restorative practices empower victims to recount their experiences and express their pain (Shapland et al., 2011). This participatory approach enhances the legitimacy of the Commission, ensuring that justice is not only delivered but also resonates with those who have been most affected.

The Commission's legitimacy and effectiveness are closely linked to its capacity to foster enduring peace and reconciliation. Justice should extend beyond merely addressing past injustices; it must also work to avert future violence. Restorative practices play a vital role in this process by facilitating communication between victims and offenders, tackling root causes of conflict, and encouraging mutual understanding, all of which help diminish the chances of renewed violence (Nussbaum, 2019).

A significant obstacle in post-conflict justice is the reintegration of offenders into society. An exclusively punitive approach risks alienating those who may find it difficult to reintegrate after serving their sentences (Gordon, 2017). In contrast, restorative justice prioritizes rehabilitation over exclusion, providing a framework that encourages offenders to acknowledge their actions and contribute positively to their communities. This method not only benefits the individuals involved but also fortifies the social cohesion essential for lasting peace (Latz, 2020).

The Commission's efforts go beyond merely addressing individual cases; it is instrumental in repairing the social fabric of Côte d'Ivoire. To tackle the divisions that led to conflict, it is essential to engage with communities, fostering a culture of accountability, empathy, and coexistence. By encouraging direct interactions among affected individuals, restorative justice helps to rebuild trust in ways that conventional legal systems often fail to achieve (Hamber & Van der Merwe, 2008).

The implementation of restorative justice positions the Commission in alignment with global best practices in transitional justice. Notable examples of successful reconciliation initiatives, such as South Africa's Truth and Reconciliation Commission and Rwanda's Gacaca courts, have effectively integrated restorative principles (Hayner, 2011). By adopting a comparable approach, Côte d'Ivoire not only bolsters its international credibility but also signals a dedication to a justice system that is both effective and compassionate. This strategic alignment is likely to attract international support and collaboration, which are essential for the nation's post-conflict reconstruction efforts.

In summary, the pursuit of justice in post-conflict Côte d'Ivoire should extend beyond a simple legal framework; it must also create pathways toward a more promising future. Restorative justice offers a comprehensive approach that transforms justice into a mechanism for healing, restoration, and reconciliation. The Commission has the capacity to mend societal wounds, rebuild trust, and establish a foundation for a peaceful society that is resilient to future challenges.

By adopting the principles of restorative justice, Côte d'Ivoire can transcend its history of division and violence. The success of the Commission should not be gauged merely by the number of convictions but by the extent of healing it fosters. Justice must prioritize the needs of the people, address their traumas, and restore their dignity. Only by embracing a justice system that values healing over retribution, inclusion over exclusion, and peace over revenge can Côte d'Ivoire genuinely move forward and create a future where justice and reconciliation coexist harmoniously.

The assessment of the Ivorian Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) through the lens of restorative justice carries profound implications across various fields, such as transitional justice, conflict resolution, governance, and socio-political stability. This examination highlights the potential of truth commissions to play a pivotal role in fostering national healing and reconciliation in the aftermath of conflict.

By evaluating the Ivorian TRC in relation to restorative justice principles, this research investigates its success in mending relationships, facilitating healing, and ensuring accountability, while also offering valuable insights for policymakers seeking to improve future truth commissions (Mendeloff, 2004). Identifying potential weaknesses,

such as limited victim engagement or inadequate enforcement mechanisms, can guide enhancements in the legal and institutional frameworks that underpin reconciliation initiatives in Côte d'Ivoire and similar post-conflict settings.

Furthermore, this analysis considers whether the Ivorian TRC succeeded in promoting authentic reconciliation among various communities, political groups, and between victims and perpetrators of violence. By scrutinizing its effects through the restorative justice framework, we assess the efficacy of mechanisms such as truth-telling, apologies, and reparations in alleviating societal tensions and rebuilding trust (De Greiff, 2009). The focus on victim healing and the reintegration of offenders into society offers a holistic perspective on the operational dynamics of the TRC, advocating for increased victim involvement in future peace and justice endeavours.

Côte d'Ivoire's experience with its Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) offers significant insights for other nations grappling with similar post-conflict justice issues. By analysing the application of restorative principles within this context, the research can assist other countries in crafting more effective reconciliation strategies that adeptly balance the elements of truth, justice, and peace.

This investigation enhances the scholarly discourse surrounding the efficacy of truth commissions by providing empirical data from Côte d'Ivoire. It adds to the ongoing debate regarding the advantages of retributive versus restorative justice models and identifies the variables that affect the success or failure of these initiatives (Hayner, 2011). A well-functioning TRC can establish a foundation for lasting peace by tackling the underlying causes of conflict. By assessing the Ivorian TRC's effectiveness in curbing future violence, this study contributes to the sustainability of peace efforts, ensuring they are not merely short-term solutions.

In conclusion, this research goes beyond a binary assessment of the Ivorian Truth Commission's achievements or shortcomings. It offers actionable recommendations for improving reconciliation processes, thereby assisting policymakers in strengthening transitional justice frameworks. Furthermore, it supports peacebuilding efforts in Côte d'Ivoire and other regions. By emphasizing the principles of restorative justice, this study highlights the critical roles of truth, accountability, and healing in

post-conflict environments, making it an asset for scholars, government entities, and international organizations involved in conflict resolution.

1.8 Structure of the thesis

Chapter one presents the context of the study, the main research question, and the specific questions that guide the study.

Chapter two reviews and presents research on transitional justice, restorative justice and truth commissions.

Chapter three presents the conceptual framework within which the thesis fits and determines the relationship between restorative justice and reconciliation by focusing on the needs of victims and the responsibility of the perpetrator to repair the harm caused.

Chapter four presents the research methodology and justifies its choice. The chapter also presents the choice of population to interview and the size of the research sample. Also, the data collection methods used, analysis and interpretation of the data are presented. The relevance of the methods used is also explored. The first section examined the design frameworks used. Restorative justice and theory of change are introduced as methods for evaluating CDVR design. In this chapter, the reasons for choosing CDVR as a case study are explained. The second section of the chapter discusses the collection and analysis of data through a literature review and interviews. Discussions focus on researcher positionality, ethical and gender considerations that might be encountered during this research.

Chapter five presents a framework for assessing the impacts of truth commissions on promoting social cohesion and reconciliation. The first section of the chapter contextualises restorative justice and reconciliation within the field of transitional justice and within truth commissions. The second section determines the relationship between restorative justice and reconciliation by focusing on the needs of the victim and the responsibility of the perpetrator to repair the harm caused. Based on this relationship, the third section presents the argument that truth commissions contribute to reconciliation by judiciously integrating restorative justice into its process. To operationalise this argument and evaluate the impacts of truth

commissions, the fourth section establishes a framework composed of seven evaluation criteria.

Chapter six assesses the impact of the commissions (CDVR) created in Côte d'Ivoire. The first section of the chapter examines the context in which the creation of the commission took place. The second section provided an overview of the commission, its findings, and recommendations. The third section assessed the impact of the commission. The impact assessment follows the framework established in chapter five.

Chapter seven delineates how the research has furthered the aim and research questions of the thesis. The chapter seeks to demonstrate the empirical, conceptual, analytical, and methodological manner are described contributions.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

Transitional justice (TJ) has emerged as a critical field of study, particularly in post-conflict societies and states transitioning from authoritarian rule to democracy. It encompasses a range of judicial and non-judicial measures aimed at addressing past human rights violations, fostering reconciliation, and ensuring sustainable peace. Over the past few decades, scholars and practitioners have debated the effectiveness, scope, and limitations of transitional justice mechanisms, including truth commissions, criminal prosecutions, reparations, and institutional reforms.

This chapter provides a comprehensive review of the literature on transitional justice, tracing its historical evolution, theoretical foundations, and practical applications in different contexts. It examines key debates surrounding justice and reconciliation, the role of international and local actors, and the impact of TJ on long-term peace and development. Additionally, it explores challenges such as selectivity, victim participation, and the tension between peace and justice. By critically analysing existing research, this chapter seeks to identify gaps in the literature and provide a foundation for the study at hand.

2.1 Transitional Justice: The emergence of a paradigm

Transitional justice theories began to emerge suddenly, around the turn of the 1980s, long after conflicts and human rights abuses in societies and regime change (Buckley-Zistel *et al.*, 2014). The massive emergence of these theories at the international level has, for this reason, been portrayed in terms of "Cascade Justice" of a cultural, legal, and political nature (Sikkink, 2011). While its legal origins can be found in the post-war justice of Nuremberg (imprescriptibly of crimes) according to specialists, and its historical origins in Argentina (1983) (referring to precedents in Greece and Portugal), transitional justice has essentially been implemented in former colonies and emerging democracies in Eastern Europe, South Africa, and parts of the Middle East and Africa. Transitional justice was first implemented in Argentina and then in Chile after the fall of military dictatorships, in the context of what has been called the third wave of democratisation and discussions aimed at organising the transition from dictatorial regimes to democratic regimes. We could, all the same, return to the history of transitional justice which dates to the beginning of Athens, because in 411 BC, the

new democratic regime applied retribution policies against the removed oligarchy, it promulgated an amnesty law and, after the defeat of a second oligarchic regime, it developed reconciliation policies (Reiter, 2017).

The period when transitional justice is recognised is more than two thousand years later, especially during the English restoration (Elster, 2004). The defeat of France in 1814, the end of the American Civil War in 1865, and the end of World War I in 1918, among others, were other times when transitional justice played an important role. Indeed, during these different transitions, the first efforts of transitional justice focused on immediate punishment through exiles and executions or the development of amnesty policies that would allow societies to emerge from the violence that has happened in the past (Reiter, 2017). The foundations of transitional justice, as is commonly seen today, emerged after the war crimes committed by the Nazi regimes in the various countries, they occupied during World War II. Indeed, the allies decided that to deal with the various crimes that occurred during the war, individual criminal responsibility in a public trial should be pursued (Reiter, 2017).

To achieve the central goal of justice, international trials, notably the Nuremberg Trials and the Tokyo Trials, were established based on prosecuting war criminals in the aftermath of World War II. The Nuremberg trials in Germany were held from November 14, 1945, to October 1, 1946. The main Nazi leaders were tried by an International Military Tribunal (IMT) made up of the United States, the United Kingdom, the USSR, the United States and France. The tribunal defines 4 charges: conspiracy, crimes against peace, war crimes and crimes against humanity. According to Lavon (2005), the trial concerns 24 German political, military, and economic leaders and 4 organisations: the NSDAP (Nazi Party), the Gestapo, the SS, and the SD (Security Service of the SS). Sigalit argued that the main objective of this trial was that the Allies wanted to show democratic notions of justice to the world. These trials were therefore one of the first real collaborative efforts in international justice and have become the foundation of modern international criminal law (Reiter, 2017).

Indeed, although much critical and controversial, the international military tribunal of Nuremberg constitutes a decisive innovation for the development of an international criminal law with the definition of crimes, such as crimes against humanity, and the

use of documents, including images, to indict the Nazi system (Reiter, 2017). Crimes against humanity are defined by article 6 of the London Charter:

“Assassination, extermination, enslavement, deportation, and any other inhuman act committed against all civilian populations, before or during the war, or persecution for political, racial or religious reasons, when these acts or persecutions, whether or not they constituted a violation of the internal law of the country where they were perpetrated, were committed as a result of any crime falling within the jurisdiction of the Tribunal, or in connection with this crime”.

(Article 6, the London Charter of August 8, 1945)

Thus, the international military tribunal of Nuremberg served in part as a model for the tribunal which sits in Tokyo from May 3, 1946, to November 12, 1948. There was therefore, through the Nuremberg trials, a notable shift from national justice to international justice (Teitel, 2003). Asmal (2000) describes this military tribunal as an exercise in "victor's justice" since the judges and trial prosecutors were all representatives of the Allied Powers. Likewise, it was the victorious states that created the legal law of the tribunal. Furthermore, the Allies are very far from being innocent in the war and researchers have shown that certain crimes committed by the victors could have answered all the accusations, notably the two atomic bombs dropped on Nagasaki and Hiroshima on August 6 and 9, 1945. Since the mid-1970s and for almost two decades, there have been democratic upheavals in several states, including Argentina, Chile, Rwanda, and South Africa. During this period, several countries, including those in the former colonies and emerging democracies in Eastern Europe, South Africa and parts of the Middle East and Africa, have moved from an authoritarian regime to democracy (Reiter, 2017). During this transition, debates on transitional justice have been dominated by the role of trials and the definition of crimes against humanity as defined in the Nuremberg trials. For example, in many countries, including Argentina and Chile, experts in international law were reluctant to punish or condone atrocities (Leebaw, 2008). Leebaw argued that in the context of the transition of Argentina in 1984 and Chile in 1990, other regimes debated whether to sanction or condone human rights violations committed under a previous regime (Leebaw, 2008). The relative power of the former authoritarian actors maintained the transitional

justice decisions taken, as many states, including South Africa, Nepal, Argentina, and Chile, had to compromise between justice and peace. In addition, the field of transitional justice, formerly dominated by lawyers and jurists, is now opening in the academic world, more particularly in the social and human sciences. In Latin America, for example, a truth commission was created, as a new approach to transitional justice. This commission would be a temporary institution designed to investigate past human rights violations and hold account for crimes while ensuring the healing and closure of victims (Reiter, 2017).

In addition, truth commissions have been encouraged in several transition countries as alternatives to prosecution and as a means of combating crimes against humanity (Fischer, 2011). The truth commissions are often associated with the famous South African Truth and Reconciliation Commission; however, this transitional justice mechanism was first used in Argentina (Teitel, 2003; Reiter, 2017). Indeed, the CONADEP (National Commission on the Disappeared), set up in 1983 in Argentina, is in fact considered to be the first true CVR. The institution was then taken up in several countries including Bolivia, Uruguay, Sierra Leone, Uganda, Rwanda, and Sri Lanka, where it experienced many changes and adaptations (Rosmade, 2014).

The first truth commissions are most often responsible for investigating one or two specific types of crimes over a period. For example, commissions of inquiry into disappearances (a specific type of crime) have emerged in several countries, including the National Commission for Disappearances of Argentina in 1983, the Commission of Inquiry into the Situation of "Disappeared" and its cases in Uruguay in 1985, the Commission of Inquiry into Disappearances in Nepal in 1990 and the Presidential Commission on Disappearances in Sri Lanka in 1998 (Rosmade, 2014). The central objective of these commissions at the time was to find out the truth about the fate of these missing persons. These commissions of inquiry are not judicial bodies. Rather, they establish the root causes of the disappearances and the perpetrators. After having located the responsibilities and provided the list of the missing, the commissions make recommendations for the non-repetition of kidnappings, the victims, institutional reforms, or assistance to the victims. The implementation of the recommendations depends on the government. Perhaps one of the best-known episodes of mass enforced disappearances of the 20th century is Argentina's last

dictatorship. When the army was in power in that country between 1976 and 1983, security forces abducted around 30,000 people, many of whom have still not been found. Widespread and systematic human rights violations have been committed, including acts of torture and large-scale extrajudicial killings including the infamous “death flights”, where victims were thrown from military airplanes or helicopters, with no possibility of survival. International organisations such as Amnesty International have long campaigned for justice for these victims and for convicted military and government officials to be convicted. Many of them have also been brought to justice in ordinary civil courts in recent years. Lefranc (2006) noted that commissions of inquiry were widely used in the 1980s and 1990s as a default means of obtaining truth and justice because they could not force perpetrators to confess. From the 1990s, commissions of inquiry began to be rejected by truth and reconciliation commissions. According to (Reiter, 2017), these commissions are temporary institutions designed to investigate and report on past crimes and human rights violations. From the early 1990s to date, a lot of money has been invested in transitional justice mechanisms in several countries including South Sudan and Afghanistan (Weinstein, 2011). In South Sudan, a multi-donor trust fund of \$ 545 million was established in 2005, with funding from 14 donors and in Afghanistan the UNDP established the Afghan Interim Authority Fund (AIAF), supported by 24 donors, and valued at \$ 73 million, for a limited period of six months, to ensure payment of the most pressing needs in the restoration of the civil service.

Former Secretary General Kofi Annan, in his 2004 report entitled “Rule of law and transitional justice in societies in conflict and post-conflict situations”, underlined the normative commitment of the United Nations in favour of transitional justice (Bell, 2009). Vinjamuri (2010) added that transitional justice becomes a daily debate in international aid and development organisations, as well as among mediators who are invited to include transitional justice mechanisms in their peace negotiations. According to the World Bank's 2011 World Development Report, there are links between transitional justice, security, and development. The report also confirms the appointment of a special rapporteur on promoting truth, justice, reparations and ensuring the non-replication of serious crimes and gross human rights violations to the Human Rights Council. Thus, the Truth and Reconciliation Commissions are non-judicial bodies responsible for investigating, generally in times of political unrest or

violence, with the mission of producing a final report that will provide conclusions on the causes of this violence, on civil liability and make recommendations either on institutional reforms or on victim assistance. These commissions seek above all to establish facts about a radical period of transition, before making recommendations on how to achieve reconciliation between the warring parties, and society, hence their name Commission of truth and reconciliation. Its creation was therefore promoted as alternatives to prosecution and as a means of combating cultures of denial (Fischer, 2011). As mentioned above, the first truth commissions were operational in Argentina and spread immediately. The success of this mechanism in South Africa is now linked to this country which has experienced serious human rights violations under apartheid (Teitel, 2003; Reiter, 2017).

After the success of the transitional justice process in South Africa, the field of transitional justice has grown, and its application has spread across societies emerging from serious conflicts or human rights violations such as Rwanda, Liberia, Sierra Leone, Peru, and Canada. The success of the transitional justice process has led to the establishment of several hybrid courts and the International Criminal Court. The concept of transitional justice has gained influence among academics and human rights scholars as a new field of study since the 1990s (Buckley-Zistel *et al.*, 2014). It is nevertheless important to remember that the term "transitional justice" was coined by Teitel in 1991 with the aim of clarifying the conscious construction of a creation of justice by countries associated with periods of radical political transition replacing a past oppressive regime (Teitel, 2008).

At that time, transitional justice appeared as a solution to talk about serious violations of human rights and to facilitate political transitions in several countries in Latin America and Eastern Europe. Since then, transitional justice measures have continued to be applied in post-conflict contexts and in countries that have not experienced significant political transition and even in countries still in conflict (Duthie, 2011). Over time, the concept gradually broadened its meaning (Fischer, 2011). For this and other reason, there is not a single theory on transitional justice known to all that can be applied in all contexts. Conversely, it is a common term for approaches that deal with the past in the aftermath of violent conflict or political transition (Buckley-Zistel *et al.*, 2014). This great pluralism of approaches could be explained by the fact

that the field of transitional justice is interdisciplinary because it covers several disciplines including sociology, law, psychology, political sciences, and social sciences (Buckley-Zistel *et al.*, 2014). This growth in multidisciplinary studies on the management of countries emerging from conflict or human rights violations has fostered a multitude of methodologies in its operation according to the context of each crisis and each country (Hughes and Kostovicova, 2018). The absence of theory on transitional justice can also be explained by the fact that each country has its context. The success of a transitional justice approach can be enhanced or can be adapted to the context of another country but cannot demonstrate a universal theory (Buckley-Zistel *et al.*, 2014). Kritz (2009) indicates that many scholars believe it is a mistake to say that a successful approach to transitional justice in one country can be applied in other transition states as a model to follow. As for Van der Merwe, Baxter, and Chapman (2009), they confirm that a universal theory is neither desirable nor appropriate in the field of transitional justice because the achievement of objectives is difficult on the ground. They add that these objectives could conflict with each other due to the complexity of the context. On the other hand, many researchers interested in transitional justice as a normative activity, which can lead to losing sight of reality. Loyle and Davenport (2016) that transitional justice offers only positive intentions, good objectives, which makes the current framework of the concept problematic. Some governments may therefore hide transitional justice to make people believe that they are trying to pinpoint responsibility in each situation, but they are using identical judicial institutions for destructive purposes. This idea of using transitional justice for other purposes makes the notion confusing. This is also another reason for the lack of theory in the field. Loyle and Davenport (2016) also noted that transitional justice mechanisms promote transitional injustice, with transitional justice based on tangible normative assumptions that can be misused and in turn can undermine goals. Under these conditions, transitional justice can hardly achieve its objectives for either a lack of clarity in the process or for petty political ambitions. In some countries, such as Serbia, the mandates of truth and reconciliation commissions are terminated prematurely due to the lack of clarity of their efforts. In Serbia, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission was dissolved prematurely because it became a political instrument instead of an independent cohesion instrument. Teitel (2008) adds that certain specialists in transitional justice consider that the normative effects of transitional justice are likely to advance the rule of law and security in the countries

where it must be applied. Today there are many conflict zones around the world. To this end, transitional justice focuses much more on relevant issues, a broader international commitment to human security, and not primarily on normative issues of dealing with a state through its violent past (Teitel, 2008). The success of transitional justice has made it an international instrument. In this regard, it has international and global normative scope that affects the debates and structure of international affairs (Potgieter, 2017).

Despite the many critiques of transitional justice, the term appears to be widely used in many countries (Reta, 2017). Buckley-Zistel *et al.*, (2014) indicate that transitional justice encompasses a significant number of formal and informal institutions and mechanisms that can all help to right past wrongs, preserve the dignity of victims and deliver justice in times of transition. Formal and informal transitional justice institutions and mechanisms include courts, truth commissions, reparations, and draft memorandums (Buckley-Zistel *et al.*, 2014). Formal or informal mechanisms of transitional justice, Van der Merwe *et al.* (2009) argue that they can be international organisations and formal legal structures codified in treaties and laws, but also regional or national bodies that depend on voluntary processes and traditional values. States and international organisations see truth commissions as a good mechanism to set up after violent conflicts between ethnic, religious, or political groups, leading to serious atrocities or human rights violations. These truth commissions can help prevent the ardour of some actors from blaming the blame for human rights violations and past crimes with their ethnic, religious, or political opponents. In this situation, it is desirable for truth commissions to be truly independent and impartial to avoid political manipulation. Kritz (2009) justified the creation of the truth commission as a means of engaging society in a painful national dialogue, trying to examine the root causes that have caused these conflicts and atrocities, to avoid repetitions and above all to push the company to continue collaborating. Although there are multiple approaches and measures of transitional justice, they all have the same objective as they are all concerned with preventing states, society, and institutions from repeating the incriminating acts of the past which led to repression, to war and personal loss (Mihir, 2016).

According to Duthie (2011), the different mechanisms and measures of transitional justice constitute a holistic approach to the concept. All transitional justice mechanisms have the same objective, but each mechanism has a specific role. Some transitional justice mechanisms attempt to situate responsibilities or reconcile protagonists, other mechanisms focus on building trust in institutions, and other mechanisms attempt to recognise and recall past injustices through apologies, memorials, compensations, or any other legal means (Mihir, 2016). This is the case in South Africa where the mandate of the TRC created in 1995 was to investigate human rights violations that occurred during part of Apartheid, that is from 1960 to 1994. The Commission included three investigative sub-committees: The Amnesty Committee, the Human Rights Violations Committee and the Reparation and Rehabilitation Committee, whose objectives are different in nature, but not divergent. The Human Rights Violations Subcommittee was charged with investigating the crimes; the reparation and rehabilitation subcommittee was responsible for making recommendations to compensate the surviving victims and the families of the victims; the task of the amnesty subcommittee was to judge cases falling under the Amnesty Law which provided for amnesty for crimes meeting conditions defined by law, in exchange for full confessions from their authors (Tutu, 2000, p.38).

The main objective of transitional justice is to create a peaceful society, cohabitation, and collaboration between peoples, in a word the objective is to reconcile the societies in conflict by the good of its mechanisms (Merwe, Baxter and Chapman, 2009). In the meantime, there are some secondary goals which when combined can help achieve the primary goal. According to Merwe, Baxter, and Chapman (2009), some other goals of transitional justice are to promote a democratic political order in which human rights are respected, and to encourage means to avoid future atrocities. At the same time as the various mechanisms and measures of transitional justice aim to face an unjust or atrocious past, these mechanisms and measures also aim to restore and legitimize a new political regime (Mihir, 2016). Also, Mihir (2016) distinguishes two transitional justice processes: an inclusive process of transitional justice and an exclusive process of transitional justice. The author defines the inclusive transitional justice process as the process that includes all parties or members who have been involved in a dictatorship or past conflict. By including all parties, the inclusive process does not consider their political or social status, religious or ethnic origins. The inclusive

transitional justice process can involve victims and perpetrators in the process to achieve its goals. This inclusive process can be a reason to condemn barbarism but also to hold all parties accountable.

Compared to the inclusive process, the exclusive transitional justice process is, in most cases, victim and perpetrator focused (Mihr, 2016). In this case, the author argues, the new government sees the victims and perpetrators as the aggressors of the previous regime and thus the antagonists of the current political justice. In such a case, it is said the justice of the winner. Mihr (2016) adds that there is not purely inclusive or exclusive transitional justice process in practice. It all depends on how States or international organisations conduct the process, and particularly the objectives set. The case of Rwanda represents a far-reaching example of transitional justice. It reveals how the combination of international, national, and traditional criminal prosecutions can both facilitate and limit the process of justice and reconciliation. For example, the gacaca courts were part of a context of transition following the genocide of 1994. In disagreement with several orientations and decisions taken by the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (Graybill, 2004) and because of the Slowness in its process, the new Rwandan government adopted a law in August 1996 authorizing the State to bring genocidal perpetrators to justice. However, the genocide spared few judges and lawyers (Wierzynski, 2004), many of them themselves genocidal and imprisoned. Mihr (2016) argues that states or international organizations tend to favour one or the other transitional justice process, which has had a positive impact on how transitional justice has helped stabilise and strengthen new political regimes (Mihr, 2016). Whatever mechanisms each state chooses, they will necessarily have an impact on the inclusiveness or exclusivity of the transitional justice process. Vu Lan (2014) advises that to study the effects of different mechanisms and forms of transitional justice, long-term analysis or systematic empirical research is needed. He advises gathering a lot of evidence on the impact of these mechanisms on victims, perpetrators, and society. This can help to know the success or failure of the mechanisms put in place. Knowledge of the objectives and context of the establishment of the mechanisms are very important elements for the evaluation of transitional justice mechanisms (Fischer, 2011). Merwe and Lykes (2016) explain that the capacity of these mechanisms to contribute to a culture of compassion and to the creation of a new social contract is still uncertain.

Although a great number of changes occur during the process, one realises that a lot remains unchanged, including the experiences of racial, ethnic, or political exclusion, the marginalisation of certain social classes, the root causes conflicts, and even the behaviour and attitudes of the protagonists (Merwe, Baxter, and Chapman, 2009). This will have a great influence on the degree of reconciliation of the society (Merwe, Baxter, and Chapman, 2009). Transitional justice is based on four central measures: trials, the revelation of the truth, reparations, and administrative reforms, which are supposed to guarantee four objectives: recognition, trust, the rule of law and, ultimately, reconciliation (UN, 2012). If these measures have existed for a long time, it is their justification by reference to universal human rights and a democratic aim that is new.

2.2 The impact of document destruction on accountability and legalism

This section explores the relationship between document destruction, legalism, and their implications for reconciliation, non-recurrence, and nation-building in post-conflict societies. Document destruction often serves as a tactic to undermine the establishment of accountability and transparency, which are vital for progressive legal frameworks. When critical records of human rights violations are destroyed, it not only erases historical truths but also impedes the efforts of legal institutions to prosecute offenders and foster accountability.

The role of legalism in post-conflict societies

Legalism, in this context, refers to the reliance on legal frameworks and formal judicial processes to achieve justice and promote social order. However, when document destruction occurs, the efficacy of these legal systems is severely compromised, leading to a lack of trust in state institutions and a threat to societal stability. The failure to acknowledge past atrocities complicates the processes of reconciliation and impedes efforts to prevent future conflicts. Furthermore, the interconnections among reconciliation, non-recurrence, and nation-building are essential to understanding how societies can move forward after conflict. Reconciliation efforts rely on an accurate historical record, which is often hindered by document destruction. To build a cohesive national identity, societies must confront their past and ensure that justice is served for victims of violence and oppression.

Holistic strategies for sustainable peace and development

In summary, the destruction of documents poses significant challenges to legalism and the establishment of a fair justice system, ultimately affecting the broader goals of reconciliation, non-recurrence, and nation-building. This highlights the importance of safeguarding historical records and institutional integrity as key components of sustainable peace and development. Reconciliation aims to mend historical divisions, while non-recurrence focuses on preventing future conflicts, and nation-building fosters long-term stability through inclusive governance and socio-economic advancement. Societies that overlook the integration of these processes may face instability, especially in post-conflict contexts where reconciliation efforts lack adequate institutional support or where preventive measures fail to curb the resurgence of violence. Consequently, effective nation-building requires a holistic strategy that encompasses truth, justice, reform, and inclusivity, thereby nurturing a cohesive and resilient society. It is both essential and urgent to address the interconnections among reconciliation, non-recurrence, and nation-building to formulate strategies that promote peace and facilitate development in post-conflict environments.

Historical examples of document destruction in conflicts

In times of conflict, the act of destroying documents serves a dual function: it is both a strategy for survival and a method of oppression. A comparative examination of pivotal historical instances, including the Rwandan Genocide (1994), the Bosnian War (1992-1995), and Argentina's Dirty War (1976-1983), demonstrates how the obliteration of documents has obstructed accountability and hindered reparative measures. For example, in Rwanda, many individuals chose to destroy their identity cards, which indicated their ethnic identity, to escape targeted violence during the genocide. However, this destruction severely complicated post-genocide efforts to seek reparations or assert property rights due to the lack of official records (Eltringham, 2004). In the context of Bosnia and Herzegovina, military operations resulted in the intentional destruction of property records and other essential documents, which impeded post-war restitution efforts. The Commission for Real Property Claims of Displaced Persons and Refugees (CRPC) was forced to rely on alternative evidence, such as witness accounts, to adjudicate claims (Peterson, 2010; Hadžihalilović, 2021).

Likewise, in Argentina, the military government systematically eliminated records related to forced disappearances to conceal evidence of human rights abuses, creating significant obstacles for families seeking to ascertain the fate of their missing relatives (Crenzel, 2011). These instances highlight how the destruction of documents functions as both a survival tactic and a tool of repression. Nevertheless, once the conflict has ended, the resultant lack of documentation greatly restricts victims' ability to access justice and obtain reparations.

Challenges for transitional justice and the need for adaptability

Transitional justice mechanisms often depend on documentation to substantiate claims, creating a challenging scenario where the lack of official records results in exclusion, an excessive reliance on legal procedures, and an unfair burden of proof on victims. This issue has been particularly evident in post-genocide Rwanda, where survivors without formal documentation of land ownership face considerable obstacles in reclaiming their properties (Burnet, 2012; Ongwen, 2020). Many transitional justice systems function within strict legal frameworks that prioritize the necessity for documentation and formal evidence to promote procedural fairness. However, these methods may unintentionally disregard the complexities encountered in post-conflict environments, where vital records may have been lost or destroyed (McEvoy, 2007). Legalistic approaches often place the onus of proof on victims, requiring them to validate their claims of suffering. In cases where records have been intentionally eliminated, this demand can exacerbate the victimization of those already affected (Teitel, 2000). Legalism in the realm of transitional justice pertains to the pre-eminence of established legal mechanisms, such as judicial systems, truth commissions, and reparations initiatives, that may eclipse more flexible, victim-focused strategies (McEvoy, 2007). Detractors of legalism contend that it frequently neglects alternative evidence forms, fails to consider the socio-political contexts of the communities involved, and limits access to justice. In situations where official documentation has been destroyed, as seen in Sierra Leone during its civil conflict, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission confronted these obstacles by heavily relying on oral testimonies (Shaw, 2007; Kim & Kelsall, 2021). Furthermore, inflexible legal structures can inadvertently perpetuate existing power imbalances that disproportionately impact

marginalized populations, including displaced persons and women, who are often the most affected by the lack of official records (Rubli, 2012; Anderson, 2021).

In conclusion, the consequences of document destruction in post-conflict societies extend far beyond immediate survival tactics, profoundly impacting the prospects for healing, justice, and stability. The cases discussed demonstrate how the lack of documentation severely undermines legal mechanisms and transitional justice processes, leaving victims in a state of limbo, deprived of their rights and recognition. To create a just society that fosters reconciliation and non-recurrence, stakeholders must prioritize the development of adaptable frameworks that can recognize various forms of evidence. Emphasizing inclusivity and the involvement of affected communities can enhance the effectiveness of transitional justice initiatives. Moving forward, it is critical to preserve historical records and engage in comprehensive documentation efforts, thereby illuminating the path toward accountability and sustainable peace in societies healing from the scars of conflict. Ultimately, fostering a culture of truth and justice is imperative for building resilient and cohesive communities capable of preventing future violence and promoting long-term national stability.

2.3 Truth commissions

The first well-known truth Commission was established in 1983 in Argentina under the name of the National Commission on the Disappeared. Over the past 30 years or so, several Truth Commissions have emerged around the world (Llewellyn, 2013). A Truth Commission is generally charged with finding out the truth on a particular subject or an era, hearing witnesses, making inquiries, analysing documents and consulting experts (Leman-Langlois, 2006). It is about confronting society with its painful and shameful past to turn the page on national reconciliation. Forgetting as a means of dealing with past crimes is rejected and, truth and narrative through justice are recommended (Matignon, 2010). The objective is to seek the truth through the testimony of offenders and victims, who must find a real place of listening and public recognition of their suffering. The function of the Truth Commissions goes beyond that of retributive justice that punishes, condemns, and compensates since they are the site of historical narrative and political truth. In other words, they are an unprecedented place for dialogue in a battered and torn society.

The objective is the reconciliation of a people but first the appeasement of the burden of silence through the narrative which, without it, would continue to turn every day a little more into a negation of the suffering suffered. As for the course of the process, the Truth Commissions constitute a stage in a long process and their implementation is specific to the specificities of each country. Generally, the mandate of the committees is eighteen months. They are made up of commissioners whose number and nationality vary according to the case and, following their exercise, a report is published and widely distributed. The Truth Commissions are concerned with achieving a better understanding of the past, applying wider remedies, and ensuring the independence of their work. They aim to place the victim at the centre of the process, to promote a form of dialogue between victim and perpetrator and to ensure that another form of reparation is offered (Matignon, 2010). The first two Truth and Reconciliation Commissions were established in 1990, one in Chile, and the other in Nepal. Their establishment and operation are not yet formalised, which makes them hesitant bodies, with moderate effectiveness.

The Nepal Truth Commission is dissolved after two months of activity, replaced by a Commission of Inquiry, which proves that the Truth Commission has not yet found its place in national democratisation. While Chile's National Truth and Reconciliation Commission went to the end of its term, issuing a final report in 1991, it was not made public. Moreover, this Commission did not enjoy real cooperation from the government. For example, she did not have access to military documents capable of providing evidence to witnesses. In addition, the Commission was not unanimous since its mandate excluded all human rights violations other than murders and disappearances of persons, so that a "national corporation for reparation and reconciliation Was created in 1994 to continue its work (Hayner, 1994, p. 162), which tends to prove that it was incomplete. In fact, the first two Truth and Reconciliation Commissions seem to hesitate between the old model of Investigative Commissions and a new, truly formalised approach with South Africa. South Africa's Truth Reconciliation Commission is now touted as the most successful initiative of any commission. It represents a significant development in Truth Commissions as institutional models of restorative justice. As a reaction to apartheid, a crime against humanity, it was born in 1995 thanks to its promoters, Nelson Mandela, leader of the ANC (African National Congress) and Archbishop Desmond Tutu (president of the

Truth and Reconciliation Commissions which wanted to rebuild their country based on national reconciliation and the policy of forgiveness and brought together the entire population to invest in this unprecedented process. By affirming that “words hurt but silence kills”, Desmond Tutu summarised the philosophy of this transitional mechanism (Tutu, 2000). This restorative device is developed and based on the concept of Ubuntu (Louw, 2006) presented as intrinsic to an African culture that favours reconciling justice. Ubuntu is a concept coming from sub-Saharan Africa which has its origin in the Bantu languages of South Africa. The Truth Commission had a threefold purpose that is shed light on the past, reconcile the nation and lay the foundations for a better future (Leman-Langlois, 2006, p. 209-218).

South Africa's Truth Reconciliation Commission was made up of three committees. The Human Rights Violations Committee was responsible for collecting in writing the testimonies of victims, considered to be bearers of truth, out of 20,000 cases, 2,000 were heard in person. During public hearings, the victim could freely relate what had happened, without having to demonstrate or prove anything. She spoke directly to the Commissioners (between 3 and 5, a total of 21 in 4 regions), and a few questions were asked if any of them felt that some important material was missing from the testimony. The victim and his companions were seated at a table arranged directly in front of the commissioners. Such a process is therefore centred on the person of the victim. The committee on reparation and rehabilitation aimed to develop a system of compensation for victims and that of reconversion of South African civil institutions. Finally, the committee on amnesty aimed to study requests for amnesty from perpetrators of past crimes. By law, applicants had to reveal all the details of their actions to be able to obtain amnesty. Most victims and relatives of victims objected, claiming that details were still missing, one of only two protest strategies available to them, unless they could directly contradict the facts presented (the other being to assert that the applicant had acted out of racism). After study of the case by the commissioners and their agreement, the case had to obtain the approval of the Parliament, which thus confirmed the act of amnesty. Of the 7,116 requests made, 1,312 were accepted. Overwhelmed by this burden, the committee had to continue to function more than two years after the official closure of the activities of the South African Truth and Reconciliation Commission. The Truth and Reconciliation Commission is not a jurisdiction even if there are similarities with such a body, it says

lawlessness and not law. However, this non-legal institution gives a legal answer: amnesty. It is therefore a hybrid body in the service of restorative justice.

Called a restorative approach as an effective response to mass crimes, the Truth Reconciliation Commission has not been spared by critics although the benefits are not denied. Controversies regarding its impact and functioning have been raised (Matignon, 2010). First, it is a very controversial system of amnesty, as it introduced forgiveness-based impunity into the process of national reconciliation. For some, amnesty was too easily granted and would have created a feeling of injustice among the people. The danger of an endorsement of impunity is a very real possibility and raises fears of a repeat of the violence of the past. The international community has also expressed some disapproval; it has expressed its fears against this mechanism of institutionalized impunity. Second, the judicial system has shown the lack of responsiveness or leniency that characterizes state prosecutions, when amnesty is denied or not requested.

In addition, the lack of personnel responsible for investigations within the Truth Reconciliation Commission as well as the lack of time and resources available to such a provisional body also led to questioning the veracity of the confessions made by the applicants for the amnesty. The excessiveness of the cost of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission, which has been in session for three years, which represents a budget of nearly 9 billion dollars per year, was also raised. Finally, the Reconciliation Truth Commission was unable to guarantee compensation and overall reparation (psychological and social) for the prejudices of most of the victims because the State had to structurally re-establish itself in exchange for the establishment of certain budgetary priorities. Indeed, the "instrumentalised" truth and this justice are guided by the political objective of national reconciliation and the amnesty is not granted on the principles of restorative justice, based on enlightened negotiation between the parties, but conditioned by a confession whose authenticity is difficult to verify. Thus, the restorative colour of the Reconciliation Truth Commission was attenuated during its institutionalization, even if this approach contributes to a concern for the revelation of the truth and the exercise of restorative justice (Leman-Langlois, 2006).

In Rwanda, another measure of a restorative nature was created through the rehabilitation of traditional courts for the reconciliation of the people after this violent conflict. From April to June 1994, eight hundred thousand Rwandan Tutsi were massacred all over the country. To bring justice was then the foundation on which one had to try to free the Rwandans from their painful memory to reconcile the people. This was one of the priorities of the new government put in place at the end of the genocide, which at the same time had to face a very difficult situation where the judicial system had to be restored. Faced with the enormous number of prisoners and genocide suspects at large and a pressing demand for rapid and effective justice from the survivors, new measures compared to existing legislation, and in this transitional situation, were invented by the Rwandan state. In 1996, the government adopted an organic law on the organization of the prosecution of offenses constituting the crime of genocide or crimes against humanity. The dominant features of this system are the hierarchy of criminal responsibilities; heavy penalties for genocide planners; lightened sentences for the executants.

Indeed, on this path, classical justice is privileged. Despite the innovations brought about by this law, it proved incapable of allowing the rapid trial of more than 100,000 defendants, the majority of whom were in prison. This impasse led the government to resort to alternative measures which gave rise to the organic law n ° 40/2000 of January 26, 2001, creating the Gacaca jurisdictions. These Gacaca courts are inspired by a traditional system of conflict resolution which is based on participatory justice and the virtues of reconciliation attributed to it. Originally, Gacaca courts met on the hills to settle neighbourhood or family disputes. They were very far from state justice. This Rwandan popular justice is based on the principle of conflict resolution negotiated and arbitrated by a sage whose respectability is recognized by the community (Matignon, 2010). Therefore, these traditional courts were not intended to determine guilt or to apply state law in a consistent and logical manner, but to restore harmony and social order in each society, and to reintegrate the person who was the source of the disorder (Vandeginste, 1999). Most of the conflicts settled by the Gacaca were of a civil nature, concerning property rights, marital problems, and damage to property. They could also intervene in certain minor crimes, such as theft. Sanctions made it possible to settle disputes, for example through the payment of compensation. Not only the individual, but his entire family, were held accountable for his actions (Hategekimana, 2011).

Qualifiable as participatory justice or local justice, the objectives of Gacaca courts are to establish the truth about the genocide (which took place between October 1, 1990, and December 31, 1994), to provide themselves with the means to accelerate justice, to heal wounds, to hold the perpetrators of violence accountable, to put an end to impunity, to reconcile Rwandans and to strengthen the unity of the people. To try those accused of genocide and other crimes against humanity, the Gacaca courts first checked and listed the victims, damages, and perpetrators of the genocide. Then, they divided the perpetrators into four categories, depending on the type of offense committed and their level of participation (Matignon, 2010). The first category includes planners, organizers, motivators, coaches, and supervisors. The maximum penalty for these crimes was the death penalty. The second category concerns individuals who are perpetrators, co-perpetrators or accomplices in intentional homicides or serious attacks against people who have resulted in death. The maximum penalty for this category was 25 to 30 years in prison. The third category includes those who have committed serious crimes without intention of causing the death of the victims. Finally, the fourth category consists of criminals against property. The penalties at this level consisted of compensation for damage. Category 1 defendants were intended to be tried by the ordinary (classic) justice system and the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (T.P.I.R.). The other categories were subject to the jurisdiction of the Gacaca Courts. Most perpetrators prosecuted for genocide fell into the second category.

The organisation of the courts was designed to reflect Rwanda's administrative system. Each court corresponded to an administrative division: the cell (between 150 and 300 people on average), the sector (including several cells), then the district and the province (Matignon, 2010). The Gacaca were made up of the Cell and Sector General Assembly and the Cell and Sector Coordination Committee. The Inyagamugayo judges (19 judges for each court) who sat in these courts were wise men or notables, qualified for their integrity. They had to meet certain conditions: not to have participated in the genocide, to be free from the spirit of division, to have good conduct, to be considered as having a good life and of good morals, to always speak the truth or to be characterised by the spirit of sharing the floor. They were elected by public ballot and received basic legal training. These courts had the power to question prosecution and defence witnesses, issue warrants or even order preventive detention. As for the procedure, the Gacaca courts have introduced a "confession and

guilty plea" which may give the right to reduced sentences and / or community service. To benefit from this, the accused had to give a detailed description of everything related to the offense, give information about the co-perpetrators and accomplices, and apologise for the atrocious acts committed.

Gacaca courts, whose origins can be traced back to traditional conflict resolution methods, are designed as a justice system that allows the participation of society. They introduce a unique and innovative character into questions of transitional justice. For the first time, an entire (adult) population is given the responsibility of trying individuals accused of the crime of genocide and other crimes against humanity. While most observers at the time agreed on the advantages of these jurisdictions, its restorative potential was nonetheless threatened by many pitfalls that called into question its ability to dispense justice (Hategekimana, 2011). These were above all the harsh socio-cultural realities that blocked the way towards restorative justice based on public participation. Indeed, the main limits of the implementation of a Gacaca were at the level of the extent and the nature of the popular participation because the success of such a mechanism required that this participation be active and voluntary and concerns all members of Rwandan society. Such participation would not only promote the revelation of the truth but would also reduce the mistrust and suspicion that characterised the relationship between victims and genocidaires in the post-genocide era. However, as a participatory justice system, the Gacaca have not succeeded sufficiently in involving the Rwandan people in the process as evidenced by the low participation rate of Rwandans. This decline in participation was due to several socio-cultural reasons: 1) the lack of information from the government regarding the main aspects of the process, giving rise to confusion, misinformation, and widespread disillusion, especially in the pilot phase. 2) fear of secondary victimisation; 3) fear of stigmatisation of perpetrators; 4) tensions between victims and genocidal criminals (since the first releases of prisoners in 2003), forced to rub shoulders in fear of each other, of the possibility of retaliation and murderous revenge; 5) Rwandan culture which does not privilege the word but the silence and the discretion which testify to a form of respect. Thus, the victims did not dare to speak out to tell the truth and express their suffering, and the perpetrators had difficulty recounting their crimes in public; 6) the impact of the significant economic sacrifice, because the time taken to participate in Gacaca directly impacts the agricultural work

essential to survival. The Gacaca are also relatively inefficient, concerning the reparation of victims, who in principle must play a key role in the process of “transitional justice” (Mabiala, 2009), at the same level as the search for truth and justice. Whatever its form, reparation has a special meaning, which can be likened to a kind of symbolic healing for the losses suffered, as well as a public recognition of the suffering. Despite the government's original desire to provide justice to the victims, the harsh realities of Rwanda did not allow the victims of the genocide to benefit from reparations for the totality of the damages: the resources of the State were inadequate to establish a national regime of fundable compensation. While reparations were envisaged as early as 2000, a whole series of questions remained unanswered: what form should this compensation take, in what terms should a beneficiary be defined and how should the victims be paid? Faced with the impossible reparation, the difficulty of forgiving intensified for the survivors, they experienced a feeling of bitter disenchantment and turned their backs on the Gacaca process. Finally, it should be remembered that the Gacaca courts were supposed to ensure a simple, rapid, and effective response to mass crimes.

However, by wanting to accelerate the course of justice to the detriment of quality (Hategekimana, 2011), they have ignored a certain number of key principles of justice, undermining the revelation of the truth and the dispensation of fair justice for all. Judges were unable to study the cases in detail, as a result, judgments were rushed, and defenders were not always given sufficient time. As for the final objective of the Gacaca process, namely national reconciliation, it could not put a definitive end to the conflict because reconciliation is part of a much broader concept that cannot be settled by a simple court of law justice. Many advocates of restorative justice and its detractors wonder if restorative justice really achieves what it promises. The appreciation of the impact of restorative measures on the protagonists of the conflict born of the offense is therefore inevitable to propagate its good aspects, improve those which are promising and eliminate those which do not conform to the philosophy of restorative justice.

2.4 Truth commissions and evaluating impacts.

Concerned were raised by scholars and practitioners on the functioning of transitional justice (Bell, 2009), It is often difficult to know exactly who is intended for transitional justice. One wonders whether the focus should be primarily on the survivors, on the victims or rather on the consolidation of a new democratic regime. The objectives of transitional justice are also not clearly defined. According to (Bell, 2009), research on the functioning of transitional justice has two main axes. The first is the conceptual axis, which requires the attempt to conceptualise the link between transitional justice and a series of other goals such as the rule of law, democratisation, and reconciliation. Research in this area has drawn on disciplines deeply linked to the declared "corn": for example. Political science in democratisation discussions (Bell, 2009).

A key problem when conceptualising these links is that the purpose of transitional justice is not yet clear, "transitional justice for what and for whom" according to (Dancy, 2010, p. 361). This amounts to doubting the objective of establishing transitional justice mechanisms, such as truth commissions. (Merwe, Baxter, and Chapman, 2009) argues that transitional justice mechanisms are clearly lacking and clearly defined. Some have bequeathed this lack of precise objectives to the fact that transitional justice is in its

"Early stages of theory building and several hypotheses which highlight transitional justice initiatives are unverified or questionable"

(Duggan, 2010, p. 320).

Beyond the lack of clarity on the role of transitional justice, the goals themselves, such as democracy, human rights, and peace, are broad and ambiguous without clear and precise boundaries. In addition, transitional justice outcomes are not operated to account for change, to identify any difference that a transitional justice mechanism can make to society. If the objectives of transitional justice are not formally expressed and operationalised, their measurement "becomes a subjective evaluation" (Wiebelhaus-Brahm, 2010, p. 17).

Continuing with (Bell, 2009), the second axis of research on the functioning of transitional justice is empirical: this axis aims to determine how to measure whether

transitional justice achieves the objectives it sets for itself. To understand the concept, empirical work attempts to study transitional justice using qualitative research methods while increasingly trying to quantify the relationship between transitional justice and its stated goals (Bell, 2009). A major challenge here is the operation of transitional justice is not clear, how it will achieve the objective it has set for itself. In this context, studies of transitional justice mechanisms assessing impacts lack references to how change is expected to occur in each society.

As Robins (2015) points out, creating a practice that can be controlled by its presumed effects leads directly to the question of “how” transitional justice works or how transitional justice should work to achieve its objectives. Any understanding of transitional justice is based on one or more theories of change according to which respect for human rights will be improved by resolving past violations. If an impact mechanism can be postulated, it can be tested, illuminating the process by which social and political change occurs during transition (Robins, 2015, p. 185). A theory of change would explain how things should work to produce the desired change, a common practice when evaluating the implementation of peacebuilding projects. A theory of change to test whether a transitional justice mechanism produces the expected results. Although, as (Robins, 2015) points out, the transitional justice literature does not make these theories of change explicit, let alone attempt to test and verify them. As a result, it is difficult to understand the process that leads to changes in societies in transition. Knowing what is the objective that a transitional justice mechanism has set and how it will achieve this objective also makes it easier to measure whether a transitional justice mechanism has succeeded or not. It would probably be possible to assess the success of a transitional justice mechanism based on its projected impacts on a projected and clearly defined objective. With these preliminary considerations relating to the impacts of transitional justice mechanisms and transitional justice mechanisms, the following section reviews the current literature on the evaluation of the impact of transitional justice.

Transitional justice has become nowadays a permanent mechanism facilitating the conflicts resolution by States by enabling them to deal with human rights violations past because of conflict or state repression under an authoritarian regime. Transitional Justice experts and the UN estimate that more than forty transitional justice

mechanisms such as Truth Commissions have been established in different countries over the past forty years. Often these commissions are set with high expectations. These mechanisms are expected to support societies emerging from conflict in establishing the facts on past human rights violations, preserving evidence, identifying perpetrators, encouraging responsibility, recommending reparations and institutional reforms (Secretary-General, 2004: para. 50). Despite these expectations, the literature of the last decade on Transitional Justice has raised doubts about the impacts of these transitional justice mechanisms, highlighting the need for more empirical research (Mendeloff, 2004; Brahm, 2007; Thoms, Ron and Paris, 2010). In his critique of peace promoting the benefits of a formal post-war disclosure and truth-seeking mechanism, Mendeloff writes:

“The literature has done a poor job of specifying the logic of truth-telling arguments, defining, and clarifying key concepts, operationalising key variables, indicating the conditions under which proposed relationships hold, providing compelling empirical evidence to support core assumptions, and testing claims systematically against competing explanations. In short, truth-telling advocates claim more about the power of truth telling than logic or evidence dictates” .

(Mendeloff, 2004, p. 356).

Although this critical analysis was directed at both trials and transitional justice mechanisms around the world, as a mechanism that could bring the truth to light, transitional justice was at the centre of this criticism. Since then, several empirical studies have considered assessing the impacts of transitional justice systems. These studies have tended to make this assessment of the impacts of transitional justice around certain factors such as on institutional reforms, trials, the legislative framework or on reparations. Thoms et al. review empirical research on the impacts of trials and transitional justice systems on political processes. The authors limit this literature to the state level, without reviewing the sub-state or community level (Paris, Ron and N.T. Thoms, 2010: 2). Thoms et al., to organise this review, distinguish between single case studies, small to medium samples, and large samples of comparative studies. As for Brahm (2010), in his review of evaluation studies of transitional justice, he first examines studies that require whether some transitional justice has been successful,

then studies that explore the effects of transitional justice (Wiebelhaus-Brahm, 2010, p. 8). If successful, the studies would focus on the outcome of the truth commission after its investigation. As for the evaluation of the effects, the studies treated transitional justice as an independent variable studying the consequences of surveys on individuals and societies.

Melish (2012) for her part, instead of comparing the studies that have examined the impacts and those that have explored the effects of transitional justice, she instead referred to the success of each category in which she organises the literature on impacts of transitional justice. Thus, according to Melish, measurable truth would determine the success of transitional justice based on everything that transitional justice is able to prove and consider to be truth (Melish, 2012, p. 12). This approach corresponds to Brahm's first proposition, the studies that focus on the outcomes of the commission. The other approaches presented by Melish stick to the type of Brahm's studies that explore the effects of transitional justice. Broadly speaking, Brahm suggests to the individual and societal level depending on whether the studies assess impacts on individuals or on society (Wiebelhaus-Brahm, 2010, p. 10). Therefore, Melish's second approach (victim perception) assesses success at the individual level, based on how transitional justice and its operations are perceived by the public. A third approach, which Melish calls formal political rights, studies impact at the societal level, that have sought to assess impacts on democracy, human rights, and peace. Melish's latest approach also attempts to write down the success of transitional justice at the societal level, shifting the attention to social rights and economic to explore redistributive reforms (Melish, 2012, p. 23). Considering this overview, I focus this study on the impacts of Transitional Justice understood as the effects of its work and not in terms of the outcomes it produced. Considering its own assessment, I concentrate this research on those studies that analyse the impacts of Transitional Justices at an individual, societal, and state level.

2.5 Restorative justice: A space for dialogue

Restorative justice is a practice that has a very ancient origin. It has its origins in the cultural and religious traditions of the indigenous peoples of North America and New Zealand (Zehr, 2010). The term "restorative justice" was proposed in 1975 by Albert Eglash to distinguish "distributive" justice, centred on the treatment of the offender,

from punitive justice, centred on punishment, and that of justice whose finality would be based on restitution. This concept stems from the notion of creative restitution that Eglash elaborates in a text published in 1958 to suggest an overhaul of the rehabilitative model. Modelled on the spiritual principles of the Alcoholics Anonymous program, creative restitution is intended to be a rehabilitation technique whereby an inmate "is helped to find some ways to make amends to those he has hurt by his offense, and to walk a second mile by helping other offenders" (Eglash, 1958, p. 20). The conceptual sources of restorative justice are seldom uncovered. They are nevertheless instructive, the name restorative justice having taken shape in a perspective of reform of the therapeutic model and not, as it is too often stated, in that of an exclusive challenge to the punitive model.

The modern concept of restorative justice developed in the 1970s, particularly in Canada and the United States, from critiques of the criminal justice system and its administration (Charbonneau and Béliveau, 1999). The first experiments with restorative justice measures in Canada took place in 1974, in Kitchener, Ontario, in the form of mediation in criminal matters (*ibid.*). In Quebec, in the late 1970s, adolescent non-judicialization projects began to emerge in a few communities, the first of which took place in Montreal (Leclerc, 2013). These were intended to enable young people to right the harm they had caused, while avoiding being confronted with the legal process (*ibid.*). To date, many restorative justice initiatives have emerged in several thousand communities around the world.

The application of restorative justice to post-conflict transition situations or TRCs is recent. South Africa's Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) is the first truth and reconciliation commission to mobilise a restorative justice approach and arguably this is one explanation for its success. Since then, restorative justice has been a sometimes-advantageous alternative (Lefranc, 2014) to the transitional justice model centred on fault and it corresponds more to the ethical purpose of certain truth and reconciliation commissions.

From the outset, there is no consensus on the exact definition of this concept. Restorative justice scholars such as (T F Marshall, 2003) and Pranis (2007) argue that there is no single definition of the concept, but only an "eclectic accretion of cultures, practices, and experiences" (Pawlychka, 2010, p. 4). Nonetheless, scholars such as

(Tony F Marshall, 2003, p. 28), (Howard, 2002) and (Van Ness, 2009) have attempted to create a working definition of restorative justice. For example, Marshall defines restorative justice as:

"The process by which the parties involved in a specific offense collectively resolve how to deal with the consequences of the offense and its implications for the future"

(Marshall, 2003, p28)

For Howard, one of the pioneers of restorative justice, proposes the definition according to which restorative justice is a process which aims to involve, to the extent possible, all parties concerned by a specific offense, and which seeks to identify and collectively deal with suffering, needs and obligations, to heal and repair as much as possible (Howard, 2002). While there are many definitions of restorative justice, there are some basic principles that are essential when discussing this practice. This is based on the principle that criminal behaviour, in addition to harming the victim, also harms the community and the criminal himself (Ness, 2009). Unlike traditional criminal justice, it is not the state that is wronged when a crime is committed, which gives rise to an entirely different approach to the settlement of justice. According to (Howard (2002), crime is, fundamentally, a violation of people and interpersonal relationships. Crime harms first and foremost the direct victim, but also the community, indirectly. In restorative justice, the focus is on the involvement of the victim, the community, and the offender (Ness, 2009), who are seen as central parts of the redress process. The state may have some role to play in facilitating the process, but it is not at the heart of it (Howard, 2002). The harm caused by the criminal act creates an obligation for its perpetrator to make reparation. The latter is made to realize the damage he has caused to the victim and to adopt means of repairing it. Crime also engages community responsibilities: supporting victims of crime and participating in the social reintegration of offenders. Restorative justice aims to heal the wounds caused to all parties by the crime and to right the wrong done.

Restorative justice aims to meet the needs of both the victim, the offender, and the community (Zehr, 2010). Victims of crime often have needs that are not met by the traditional justice system. According to Zehr (2010), the restorative justice approach

applies to considering such needs, such as the need for information, the need to be able to tell the truth about what really happened, the need to accountability by having a place in the judicial process and the need for redress and justification. Regarding the offender, the restorative justice process aims to make him realize and recognize the harm he has caused to the victim and to take the necessary measures to repair the harm suffered by the victim as much as possible (Wemmers, 2002). The aim is also to reintegrate offenders into the community, although imprisonment is not excluded in some cases (Zehr, 2010). Finally, restorative justice aims to consider the needs of community members as secondary victims of crime (Zehr, 2010), to build a sense of shared responsibility in the face of crime and to promote support for victims, as well as offenders.

Thus, restorative justice can have benefits for all parties involved (Zehr, 2010). This approach is not, however, a silver bullet to replace the formal criminal justice system (Zehr, 2010). There are situations where the application of a restorative justice process is not appropriate (for example, when there is no voluntary participation of one of the parties) (Leclerc, 2013). Nor does it necessarily represent an alternative to prison (Zehr, 2010). Moreover, restorative justice is not unanimous among victims' rights groups (Wemmers, 2002). There are concerns that the victim may experience secondary victimization due to the increased responsibilities in the justice process, as she takes a central place in the restorative justice process. However, studies that have evaluated restorative justice practices have shown that victims greatly value restorative interventions as an adjunct to legal proceedings (Shapland *et al.*, 2006). They would even be more satisfied with these interventions than with the legal process itself (Shapland, Willmore, and Duff, 1985; Umbreit, Coates, and Vos, 2002; Strang and Sherman, 2003; Latimer, Dowden, and Muise, 2005).

Restorative justice is an increasingly popular approach that emphasises healing and redress for victims rather than retribution. Advocates of restorative justice such as Johnstone and Ness (2007), (Marshall (2003) and (Pranis, 2007) believe that the current system, characterized by confrontation and revenge, cannot meet the needs of victims (Zehr, 1990; Umbreit, Coates and Kalanj, 1994). They emphasise that restorative justice provides an opportunity for victims to take an active role in the process. They can make requests and reject or accept the offender's proposal.

However, restorative justice continues to be a controversial topic in victim advocacy groups (Reeves, 1989; Reeves and Mulley, 2019) Reeves, 1989; Avalon, 1999). According to them, the victim already bears a disproportionate burden because of the offense, and it is possible that an increase in their responsibility constitutes a second victimization (Law Commission of Canada, 1999). Despite this, victims show some interest in restorative justice (Tufts, 2000). In addition to the difficulties in finding an adequate definition of the concept of restorative justice, questions exist as to the extent to which restorative justice resembles or does not resemble traditional Indigenous methods of delivering justice. Justice scholars such as (Griffiths, 1996) and (Nielsen, 1995) believe that restorative justice is a process that stems from the traditions of Indigenous justice, although not all Indigenous justice methods are restorative. Ross (2006) notes that one of the points of overlap between the values of Indigenous justice and restorative justice is that instead of punishing the perpetrator, there is a much greater focus on “teaching and healing all the parties involved” (Ross, 2006 p12). Sawatsky (2009) also believes that indigenous justice has focused on repairing indigenous identities destroyed by historical injustices such as assimilation. For Smith (1999), two of the means of repairing Indigenous identities are the healing of Indigenous communities and the decolonisation of Western justice. Henderson and McCaslin (2005) attempt to explain how native people tried to shift away from Euro-centric notions of good and just, such as rationalisations of crime, and how to deal with them. According to the authors, the decolonisation of justice includes the dismantling or separation of colonial oppression from indigenous traditions of justice and definitions of crime by using indigenous language, customs, knowledge, and values to heal peoples and communities (Henderson and McCaslin, 2005, p. 5).

Indigenous justice and restorative justice methods are defined by the participation of victims, perpetrators, community members and a mediator, while harm is caused one person on another. Gibbs (2009) argues that there is a connection between Indigenous justice paradigms and restorative justice in recognizing the interdependence of victims, offenders, and their communities (p54). Given the overlap between the practices of the two jurisdictions (restorative and Indigenous), restorative justice is not systematically the preferred method in Indigenous dispute resolution processes. The literature reviewed for this thesis suggests that the indigenous peoples of Côte d'Ivoire primarily use non-retributive approaches as community strategies for

conflict resolution. These strategies aim to re-establish relationships between the victim, the abuser, and members of the community.

The following section mainly focuses on the discussion of the key themes of restorative justice which are victim-centred, inclusiveness and engagement, negotiations of reparation processes, victim-perpetrator mediation, restoration of identity, respect and dignity of victims, symbolic / material reparations, seeking the truth and overcoming the denial of injustice and the challenges and limitations of restorative justice. The choice of themes in this study is made because of their overlap with Indigenous justice practices and given their relevance to the work of truth commissions. These themes form the basis of our study of the “restoration” of the CDVR.

2.5.1 Centred on the victim.

Restorative justice scholars such as Roche (2006), (Llewellyn and Howse, 1999), Woolford (2009) and Zehr (1985) recognise that restorative justice practices are often aimed at enabling victims to reveal their history and prioritise their needs such as information needs, emotional needs, compensation, protection needs, lack of participation and practical needs. Regarding the practical needs of victims, these usually arise immediately after the crime (Shapland, 1986). The need for information is the most frequent need of victims (Maguire, 1991). For example, (Wemmers, 1996) found that 80% of victims wanted information regarding the follow-up of their case. The victim or survivor seeks information to better understand victimization. Basically, this need is emotional. This is a coping strategy; a way of dealing with victimization. It may take a few days to a few years for the victim to heal, depending on the severity of the psychological injury and the treatment received immediately after the crime.

After victimisation, the victim may fear and feel vulnerable. Some victims are above all afraid of their attacker. They are afraid of reprisals. For some victims, freedom is lost as well as the feeling of security (Baril, 1984). Several studies have shown that victims feel excluded from the justice system and want to play a role in it (Shapland, Willmore, and Duff, 1985; Kilchling, 1995). Victims can also play an active or passive role (UN Handbook, 1999). Active participation implies that they want to make the decisions and make the demands. Passive participation implies that they want to be consulted and informed without being responsible for decisions (Wemmers, 1996).

By seeing victims as the important part of the process, restorative justice practices recognize their roles in conflict resolution and "lead victims to become stakeholders in the justice process whose needs are the primary concern of justice" (Zernova, 2007 p42). Therefore, understanding the needs of victims can lead to dealing adequately with the consequences of wrongful acts. McEvoy et al. (2002) and Ness (2009) confirm that restorative justice also aims to empower communities to resolve conflicts. In this sense, it means the community responsibility to face the effects of injustices and prevent their repetition.

To say that a TRC is victim-centred is to pass judgment on the direction of activities aimed at finding the truth. This does not mean that the commission is run by the victims or that it is established to serve their interests (James, 2012: 185). This model contrasts with crime centric TRCs, which are often criticised for using victims' testimonies to establish the crimes and the identity of their perpetrators, thus risking failure to transform a community based on exclusion and repression into a more just community (James, 2012: 187). Indeed, the victim-centred model is not only concerned with the dignity of victims and the respect due to them, it also and above all aims for transformation (2012: 188). It is in this sense that he implements restorative justice.

2.5.2 Inclusiveness and engagement

It is not yet clear whether victims want to play an active or passive role in conflict resolution. Reeves and Mulley (2000) cautioned that invitation to attend a restorative justice programme may be viewed as an obligation or a responsibility to the offender. Several studies have shown that some victims say they attended a meeting because they felt obligated (Marshall and Merry, 1990; Morris, Maxwell, and Robertson, 1993). However, various definitions of restorative justice including that of Braithwaite (2003) show that restorative justice is essentially inclusive and involves the participation and engagement of all parties concerned during reparation encounters. (Llewellyn, 2002) argues that restorative processes should ensure that those responsible for the abuse can participate in restoring the harm they have caused (2002, p. 299). Some scholars such as Sawatsky (2009) and Ross (2006) believe that inclusiveness is a core tenet of many Indigenous justice practices. Restorative encounters, such as Healing Circles and Family Group Conference allow all parties to speak out about how they have been

affected by wrongdoing. Van Ness and Strong (2006) assert that the inclusion of dating is important and argue that restorative justice is guided by four main values: encounter, restitution, and restorative inclusion and reintegration. This importance is since victims, offenders and members of the community affected by a wrongdoing organise a meeting in which all parties affected by the conflict are included to assess the consequences and plan to redress the consequences. prejudices.

What does indicate the reintegration potential of restorative justice according to Pawlychka (2010), is that all parties have the means and the opportunity to reach their communities, contributing members (Pawlychka, 2010 P6). In the case of the Ivorian crisis, according to this definition of restorative justice, I expected an inclusive restorative meeting to involve Ivorian government officials (certainly CDVR) and rebel forces in as perpetrators, and survivors and their families as victims, as well as members of the public, who consider themselves affected by the Ivorian crises. In theory, the list of participants in restorative justice processes can be quite long (Cawsey Inquiry 1991). In addition, there is the question of whether victims are more satisfied with restorative justice programs than with the justice system. Some authors like (Fattah, 1998) and (Zehr, 1990) believe that punishment does not meet the needs of victims and that restorative justice should better meet their needs. But the research is unclear. Most studies are not complete enough to allow to conclude that there is a causal relationship. Concretely, victims who have chosen restorative justice programs may already have more positive attitudes.

In addition, participation in a restorative programme would also ensure that participating victims feel they are taking charge of themselves (“empowerment”) (Wemmers and Canuto, 2002; Wemmers and Cyr, 2005; Shapland *et al.*, 2007). Finally, comparative studies reveal that victims are more satisfied with the restorative intervention than with the legal process (Umbreit *et al.*, 2002; Strang and Sherman, 2003; Latimer *et al.*, 2005; Strang *et al.*, 2006) , among other things because they feel more involved in finding a solution to the consequences of the offense (Wemmers and Cyr, 2006). Insofar as the offense has direct and secondary impacts, all those who have suffered from its consequences and have a legitimate interest, namely the victims, the offenders, their relatives, members of the community should have the possibility active participation in the justice process as early and as fully as possible.

Victims and offenders must be able to speak out unreservedly about the offense, highlighting all their trauma (past, present, and future). Meetings and dialogues, associating, where appropriate, family, referents, witnesses, and members of the community, should be encouraged to allow everyone to be involved in the search for solutions to get out of the conflict crystallized by the offense.

2.5.3 Mediation and Negotiations of restoration processes

Old practices, negotiation and mediation have become, with the end of the Cold War, a privileged mode of conflict management and resolution. Involving a diversity of actors and methods, these conflicts exit strategies offer a peaceful alternative to resorting to violence and signal the possibility of common ground between the conflicting parties. Moreover, reparation is a negotiated and consensual process as the perpetrators, victims and authorities collaborate in determining how justice should be served in specific cases (Huculak 2005). More specifically, by including all parties to the conflict, the goal is to make collective and consensual decisions on how to resolve an injustice (Zehr and Mika 1997). This way of negotiating can facilitate the empowerment of victims by giving them the opportunity to take control and ownership of the legal process. Therefore, before the start of reparation processes, it is necessary to understand the quality of the negotiations and consider the extent of consultations with victims. To facilitate victims' participation in the negotiation of the process of resolving an injustice and restoring restorative justice practices can “provide victim representation on governing bodies and initial planning committees” (Sawin and Zehr 2007: 49). As such, restorative processes serve as empowerment tools in the sense that survivors can influence the process put in place to deliver justice to victims (Woolford 2009).

Mediation and negotiation therefore consist of the possibility offered to the victim and the offender to meet voluntarily to discuss the aspects and consequences of the conflict between them and to find an equitable solution under the assistance and control of a mediator / facilitator whose role is to supervise the meeting in a completely neutral manner. The purpose of mediation is, first of all, to make such a meeting possible, to encourage the author to measure the human, social and / or material impact of his behaviour and to take responsibility for it, but also to lead each to

reconsider the point of view of the other and take it more into account and bring the parties to consider the contours of compensation for damage.

In the case of the Ivorian crises, for example, the mechanisms developed by the authorities to redress the experiences of the victims would involve dialogues with the survivors to determine what needs to be done to redress the harm. In addition to their initial contribution, the engagement of survivors would be essential to ensure that their justice needs are met. Mediation between victim and offender was tested in the early 1970s in Kitchener (Ontario) (Peachey, 2003). There are more than 300 programmes in North America and about 700 in the rest of the world. In Europe (Willemssens and Walgrave, 2004), most countries have formally integrated mediation into their legislative arsenal or their praetorian practices, both regarding minors and adults, at each stage of the criminal trial for some of them such as Belgium (Lemonne, 2007). In France, penal mediation is reserved for adults within the framework of alternatives to prosecution. Criminal reparation for minors is much more appropriately installed at all stages of the procedure (Cario, 2005). It is good to note that the conditions for the implementation of these measures are very close to the three main objectives of restorative justice: reclassification of the culprit, compensation for the damage and cessation of the disorder (Cario, 2005). Victim-offender mediation offers those concerned the opportunity for a voluntary, face-to-face meeting to discuss the characteristics and consequences of the criminal conflict between them. Structured and secure, the meeting is led by a professional mediator / facilitator. The goal of victim/offender mediation is, first of all, to make such an encounter possible; to then encourage the author to measure the human, social and / or material impact of his action and to take responsibility for it; to further lead each to reconsider the other's point of view and to take it more into account; to bring, finally and mainly, those concerned to consider the contours of the reparation of the damages caused (Ness, 1999).

2.5.4 Restoration of the identity, respect, and dignity of victims

According to Frederiksen (2008) and Llewellyn (2002), the goals of restorative justice processes and indigenous justice practices are to restore the identity of victims damaged by injustices such as conflict, genocide, criminality, and human rights violations. human rights. Ame and Alidu (2010) suggest that one of the possibilities for

restoring the identity of victims is to restore their respect by educating the public about the wrongs committed against them. By giving victims, the chance to meet the public and share their experiences, participate in national meetings, explain their sentences can facilitate understanding and awareness of prejudices and contribute to the restoration of a social identity positive for victims. In addition, the actions of perpetrators of public recognition of injustice can encourage recognition of these identities by the public and restore the dignity and respect of victims (Allan and Allan 2000). Gibbs (2009) and Guest (1999) believe that certain characteristics of restorative justice give it the potential to remedy historical injustices, such as those in the Côte d'Ivoire. For example, restorative justice and indigenous justice systematise an unlawful act based on how it degrades the social status of the victims and, to redress the injustice, the abuser must restore the victim's previous status (Guest 1999: 338). Because during the Ivorian crises, the survivors suffered the loss of their cultural identity, their dignity, and their respect. Gibbs (2009: 50) suggests that the use of restorative justice in Indigenous historical grievances offer the possibility of restoring what victims have lost. According to Llewellyn and Howse (1999), for the restoration of the identity, respect, and dignity of victims to be possible, perpetrators must acknowledge their experiences. Regarding the offender, its accountability and redress are at the heart of the strategy of restorative justice. Restorative justice, rather than treating the offender as an object to be manipulated, pays considerable attention to his capacity to perform positive and constructive acts (Radzik, Johnstone, and Ness, 2007) and gives him the means to achieve this. Such human justice then promotes the reconquest of self-esteem and the affirmation, more generally, of one's quality as a moral agent capable of manifesting appropriate reactions. The dignity of the author is thus restored (Braithwaith, 2003). By asserting that punishment is not synonymous with accountability, the restorative process leads the offender to face what he has done, encourages him to understand the consequences and repercussions of his actions, to feel empathy. towards the victim, to give oneself the means to repair the wrongs suffered by others and to transform degrading shame into positive shame (Zehr, 2005). Restorative justice also helps the offender to evolve in his behaviour by reducing the risk factors that led him to the offense and by offering him the possibility of being treated (for example for addiction) and of acquiring personal skills and professional qualifications which it lacks. The love and support of those close to him and members of the community for his reintegration will make the offender feel less

isolated from society, a feeling that is reinforced by the criminal process and the experience of incarceration. Thus, by responding to the needs of the offender, restorative justice enables him to take responsibility for the victim and for society, to change his behaviour in a positive way and to be a full member of the community. community (Zehr, 2005), Toews and Katounas, 2004).

2.5.5 Symbolic / material reparations

One of the essential elements of restorative and indigenous justice practices is to encourage perpetrators to take responsibility for redressing the harm caused by an illegal act (Yazzie 2005). According to Valandra (2005), reparations must be borne by the perpetrator in the process of repairing the harm. Reparations are seen to restore victims, to express recognition of the wrong, to recreate the relationship between the victim and the perpetrator of the harm. This ambition arose from the idea that reparations are the only true victim-centred approach to justice. De Greiff (2006) summarises the mission of reparations in three ways: The first is gratitude. Reparations aim to express the recognition of the victims, first and foremost as human beings, worthy of honour and respect. Then reparations send the message that the victim has suffered an injustice, that his status must be recognised as such. The second is the civil trust. This goal of reparations as an instrument of justice is the formation or restoration of trust among citizens. In this context, trust must be understood as a disposition to regulate social interactions, an alternative to vigilance (Baier, 1994). The last is solidarity (De Greiff, 2006). Reparation programmes are also expected, an attitude of social solidarity. Social solidarity is a disposition and a desire, for a person, to put themselves in the place of another. It is also taking an interest in the interests of others. Solidarity must be expressed towards the victims, the disadvantaged.

From the ideas of this author arise certain reservations. If any act of reparation very often expresses the recognition of the wrong done to others, but the people on whom the compensation is weighed are not necessarily convinced of their responsibility. This is how they do it by force of law. Moreover, trust among citizens does not necessarily keep pace with reparations. It is often stubborn, slow, or absent. The same goes for solidarity, especially when those who must repair do so by force. Literature shows that the recognition of harm caused to others is the main element of any reparation

process. It is probably this which links the notion of reparation to that of reconciliation. Reparations pave the way for reconciliation (recovery of the victim, recognition of the perpetrator's fault and reframing of the relationship). And if this is not always the case, at least one can say, all these concepts are on the same moral territory.

In the same vein, Barkan indicates that the different forms of reparation create a mosaic of acknowledgments of the wrong by its authors (Barkan, 2001). This recognition underlines the need to rectify this wrong and therefore a desire to readjust relations. Without it, nothing indicates that the culprit regrets his act. This presupposes that the burden of repairs must be borne by the author of the damage. For example, on the issue of reparations for victims of political repression in Malawi under the leadership of President Banda, the Regional Programme for Southern Africa (SARP, 2003a) reports that victims were not satisfied that reparations were designed as a vertical process, involving the victim and the new government, not the perpetrator of the alleged crimes. However, to the extent that reparations (if any) enable the victim to regain their human dignity, including improving their living conditions, it is an important ingredient in rebuilding relationships. But it is important to note that the restorative power of reparations also depends on the type of conflict they follow, the perceptions of those who have suffered, and the political realities that accompany the process. In all cases, political, economic, and social imperatives play a decisive role. For his part, Appiah (2004) distinguishes two functions in reparations: the function of restoring the situation and the expressive function. The first, explicit in the etymology (Latin "reparare" meaning to restore or restore a good condition), is that the act of reparation restores the damage to the victim. This function suggests exactly what the scale of repairs should be. The goal here is to make up for the damage and, failing that, to bring the victim back to the state in which she would be if the aggressor did not do so. The analysis of this function shows that the greater the damage, the higher the scale of reparations. It is at this level that the idea of reparations taken from this angle seems idealistic.

Indeed, when the wrong committed is sufficiently serious, the attempt to compensate for it by excessive reparations only emphasises its irreparable character. If, for example, a person has been wrongly imprisoned for years, the best thing that can be done is to admit that nothing can be given back to them for those years. Substantial

adequate repairs are not possible. This is exactly the case with victims of genocide. Any attempt to remedy this kind of experience would not only be absurd but also somewhat offensive. This means that those who propose to repair the evil do not recognise its seriousness. The second, or the expressive function, concerns rather the meaning of the act of reparation. Like apologies, acts of reparation, whether material or symbolic, are recognition of a wrongdoing. From this point of view, there is no money or even a natural remedy. Because nothing implies that the repairs cancel anything. At most, it can be said that this point of view implies the following adequacy: the more serious the damage, the more important the action. The two functions are not mutually exclusive. They can be filled in the same context. According to the former South African Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) Final Report, 2003, reparations have taken five different forms in this country, namely emergency arrangements, community rehabilitation programmes, symbolic reparation, institutional reform, and the award of individual reparations. While it has become evident that all these forms of reparation have not been proportionate to the severity of the damage caused by apartheid, it cannot be denied that they have created a lasting base of support for the victims (South Africa TRC, Final report, 2003). The International Centre for Transitional Justice (ICTJ), the leading international organisation defending the problem of transitional justice around the world, states that a reparation policy should generally include several measures combining physical and symbolic elements rather than stick to one measure (Magarrell 2007). Magarrell adds that repairs can be material or symbolic and simple or complex. Material repairs can take the form of financial compensation or the provision of services. These services make repairs complex as they include not only financial compensation but provisions for education, health, housing, etc. Symbolic reparations can include official apologies, days of remembrance, renaming of public spaces, creation of museums and parks dedicated to the memory of victims, or rehabilitation measures.

Recognising that victims of different categories of human rights violations do not necessarily have to receive the same type of benefits, it would be desirable to have a wide variety of benefits to reach many victims. This variety of benefits allows states to deal with different types of damage and increases the likelihood that each identified damage can be remedied. Since money cannot buy everything, the complexity of reparation programmes can offer the potential to bring benefits to more victims.

Particularly in the case of collective symbolic measures, victims and non-victims can benefit from these advantages. This can generally meet the diverse needs of the general population (Adhikari & Hansen 2013). Material compensation for victims of human rights violations has received more attention than any other type of reparation. Indeed, while material compensation can help victims escape the abyss of despair, they can never remedy the horrors, humiliation, rape, and destruction of human dignity.

In traumatised societies, such as Rwanda and South Africa, for example, it is not uncommon to hear people oppose any attempt at material reparation and only ask for symbolic reparations. This is how they underline the importance of the truth, of mourning and of the burial of the bodies of the victims. For this category of people, compensation, in the sense of reparations, is akin to the sale of theirs, killed in atrocious conditions, especially since this compensation is not supported by the executioners. Several individual symbolic measures such as the drafting of personalised letters of apology signed by the President of the Republic or the head of government, the issuance of death certificates, the celebration of new burials and ceremonies, the removal of criminal records have had consequences. positive effects. By making the memory of victims a public matter, symbolic measures become a very important element of transitional justice because they bring relief to victims and family members of victims. Individual or collective symbolic measures bear witness to the State's recognition of victims not only as victims, but also as rights holders more generally (Greiff, 2014).

The diversity of symbolic advantages deserves to be encouraged because it allows to reach many victims and not to frustrate others. It should be noted, however, that symbolic measures do not replace the financial compensation that is most needed. They are rather complementary. Given the semantic and representative function of symbolic measures, the participation of civil society in the design and implementation of symbolic reparations programs is very important. The basic principles state that the concept of rehabilitation due to victims includes medical and psychological rehabilitation. In general, human health is very valuable. There is therefore a need for reparation programs to address the health issues of victims and parents. Thus, the provision of medical services, including psychiatric treatment and mental support, is

an effective way to improve the quality of life of survivors and their families. However, the provision of medical services in the form of compensation for compensation should not be limited to the provision of drugs. Specialised services such as physical rehabilitation specialists, mental health specialists, etc. should be included in these medical services. In addition to the need for specialized services, it will take the experience and expertise of specialists to offer this type of service professionally (Greiff, 2014). In addition, officials of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission should consider that the issue of property restitution has clearly featured in many political transitions and peace accords since the end of the Cold War. The restitution of property, houses, land, and property is seen to redress past injustices in many forms. Restitution is more strictly linked to reparations aimed at restoring victims to the state they would have enjoyed if no violation of their rights had taken place. Restitution of property must therefore be at the centre of reparation programmes.

2.5.6 Seeking the truth and overcome the denial of injustice.

The goals of truth and reconciliation are inextricably linked. The search for the truth is conceived as a stage and an indispensable instrument for achieving the reconciliation that the protagonists of the conflict need to restart political, economic, and social life after murderous and fratricidal struggles. The argument, arguably the most compelling in favour of Truth Commissions, is that ignorance of the truth immediately biases, or spoils plans for restarting and rebuilding. The absence of truth means that the policies and methods practiced before and during the conflict cannot be debated, let alone exposed. Restorative justice, at its core, aims to uncover the truth about the past such as the reasons for the conflict and the damage caused by identifying the testimonies of survivors and perpetrators (Hayner, 2002) (Zehr, 2002). In addition, Llewellyn and Howse (1999) believe that disclosure of the truth is linked to an admission of involvement by the offender, without which healing and redress for injustice cannot take place. In addition, for restorative justice, the truth told by offenders is an important element as it facilitates the prevention of revenge on the part of the victims and is therefore associated with long-term peacebuilding goals, harmony, and reconciliation. This is linked to the recognition of past abuses, to reconciliation and to rebuilding a society based on peaceful coexistence (Joseph, 2005: 263). Depending on whether the establishment of the truth is essential to discover the causes of the conflict, without a rigorous analysis of the causes of the conflict, speeches and reform projects may be

hollow and have no hold on reality. Two dangers lie in wait for the planned reforms. In the first place, the reforms risk being removed from the concerns of a large section of the population whose part of the truth has been denied. It is thus developing a construction of institutions that are increasingly foreign to the nation or to the populations. As Ghalioun indicates in the very subtitle of his book, on Arab Malaise, it is State against Nation (Ghalioun, 1991). How, then, to achieve the recommendations that no truth commission fails to address to those in power? In the second place, the reforms, assuming that they are decided, risk not becoming effective, for lack of having associated in their development the representatives of those they concern and, therefore, of being taken with full knowledge of the facts. The absence of a true diagnosis facilitates the emergence of flawed policies. The dangers that arise from refusing to seek the truth and the causes of the conflict therefore deeply corrode the social body. Moreover, according to Chapman and Merwe (2008), the search for the truth, often carried out by truth and reconciliation commissions, allows victims to find answers to questions such as: What happened? And why did this happen? Disclosure of the truth about past facts can help prevent similar injustices in the future. While the truth revealed by perpetrators is one of the important elements of restorative justice, Valandra (2005: 35) argues that the disclosure of the truth by victims can act as a response to historical injustices.

2.6 Restorative Justice as a Framework for Evaluating TRC

Restorative justice (RJ) serves as a significant framework for evaluating the legitimacy and effectiveness of truth commissions in the realm of transitional justice. In contrast to retributive justice, which focuses on punishment, RJ prioritizes the processes of truth-telling, recognition of victims, and the healing of society, with the goal of mending harm rather than merely enforcing punitive actions (Zehr, 2002). Nonetheless, RJ has been criticized for reducing justice to a simplistic dichotomy of victims and offenders, which may obscure the essential role of the state in perpetuating systemic violence (McEvoy & McGregor, 2008). Additionally, detractors argue that RJ's emphasis on reconciliation could undermine the moral obligation to hold those responsible for serious human rights violations accountable (Duff, 2003). This chapter posits that, despite these criticisms, RJ is the most effective framework for assessing truth commissions because it: 1) goes beyond the binary of victim and perpetrator by highlighting state complicity and structural injustices, 2) provides a holistic approach

to addressing human rights violations through the integration of truth, reparations, and accountability, and 3) interacts with retributive justice without negating it, allowing for selective punishment while emphasizing sustainable justice.

This section examines the role of restorative justice (RJ) in the framework of truth commissions, highlighting the various ways in which RJ offers a nuanced and effective approach to addressing historical injustices. By analysing its key advantages, the section explores how RJ moves beyond traditional paradigms, engages with both victim and perpetrator narratives, and fosters long-term reconciliation. Specifically, we will assess the strengths of RJ in revealing systemic complicity, addressing the needs of victims, and ensuring accountability.

Examining truth commissions in South Africa, Northern Ireland, Peru, and Colombia demonstrates how restorative justice (RJ) fosters systemic accountability and promotes long-term reconciliation, thereby offering a more effective alternative to approaches that rely solely on punitive measures.

In South Africa, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) played a pivotal role in addressing the injustices of apartheid. Desmond Tutu asserts in his book, *No Future Without Forgiveness* (Tutu, 1999), that the TRC's approach, which emphasized truth-telling and reconciliation over punishment, was crucial for healing a divided society. Additionally, Mamdani (2000) critiques the TRC's framework and explores its potential to foster accountability while addressing the societal need for forgiveness and peace.

Similarly, in Northern Ireland, the processes of the Truth Recovery Commissioners have focused on creating a shared narrative that acknowledges the suffering of all communities. Hayner (2001) discusses how these initiatives aimed to promote understanding among conflicting parties, highlighting their role in systemic accountability. Moreover, McEvoy and McGregor (2008) argue that justice mechanisms beyond criminal prosecution have built pathways for reconciliation in a society marked by violent conflict.

In Peru, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (CVR) was established to address the severe human rights abuses during the internal conflict. The Final Report of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission in Peru (CVR, 2003) outlines the importance of historical acknowledgment and the need for societal healing. Gonzalez (2006)

emphasizes the significance of historical memory in paving the way for accountability and transformation in societal attitudes toward justice.

Colombia's recent peace process has also utilized truth-telling as a vital component of restorative justice. The report *I Remember: A Report on the Colombian Armed Conflict* by the Centro Nacional de Memoria Histórica (2015) highlights how these initiatives promote healing and reconciliation in a country long ravaged by internal conflict. Gutiérrez Sanín and Vargas (2015) further analyse how Colombia's commitment to restorative justice constitutes a strategic choice for long-term peace building, contrasting it with the limitations of punitive approaches.

Overall, these cases collectively illustrate how truth commissions can foster an environment of accountability and facilitate long-term reconciliation. By emphasizing dialogue, acknowledgment of past injustices, and a focus on healing rather than retribution, countries have found more sustainable alternatives to punitive justice systems.

One significant criticism of restorative justice (RJ) is its limited perspective on justice, which often frames reconciliation as a moral transaction exclusively between individual victims and offenders, neglecting the larger roles played by the state, institutions, and systemic oppression (McEvoy & McGregor, 2008). Detractors argue that when RJ is misapplied, it can be manipulated by political leaders to avoid accountability, prioritizing personal reconciliation over necessary institutional reforms or criminal responsibility for state-sponsored offenses (Gready & Robins, 2014). However, a thoughtfully designed RJ framework has the potential to reveal state complicity and promote structural changes. In contrast to retributive justice, which focuses on individual prosecutions, RJ expands the notion of accountability to include the political, economic, and social systems that have enabled widespread violence (McEvoy, 2007).

Wilson (2001) notes that the South African Truth and Reconciliation Commission, despite facing significant criticism for offering amnesty in return for truth, critics such as Mamdani (2000) and McEvoy (2007) argued that this policy undermined justice for victims and allowed perpetrators to escape accountability—successfully highlighted

the scale of state-sponsored violence during apartheid by providing a platform for victims' narratives and promoting national healing.

This process allowed victims to confront not only individual offenders but also the systemic patterns of oppression, implicating government officials, security forces, and corporate entities (Gibson, 2006). The TRC's final report called for institutional reforms and reparations, demonstrating that RJ can tackle systemic harm rather than merely concentrating on individual accountability (Tutu, 1999). Similarly, the Peruvian Truth and Reconciliation Commission (CVR) (2001–2003) documented the accountability of state forces for extrajudicial killings and other atrocities, thereby recognizing the ethnic and racial aspects of structural oppression faced by Indigenous communities (Drinot, 2009; Theidon, 2007). This illustrates how RJ transcends the victim-perpetrator dichotomy by incorporating state actors, thereby facilitating a more comprehensive and meaningful accountability process.

Critics of restorative justice (RJ), including scholars like McEvoy and Mallinder (2012), argue that it falls short in addressing the gravity of human rights violations associated with genocide, torture, and mass killings. For instance, critics such as Minow (1998) and Teitel (2003) have highlighted that RJ may not adequately provide justice for victims in extreme cases, where retributive justice or other forms of accountability are deemed necessary to recognize the severity of such crimes. Some argue that RJ places too much emphasis on healing and reconciliation, potentially undermining accountability for serious crimes (Teitel, 2000). Nevertheless, RJ does not eliminate the concept of accountability; instead, it broadens the understanding of justice to incorporate truth-telling, reparations, and institutional reform (Llewellyn & Howse, 1999). RJ promotes human rights accountability in several ways, notably through victim-centered justice, which prioritizes the experiences of victims in the justice process rather than treating them as mere witnesses (Daly, 2002). Public truth-telling can reveal human rights abuses that are often hidden in conventional legal frameworks, particularly in environments where legal systems are fragile or politically restricted (Laplante, 2015). Additionally, RJ mechanisms frequently advocate for reparations and institutional reforms, ensuring that justice encompasses not only the punishment of offenders but also the restoration of communities (Kent, 2011).

The peace process in Colombia, established in 2016 and exemplified by the Special Jurisdiction for Peace (JEP), illustrates the integration of restorative justice (RJ) with retributive justice, creating a hybrid tribunal that addresses significant war crimes while offering restorative options for lower-level combatants (García-Godos, 2020). Similarly, in Northern Ireland, the Good Friday Agreement brought forth a framework that emphasized truth recovery and reconciliation through mechanisms like the Historical Institutional Abuse Inquiry and the Truth Recovery Commissioners. These initiatives aimed to provide a platform for victims' voices while navigating the complexities of accountability related to past violence, highlighting the importance of restorative options in addressing grievances (McEvoy & McGregor, 2008).

In Peru, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (CVR), established in 2001, tackled the extensive human rights violations committed during the internal armed conflict. While it faced critiques regarding its effectiveness (Gonzalez, 2006), the CVR sought to integrate restorative justice principles by documenting victim experiences and fostering national healing, thus reflecting a commitment to long-term reconciliation despite the challenges of addressing severe crimes (CVR, 2003).

These examples, Colombia, Northern Ireland, and Peru have been selected for their innovative approaches to blending RJ with transitional justice elements, showcasing how restorative approaches can create pathways for both accountability and community healing. They illustrate the potential for systemic accountability that prioritizes reconciliation and historical acknowledgment, even in the face of serious human rights violations.

Dr. Allan T. Moore, an Associate Professor of Criminology at the University of West London, has contributed to the discourse on RJ, particularly concerning its application in cases of domestic abuse and sexual violence. In the "Survivors Voices National Consultation," Moore and colleagues explored survivors' perspectives on RJ, aiming to inform policy and practice frameworks in Scotland (Moore et al., 2019). This work underscores the importance of incorporating survivor input in RJ processes, ensuring that such frameworks are responsive to the needs and concerns of those affected by harm.

In contrast, cases such as the Rwandan Gacaca courts, while aimed at community reconciliation, have faced criticism for their shortcomings in providing adequate responses to genocide and mass violence, indicating that not all restorative efforts effectively contribute to long-term reconciliation or accountability (McEvoy & Mallinder, 2012).

Victim involvement has been pivotal in shaping accountability frameworks, ensuring that the quest for justice addresses crimes committed by the state as well as those perpetrated by insurgents (Uprimny, 2017). Consequently, RJ does not overlook human rights violations; rather, it expands the definition of justice to include truth, reparations, and institutional reform, components that are frequently neglected in strictly punitive approaches.

Advocates of retributive justice contend that restorative justice (RJ) permits offenders to evade punishment, thereby compromising moral accountability and the deterrent effect of justice (Duff, 2003). This criticism is predicated on the belief that punishment alone is adequate for achieving justice, neglecting the essential societal requirements for healing and structural transformation (McEvoy & Mallinder, 2012). Relying solely on retribution is often inadequate for various reasons: trials may be subject to selective prosecution and political limitations, punishment does not inherently prevent future acts of violence, and RJ can be implemented alongside selective punitive measures. In numerous post-conflict contexts, only a fraction of offenders is prosecuted, leaving many unaddressed (Sikkink, 2011). Retribution fails to tackle the root causes of violence, while RJ integrates historical context and advocates for systemic changes (Hinton, 2010). Hybrid models, as seen in Colombia, Sierra Leone, and Timor-Leste, illustrate the compatibility of RJ with retributive approaches (Braithwaite et al., 2012). Rather than negating punishment, RJ situates it within a broader context that prioritizes truth, reparations, and long-term reconciliation.

In summary, restorative justice represents the most effective framework for assessing truth commissions because it: 1) moves beyond the simplistic victim-perpetrator dichotomy to reveal the complicity of state and institutional actors, 2) offers a comprehensive response to human rights abuses that encompasses truth-telling, reparations, and necessary policy reforms, and 3) thoughtfully interacts with retributive justice to ensure accountability while avoiding the perpetuation of cycles of retribution.

Justice in post-conflict societies must go beyond mere punitive measures to thoroughly address historical grievances, avert future conflicts, and foster community cohesion. Rather than being a diminished form of justice, restorative justice provides a more holistic and progressive approach that has the potential to promote genuine healing and lasting peace.

2.7 Enhancing the discussion of complex victimhood in restorative justice

This section critically examines the discourse surrounding complex victimhood and its ramifications for restorative justice. It will begin by defining the concept of complex victimhood and its implications for traditional notions of victim and perpetrator, highlighting how this impacts the effectiveness of restorative justice frameworks. Following this, the discussion will explore specific case studies, including South Africa and Northern Ireland, to illustrate how varying experiences of victimhood can complicate reconciliation efforts. Finally, the section will assess the challenges and opportunities that arise when addressing complex victimhood within truth commissions, ultimately arguing for more inclusive approaches to restorative justice. Furthermore, these commissions may inadvertently reinforce state narratives of innocence while marginalizing specific victim groups, such as child soldiers, coerced combatants, or communities ensnared in cycles of violence. Additionally, it argues that RJ frameworks can progress beyond binary justice paradigms by acknowledging structural violence, systemic oppression, and collective accountability. By referencing the works of McEvoy (2007, 2018), Madlingozi (2010), Lundy & McGovern (2008), Theidon (2007), and using case studies from Argentina, Cambodia, Sierra Leone, and Yugoslavia, this section contends that adopting a more nuanced perspective on victimhood can significantly enhance the legitimacy and inclusivity of RJ practices within truth commissions.

Traditional models of transitional justice often operate under the assumption that a clear moral divide exists between victims and perpetrators, a notion that is bolstered by legal frameworks and human rights narratives (Laplante, 2015). Nevertheless, the realities of conflict frequently present a more nuanced picture, as illustrated by Hamber and van der Merwe (1998), who explore the intricate nature of identity and moral ambiguity in post-conflict environments. Examples such as child soldiers, state actors who may also be victims, and civilians ensnared in cycles of violence exemplify this

complexity. Child soldiers, for instance, are not only coerced into committing heinous acts but are also victims of forced militarization (McEvoy & Mallinder, 2012). Furthermore, Hinton and Oeung (2016) point out that police and military personnel involved in acts of violent repression can themselves be victims of violence, which complicates the simplistic victim-perpetrator dichotomy. Additionally, civilians who endure violence may later resort to acts of retaliation, further blurring the lines between victimhood and perpetration (García-Godos, 2020).

Argentina

Argentina's transitional justice framework exemplifies the challenges associated with recognizing multifaceted victimhood. The National Commission on the Disappearance of Persons (CONADEP), which authored the *Nunca Más* report, concentrated predominantly on state-sponsored violence, documenting instances of forced disappearances, torture, and executions perpetrated by the military junta. This focus, however, neglected the violent actions of leftist guerrilla factions such as Montoneros and the People's Revolutionary Army (ERP). In terms of complex victimhood, numerous former guerrilla members experienced severe repression yet were also involved in kidnappings, assassinations, and assaults on security forces. Many survivors of the military dictatorship expressed frustration at being categorized alongside these groups as part of a singular victim classification. The challenge of restorative justice lies in the legal and political imperative to delineate "innocent victims" within truth commissions, which fosters an exclusionary narrative that overlooks civilians affected by guerrilla violence, thereby perpetuating a skewed historical perspective. The inability to fully recognize the intricate nature of victimhood in Argentina has resulted in profound ideological rifts, with ongoing discussions regarding whether the nation's transitional justice system has sufficiently addressed the experiences of all victims involved in the conflict (Bouvier, 2007; Calderón, 2022).

The situation in Argentina illustrates the necessity for truth commissions to exercise caution when defining victimhood, as rigid legalistic frameworks may inadvertently marginalize certain groups. Conventional restorative justice models often perpetuate oversimplified classifications, as seen in the legal and political demands to categorize victims, which can lead to the exclusion of those who are structurally or indirectly affected. Numerous truth commissions, including South Africa's Truth and

Reconciliation Commission, mandated specific legal definitions of victimhood for the purposes of reparations and amnesty applications (Wilson, 2001). This approach resulted in a hierarchy of suffering, where individuals who were both victims and perpetrators were often overlooked (Madlingozi, 2010), echoing the concerns highlighted by Woolford (2017) regarding the experiences of marginalized communities. For example, Canada's Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) concerning residential schools concentrated on direct victims of abuse but faced backlash for inadequately addressing the intergenerational trauma stemming from systemic racism and colonial practices (Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada, 2015; Daschuk, 2020).

Cambodia

Cambodia's approach to transitional justice, especially through the Extraordinary Chambers in the Courts of Cambodia (ECCC), highlights the complexities involved in dealing with individuals who were both victims and perpetrators. During the Khmer Rouge regime led by Pol Pot from 1975 to 1979, millions faced forced labor, executions, and starvation. Notably, many of those who committed acts of violence, particularly lower-ranking Khmer Rouge officials, were themselves victims of coercion, indoctrination, and internal purges. Hinton (2010) points out that numerous Khmer Rouge soldiers were conscripted as children, leaving them with little agency in their involvement in violent acts. The internal purges that targeted thousands of suspected traitors, including low-level cadres, further complicated the lines between victimhood and perpetration. The ECCC's emphasis on prosecuting high-ranking Khmer Rouge leaders resulted in the neglect of many mid-level and lower-ranking perpetrators, which left victims feeling that justice was not fully realized. This absence of accountability for local-level violence has fostered tensions in communities recovering from genocide, as former Khmer Rouge members returned to the very villages where they had committed heinous acts (Dewaal, 2018). The Cambodian experience illustrates the challenges of addressing issues of coercion and structural violence within truth commissions, particularly in the aftermath of genocide.

Sierra Leone

The Sierra Leone Civil War (1991–2002) illustrates the complexities involved in reintegrating individuals who were both victims and perpetrators. The Revolutionary United Front (RUF), along with government forces and local militias, forcibly recruited thousands of child soldiers, many of whom were abducted and drugged, subsequently being coerced into committing horrific acts. These child soldiers emerged as both unwilling perpetrators and profoundly traumatized victims, which created significant societal tensions during their reintegration. The challenge of restorative justice is highlighted by the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC), which prioritized reintegration; however, numerous communities rejected former child soldiers due to their involvement in atrocities (Fofana, 2008). Although the Special Court for Sierra Leone (SCSL) opted not to prosecute children, the emergence of some ex-child soldiers as warlords further complicated the pursuit of justice. Sierra Leone's situation underscores the necessity for restorative justice initiatives to extend beyond mere reintegration, emphasizing the importance of community healing.

Recognizing the multifaceted nature of victimhood is essential, as evidenced by the experiences documented in various truth commissions, which reveal that individuals often occupy both victim and perpetrator roles. For instance, McEvoy (2018) highlights how in contexts like Northern Ireland and Sierra Leone, former combatants have also been victims of violence and coercion, complicating traditional narratives and necessitating a broader understanding of identity. Failure to acknowledge this complexity risks perpetuating simplistic binaries that can alienate key stakeholders and undermine the legitimacy of the truth commission's processes. By ignoring individuals' dual experiences, truth commissions may inadvertently exclude valuable perspectives that could facilitate healing and reconciliation, ultimately limiting their effectiveness in fostering lasting societal change. Rather than being overlooked, the importance of state accountability should be highlighted, with restorative justice (RJ) ensuring that institutions, in addition to individuals, are held accountable for systemic violence. It is crucial to incorporate transformative justice models that extend beyond mere interpersonal reconciliation to tackle economic and political disparities. For restorative justice to achieve its intended restorative effect, it must transcend simplistic moral dichotomies and embrace the intricate realities of victimhood in post-conflict

contexts. This deeper level of engagement is vital, as emphasized by Brundige and Eglash (2022), to establish a comprehensive justice framework that effectively meets the needs of all affected communities.

Conclusion

This chapter presented the main themes of this research. The first section dealt with the concept of transitional justice, its evolution, and its development beyond the legal discipline. According to the literature, this evolution was the result of expansions in the real-world contexts described by the transitions. Specifically, after the success of the transitional justice process in South Africa and the field of transitional justice growth and its application across societies emerging from serious conflicts or human rights violations such as Rwanda, Liberia, Sierra Leone, Peru, and Canada. The second section has dealt with the Truth Commissions, its first establishment and objectives. The discussion focused on truth commissions seeking to achieve a better understanding of the past, apply broader remedies and ensure the independence of their work. They aim to place the victim at the centre of the process, to promote a form of dialogue between victim and perpetrator and to ensure that another form of reparation is offered. The section also examined the question of Truth Commissions' impact evaluation. The section reviewed the obstacles in evaluating impacts of Truth Commissions. These obstacles include a lack of clearly defined goals for Transitional Justice and the absence of clarifications on how Truth Commissions, or other Transitional Justice Mechanisms, are to reach such goals. The last section dealt with the restorative justice. Its origins, its application to post-conflict transition situations or TRCs and its development. The section has also focused on the discussion of the key themes of restorative justice such as victim-centred, inclusiveness and engagement, negotiations of reparation processes, victim-perpetrator mediation, restoration of identity, respect and dignity of victims, symbolic / material reparations, seeking the truth and overcoming the denial of injustice and the challenges and limitations of restorative justice. These themes form the basis of the study of the "restoration" of the Ivorian truth commission.

CHAPTER THREE: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The objective of this chapter is to present the conceptual framework within which the thesis fits. The first section of this chapter contextualizes restorative justice and reconciliation within the field of transitional justice, as well as within the truth commission. The second section determines the relationship between restorative justice and reconciliation by focusing on the needs of victims and the responsibility of the perpetrator to repair the harm caused. Building on this relationship, the final section presents the argument that truth commissions contribute to reconciliation, judiciously integrating restorative justice into the process.

3.1 Restorative justice defined by process and purpose.

Restorative justice encompasses a plurality of diverse principles and practices. In fact, there are so many conceptions of restorative justice and different programmes named restorative justice that it should be viewed as a fragmented model (Ashworth, 1993; McCold, 1998). However, there is a consensus that restorative justice views criminal acts as an act that causes harm to the parties involved. The promoters of restorative justice conceive of the offense as a situation of multiple damage, whether psychological, physical, or otherwise, which must be repaired. Repairing the harm suffered because of the offense is therefore at the heart of the restorative model (Zehr, 1990; Walgrave, 1999; Van Ness, 2002; Wemmers and Canuto, 2002); Peters, 2001). While the authors agree on the fact that restorative justice pays particular attention to the consequences of the criminal transgression (the offense) and to the reparation of the harm suffered, they do not agree on the definition of the crime, nor on the means to be implemented and the objectives of restorative justice (Marshall, 1996; Walgrave, 1999). There is confusion in terms of terminology and theoretical foundations of restorative practices (Dignan and Cavadino, 1996; McCold, 1998; Bazemore and Walgrave, 1999). To describe restorative justice, some authors use for instance transformative justice (Law Commission of Canada), community justice (Moore and O'Connell, 1993), relational justice (Burnside and Baker, 1994) informal justice (Maffhews, 1988) or restorative justice (Messmer and Otto, 1992; Walgrave, 1999). This ambiguity makes up the delimitation of the restorative model complex. This shows the relevance of a study aiming to better understand the point of view of the parties directly involved in restorative justice, i.e., victims and offenders. This work aims to

understand the involvement of victims and offenders in the process of setting up CDVR and reparation. Do they place more importance on processes? Several criteria can be used together or separately to define the basis of restorative justice. For example, restorative measures can be defined according to the participation and the engagement of the processes of CVR, negotiation of the processes of restoration (negotiation), as they can be defined according to the finality (repair of the suffered damages). In a conception where the restorative measure is defined according to the process, negotiation and consensually become the main criteria for delimiting restorative justice. This conception of restorative justice is inspired by Marshall's (1996) definition, which has long been described as a standard definition of restorative justice and was even adopted by the Leuven Declaration in 1997. The Leuven Declaration was published at follow-up to the first international symposium on restorative justice. This colloquium, organised by Lode Walgrave, brought together many authors for the first time interested in restorative justice. Marshall describes restorative justice as:

“A process whereby the parties with a stake in a particular offense come together to resolve collectively how to deal with the aftermath of the offense and its implications for the future”

(Marshall, 1996, p.37).

According to this conception of restorative justice, the sentencing circle set up in indigenous communities is seen as a programme within the restorative model. The Sentencing Circle is a consultative process in a legal process where the parties and their representatives, as well as members of the community, make recommendations to the judge as to the sentence to be imposed on the offender. This can result as much in incarceration, community service, a fine, a period of probation, as in restorative measures or therapeutic care (Jaccoud, 1999). This conception of restorative justice places little importance on the finality of the process, and therefore little interest in righting wrongs. This conception of restorative justice is more akin to so-called negotiated justice since reparation measures are secondary to the principle of negotiation and consensually. Since redressing the wrongs suffered is the cornerstone of restorative justice, this view departs a bit from it. Other authors define reparation in terms of the primary goal of restorative justice, i.e., reparation or finality. This is the

case with (Bazemore and Walgrave, 1999). These authors find Marshall's (Marshall, 1996) definition too narrow since, in their opinion, restorative justice is more than a process and must include restorative measures. They insist on the finality, i.e., repairing the damage caused by the crime. They claim that reparation can be achieved without the parties involved in the conflict reaching a settlement together. According to them, reparations can begin as soon as the wrongs are known, whether the offender is present or not. Bazemore and Walgrave (1999) summarize it as follows: Restorative justice is every action that is primarily oriented towards doing justice by restoring the harm that has been caused by crime (Bazemore and Walgrave, 1999). Righting wrongs can be as much imposed as part of a criminal justice process or as part of a negotiation process, it doesn't matter. According to this view of restorative justice, a court order for reimbursement to the victim would be part of restorative justice, even if the victim and the offender were not directly involved in the conflict resolution process.

A third conception of restorative justice considers the definition of restorative justice in terms of the two preceding criteria: process and purpose. The definitions of Zehr and Mika (1998) and Zehr (2002) fit into this conception. According to Zehr (2002), the philosophy of restorative justice is based on five essential principles "1-Focus on the harms and consequent needs of the victim, as well as the communities and the offenders; 2- Address the obligations that result from those harms (the obligations of the offenders, as well as the community's and society's); 3- Use inclusive, collaborative processes; 4- Involve those with a legitimate stake in the situation, including victims, offenders, community members, and society; 5- Seek to put right the wrongs (Zehr, 2002 32-33). According to (Zehr and Mika, 2017) Victims, offenders, and the community at large are the primary stakeholders in the justice system. 1) Restorative justice emphasises the participation of these parties, including victims and offenders, and seeks redress, healing, accountability, and prevention. 2) The roles of the different parties vary according to the nature of the crime, depending on the capabilities and preferences of each. 3) The state has defined certain tasks, such as fact finding, facilitation methods and security measures, but it is not the main victim (Zehr and Mika, 2017, pp. 47–55).

Reading these two extracts allows me to see the importance that these authors attach to the process (of the participation of the parties in the settlement of the conflict) and

to the finality (the importance of repairing the damage caused by the crime) for define restorative justice.

3.2 Reconciliation: A prerequisite for the building of the nation

Reconciliation between actors but also between groups of actors after a conflict is today a real force of proposal which is based on the model of restorative or restorative justice. It is arguably one of the most pronounced concepts in post-violence societies. It is found in almost all official speeches. However, its meaning remains very vague. The concept is often identified in a normative way with very ambiguous and ill-defined processes and end goals. Reconciliation has been studied since the 1990s and has developed as a field of study (Hughes & Kostovicova, 2018). However, some of the literature tends to conceptualise issues to the extreme, establishing and then disavowing a set of binaries (Little and Maddison, 2017). Reconciliation has played an important role in various academic debates on peacebuilding, democratisation, and conflict transformation (Fischer, 2011). Reconciliation is an important word, at the same time as an unpronounceable word, in public debates born out of violent conflicts, when the belligerents are forced to coexist in the same community. It points to a distant horizon, a desirable state of "violated" societies and the still unfinished process leading to this state, at the same time as it consists of an injunction addressed to the actors of the conflict. In this form of injunction to occur to civil concord, the word has a long past; it is, for example, frequent in many amnesty laws intervening after large-scale conflicts in France (Wahnich, 2016). But it is only in the last two or three decades that it has been massively used and formed into public action programs transferable from one place to another such as programs in areas namely public education, mass media and commemoration, as well as interfaith workshops and cultural exchanges (Flournoy and Pan, 2002). More specifically, these policies include devices for rewriting history, forms of judicial policy, reparations to victims, programs encouraging interactions between enemies, etc. At the same time, post-conflict reconciliation has become an object of science, if not a scientific discipline.

Violent conflicts have negative consequences for individuals and communities such as massive violation of human rights, destruction of property and loss of opportunities. Conflicts also have economic consequences. They lead to rising unemployment and loss of income, as they disrupt economic activity, destroy infrastructure, generate

uncertainty, increase transaction costs, and promote capital flight. Loss of human life, destruction of infrastructure, human capital and institutions, political instability, and increasing conflict-related uncertainties can hamper investment and economic growth (Santhirasekaram and Amirthalingam, 2010). The authors argue that this type of action destroys the social factor that unites communities and individuals because it creates mistrust, hesitation, doubt and suspicion between individuals and communities. Although the processes and end goals of reconciliation are ambiguous and ill-defined, the concept continues to be promoted globally as the foundation for lasting peace and as essential to be able to evolve a society that has endured a devastating and divisive conflict towards a shared and constructive future. It is widely accepted that the successful implementation of reconciliation and transitional justice is a necessary requirement to consolidate peace and stability, and to deliver interrelated benefits, such as economic and social reconstruction, democratisation, and nation-building after atrocities (Hughes & Kostovicova, 2018).

In addition, many practitioners and researchers such as (Hattam, Atkinson and Bishop, 2012; Rosoux, 2014) see reconciliation as a fundamental requirement, as they believe that once a top-down political settlement is achieved, a bottom-up process should be considered and used, so that issues unresolved conflict can be dealt with in order of priority, to prevent a return to violence or even a challenge to the colony (Fischer, 2011). By initiating a bottom-up approach to peacebuilding, the objective is to question the top-down paradigm of international interventions by third parties. This paradigm is marred by unequal power relations between Western and international NGOs funded by donors and local actors who lack resources but have a wealth of community knowledge valued by third parties. The main area of reconciliation work of a bottom-up approach is to refine community relations. Here, local reconciliation is seen as the key to success (Huyse, 2003). In other words, it is about dealing with the past, which, in the opinion of scholars like (Fischer, 2011; Rosoux, 2014) is a prerequisite for building peace and harmonious relationships (Fischer, 2011). Reconciliation is considered by peace activists as an essential condition for lasting peace. They agree that reconciliation is necessary to ensure restoration and cohabitation after the war. However, empirical research on specific conflicts has increasingly tested and questioned the normative statements that underlie the term reconciliation. According to Hughes and Kostovicova (2018), this has led to an unimaginable antithesis between

the rigor of decontextualized normative statements about how reconciliation processes should be conducted and what they should achieve as a goal. Huyse, (2003) has also discussed this contrast. The author argues that, theoretically, reconciliation consolidates peace, prevents recurrence of conflict, and strengthens newly established democratic institutions. To this, it should be added that reconciliation can bring personal healing to survivors, adequate power sharing and reparation, among others. While in theory the objective of reconciliation is known, in practice this reconciliation is however difficult to achieve (Huyse, 2003). Most scholars allow themselves to say that reconciliation is a process rather than a result, and that it facilitates relations between societies, individuals, and groups (Fischer, 2011). This explains the difficulty of achieving reconciliation in practice, as it is generally a long and often unpredictable process, with which each action requires changes in attitudes, behaviour, and institutional environment (Huyse, 2003).

The need for reconciliation is considered very high for those who have been mainly involved in ethno-political conflicts, as these are marked by a loss of trust, having an intergenerational transmission of grievances and trauma resentments. Reconciliation is considered necessary to prevent the desire for revenge (Androff, 2010). To move the current peace towards a stable peace, according to (Bar-Siman-Tov, 2004), reconciliation is the most important condition for achieving this ambition. In addition, Yaacov Bar-Simon-Tov believes that reconciliation is one of the most difficult challenges of transitional justice, as it requires cognitive transformation, a change in beliefs, ideology, and emotions at all levels, like the leaders of society but also the citizens. However, the concept of reconciliation is neither the unanimity of researchers nor that of the groups to be reconciled, which gives it a plurality of definitions. Reconciliation has its origins in the Judeo-Christian tradition, with the meaning of divine reconciliation. The Bible calls, in the Gospel according to Saint Matthew (5, 24), to “be reconciled first with your brother”. It is an invitation to come closer to men separated by disagreement, urging a return to harmony, to agreement, to peace (Redonnet, 2001 p. 479-496). The political definition of reconciliation is along the same lines as the Christian definition. According to Redonnet, the concept, in the modern political and collective sense, confirms the meaning of returning to normal relations after an argument or quarrel, of putting oneself at peace with others and with oneself.

Nowadays, the term reconciliation is necessary in many situations and in many countries, such as Afghanistan, Libya, Congo, or Mali where all are exhausted to speak of “reconciliation”. This is the case of the multidimensional crisis that Mali experienced from 2012, and which pushed the State to enter a period of transition marked by the signing of an Agreement for Peace and Reconciliation (APR or Accord) in Mali, ratified by all parties to the conflict in June 2015 (ASFC, 2017). Everywhere, reconciliation appears as the ideal end of a violently interrupted story (Rosoux, 2014) . Hattam, Atkinson and Bishop (2012) explain that reconciliation is the antithesis of violence and its ravages. Reconciliation, as a crucial part of the transitional justice strategy, can fail if a specific or short-term deadline is set to try to achieve it internally. Bloomfield, (2000) argues that many people, especially those affected (victims and relatives of victims) who are very affected by serious human rights violations, are wary of reconciliation and see it as an excuse to ignore their suffering.

For Hughes & Kostovicova (2018), the concept of reconciliation has been studied since the 1990s and has broadened as a field of study. This study has been extended in several contexts and in several sectors of activity such as reconciliation in the professional environment or reconciliation after violent conflict. However, much of the literature tends to develop the problems by establishing and then contradicting a set of periodicals (Little and Maddison, 2017). The notion itself is often known in a normative way with ambiguous and ill-defined transformations and final objectives certain mechanisms of transitional justice such as truth and reconciliation commissions. This creates confusion in the interpretation by all the players. Despite this, the notion continues to be broadly supported as the foundation for a lasting and indispensable peace to be able to move a society which has suffered conflict, serious human rights violations and massive destruction of property towards a future fraternal, peaceful, and friendly future. According to Hughes & Kostovicova (2018), scholars of reconciliation and international law have always maintained that the success of reconciliation and transitional justice is an essential condition for strengthening, consolidating peace and stability, and creating incentives and related benefits, such as nation building, democratization, and economic and social recovery from devastating conflict.

In addition, some academics, and practitioners such as Hughes and Kostovicova (2018) see reconciliation as a necessary precondition because they recognise that once a political resolution of the conflict has been reached, a process must run smoothly. For these researchers and practitioners, the heart of conflict resolution to move towards reconciliation is political will. The settlement of disputes between the protagonists must consider all the unresolved issues of the conflict to find solutions to avoid any questioning of the settlement, or even a return to violence (Fischer, 2011). With the top-down approach, the belief is that for local dynamics to change, national interventions must first take place. After that, this change can be filtered out locally. On the contrary, the main area of reconciliation work of a bottom-up approach is to improve interpersonal relationships among community members. Here, local reconciliation is seen as the key to success (Huyse, 2003). Much empirical research on specific conflicts increasingly calls into question the normative claims that underlie the term reconciliation. Hughes & Kostovicova, (2018) argue that this has led to a clear divergence between the exaggeration of normative claims out of context, about how processes should be conducted and what they should accomplish, from real and lived practice experience. Huyse (2003) also discusses this divergence. Theoretically, reconciliation strengthens and consolidates peace, prevents the past from being a seed of repeated conflict and consolidates newly established democratic institutions.

Fischer (2011) goes on to say that reconciliation is essential in societies where an ethno-political conflict process has taken place, because these conflicts have created and left among people loss of confidence, trauma, after-effects, grievances, and bitterness. In these situations, reconciliation is necessary to avoid the spirit of revenge, even repetition. To achieve this reconciliation, reciprocity is essential, as the truths about the crimes committed must be recognised to achieve some degree of reconciliation (Fischer, 2011). Gibson (2006) indicates that while there are many avenues of reconciliation, truth is an increasingly popular choice among those seeking to forget the past for a more peaceful, peaceful, peaceful, and democratic future. (Bloomfield, 2003), in turn, argues that the search for truth is only one element of reconciliation, as is justice. He insists that truth and justice are not separate from reconciliation, but on the contrary, they are key principles with which the process of reconciliation must be associated. Maddison (2017) does not say otherwise. He explains that many different avenues for reconciliation have been used to build peace

by states and academics, especially in a variety of contexts due to very different histories, populations, and intentions. The context of every conflict is different, as is post-conflict democratic settlement. As a result, the reconciliation process will be different from all others in its context, even though it has many similarities (Bloomfield, 2003). In addition, in a situation of perceived serious human rights violations and atrocities, if only one tool is used to remedy these violations, reconciliation is unlikely to be achievable. Healing, the search for truth, justice and reparation are the foundations and principles of the reconciliation process, but long-term investments are also essential, such as educational programmes and activities to raise awareness of human rights (Huyse, 2003).

Another very important aspect of reconciliation, according to Pankhurst (1999), is that there are many different levels of reconciliation. One of the levels of reconciliation is the psychology of the victims. It is necessary to consider what is psychologically necessary for an individual to forget his traumatic experience and come to terms with the past. In general, this concern does not correspond to what might be necessary for a society to reconcile (Pankhurst, 1999). The two approaches presented by Little and Maddison (2017) overlap with these different levels of analysis. On the one hand, the maximalist approach emphasizes interpersonal reconciliation. It refers to a religious or medical model, through terms such as healing, forgiveness, and apologies. On the other hand, the minimalist approach is associated with transformations of institutions and socio-political processes. It is accepted in this approach that conflict is intrinsic to politics and the desire to overcome social divisions is therefore secondary (Little and Maddison, 2017).

Little and Maddison (2017) argue that the two approaches can be ambiguous and even problematic. They argue that any truly political reconciliation must look to the past to acknowledge the harm done to victims, but also to alleviate or redress current injustices (Maddison, 2017). Bloomfield (2003) believes that it is essential to understand the past, but also to understand how people explain or interpret this past. People will always ask a thousand questions about the root causes of the conflict. Wale (2014) indicates that there will always be historical and objective problems and subjective perceptions. When it comes to historical and objective questions, people will always ask who killed who, who destroyed what, who raped whom or who judged

unfairly. However, in the subjective perceptions of this story, people will ask questions such as why someone did what they did. In general, these perceptions, explanations, and interpretations of what happened, instead of what happened, will make the story susceptible to a process of reconciliation (Bloomfield, 2003). To study and analyse these perceptions and interpretations, framing could be an essential tool.

Reconciliation is influenced by many factors which vary depending on the context. To promote reconciliation, the context in which it is undertaken plays a determining role. Reconciliation has neither an instinctive approach nor a formula. Its secret is unique: to sufficiently study the other, to know him and to act correctly (Dawson, 2001). Reconciliation cannot be imposed either by decree (Rosoux, 2008) or by media campaign because there is no single frame of reference indicating the different stages to be put in place for reconciliation. It cannot be reduced to a carefully ordered set of rules. It is linked to personal motivations. That is why it involves innovation, imagination, risk, and exploration. Many researchers and practitioners view reconciliation as a direction, not a fact, a goal or perspective rather than an outcome. Desmond Tutu, former chairman of the South African Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC), admits: "The reasonable mission of our commission is not to achieve reconciliation but to promote it" (Hayner, 2002, p. 156). These perspectives argue that reconciliation is not an event, but a slow process. Its development depends on several factors, including the interests, will and broad participation of all parties concerned. These factors cannot be rushed. As R. Fisher (2001) argues, values and conscience challenge people to come to terms with each other, but emotions, because they are so powerful, discourage them. As such, reconciliation is seen as an experience of changing emotions. As Kraybill points out, true healing (reconciliation) involves the unity of head and heart. The headsets goals and seeks to achieve them. The heart determines the content of emotions. Fortunately, the two converge (Kraybill, 1988, pp. 2–3). Besides the emotions, the recreation of trust between yesterday's enemies is not a quick thing. Restoring relationships is a delicate exercise; this requires great trust, a development network, and a sustained and prolonged commitment. Reconciliation is a matter of discipline, patience, even faith. This pace at which reconciliation is developing is not unusual given its demanding nature. These demands, along with political and economic constraints, make reconciliation a difficult process. Reconciliation is not just a process. It's a long process. It takes time; it will

take time to develop (Bloomfield *et al.*, 2004). No one can impose their own rhythm. But the mere passage of time is not enough to promote reconciliation. Adequate measures such as the establishment of mechanisms and structures for good governance, justice, poverty reduction and others to support the process must be taken. The collapse of the walls of hatred and psychological resentment does not necessarily follow the discourse of political actors and NGOs. Moreover, even when she is officially on the move, there is no indication that she will continue her way. Indeed, in societies traumatised by long and cruel violence, the risks of turning back are enormous. In Ghana, the Dagbon, Konkomba-Nanumba and Kusasi-Manprusi conflicts are examples, while in Senegal, the conflict in the Casamance region is another low-intensity conflict.

Reconciliation is a profound process. It touches on the areas of beliefs, attitudes, feelings and even emotions. (Bar-Tal and Bennink, 2004) state that reconciliation is a process that goes beyond the formal conflict resolution agenda to change the motivations, goals, beliefs, attitudes, and emotions of a great deal. majority of members of societies concerned by the conflict (Bar-Tal and Bennink, 2004). For these authors, this change must also affect the nature of relations between all parties and lay the foundations for lasting peace. So, reconciliation is also about changing the nature of each group's identity from the image of the enemy to that of the friend. As Rosoux (2008) notes, deadly conflicts tend to establish enemy images, and these dominate impressions. Recourse to the past as a starting point for reconciliation is often a major obstacle to reconciliation efforts. This cannot therefore claim to be a simple compromise of facade. He must bring to the surface the horrors of the past and attempt to iron out the differences based on full information. The fear of facing the horrors of the past and settling for half-truths is no guarantee of stability. On the contrary, it risks a fatal blow to the whole process, because it will be seen as an unfair step. In this regard, Huyse warns that a reconciliation based on ambiguity will not last (Huyse, 2004 p.28). For his part, Bloomfield points out that reconciliation is a process of acceptance of a reality deemed imperfect which requires everyone to change attitudes, aspirations, emotions, feelings, and perhaps even beliefs (p. 16). As a profound process, reconciliation requires strategies that seek to change the psychological repertoire of members of society (Ackermann, 1994) and calls for the disclosure of the horrors of the past. Thus, reconciliation must burst the abscess to

heal the sick, society. The process of reconciliation risks being discredited if this painful reality is not known if the past in all its dimensions is not examined if the crimes and the perpetrators are not identified. Reconciliation must be a broad and inclusive process. The debate on which groups or actors should initiate and participate in reconciliation processes is far from over. Theorists differ on this point. Some believe that reconciliation is about the people, others argue that reconciliation is primarily the responsibility of the authorities. Our intention is not to decide, nor to give a definitive position on this subject, especially since the combination of these two models seems effective (Rosoux, 2008), but to show that the two approaches are not exclusive, and that the reconciliation process is more inclusive.

Reconciliation, as a nation-building program, is not limited to those who have suffered directly and to those who have inflicted that suffering on them. While both categories of people are at the heart of any reconciliation process, the attitudes, images, beliefs, and behaviours that underlie violent conflict spread more widely to communities that identify with one or the other group (Bloomfield *et al.*, 2004). It is at this broader level that reconciliation must be envisaged, under penalty of isolating the victims and their torturers and thus fragmenting society. Perhaps only reconciliation processes following isolated conflicts and very limited effects can ignore this aspect. In Rwanda, for example, the need for reconciliation concerns the large social groups to which the executioners and their victims belong or identify. Thus, all Tutsis consider themselves, to a certain extent, as victims, even survivors of the genocide. They start from the idea that if they had been there at the time of the genocide, they would have been killed or would have survived whereas almost all Hutus share the shame of this tragedy perpetrated in their name. In this regard, the conviction of (Staub *et al.*, 2005) against Tutsis coming from outside Rwanda after the genocide is very significant: "But those who returned from the genocide had very difficult and painful experiences. They or their parents left Rwanda after previous massacres. They also found it very difficult to forgive and reconcile their parents, with a life of refugees and exiles in other countries. A reconciliation process is only promising if it benefits from the political guidance of the authorities and the broad support of the population. The political authorities are responsible for creating a favourable climate for the conduct of debates on reconciliation, a precondition for improving relations between populations (Shriver, 1999). Not only is leadership participation important for any reconciliation process, but

it is also increasingly seen as a political imperative. For some authors, the greatest compensation that can be granted to traumatised populations is to guarantee them an environment conducive to social rapprochement (Villa-Vicencio *et al.*, 2003).

In addition to this complementarity of the bottom-up and top-down reconciliation models, it is important to note that the participation of intermediate opinion leaders is important. The intervention of church leaders, local and international NGOs, agencies, and foreign states strengthens the credibility of the process and reassures victims and perpetrators or their relatives. As a result, reconciliation is also a complex process. Although no reference is made to all studies, key works are nonetheless identified. These were selected because they fall within the scope of this study. Subotic (2015) in her study "Truth, justice and reconciliation on the ground: normative divergence in the Western Balkans" indicates the importance of international normative interventions. She found that transitional justice and the elements of truth-seeking, justice and reconciliation were extremely divergent in the Western Balkans (Subotic, 2015). The application of these elements was impossible because the standards of transitional justice were the subject of a different appeal for national groups. Jelena explains that the concepts of reconciliation, truth and justice have very different meanings for victims, perpetrators, and the state because they are at odds with what they really want (Subotic, 2015). Subotic mentions that in Serbia for example, according to the law, reparations should only be inflicted on Serbian victims if the crimes were committed by an enemy force. Due to this law, the victims were not able to accept compensation for crimes committed by Serbian troops.

Hatred between different groups has prevented them from agreeing on transitional justice mechanisms due to the number of political agendas at stake where all parties seek justice. These judges have a different meaning for each group, which makes reconciliation difficult (Subotic, 2015). Kohen, Zanchelli and Drake also conducted a study on personal and political reconciliation in post-genocide Rwanda. The study examines the process of reparation, peace and justice for healing and reconciliation after the genocide in Rwanda. The results of the study show that there is a problem in the reconciliation process due to the lack of honest public discussions about ethnicity in Rwanda. The Tutsis and the Hutus deny and maintain that they are the victims of the genocide. The authorities find it difficult to fulfil their responsibilities and bring

justice to the victims. This situation posed a problem in the process of victim reconciliation (Kohen, Zanchelli and Drake, 2011). The creation and use of Gacaca have made a positive contribution to the reconciliation process. This community justice calmed the anger of the political opposition. Gacaca emphasized the prevention of genocide and ethnic divisions. He also put an end to oppressive tendencies towards the government. Kohen, Zanchelli and Drake, (2011) argue that the redress process is called into question because perpetrators are executed instead of offering a public apology and forgiveness.

The achievement of forgiveness and reconciliation between these ethnic groups remains to be resolved Parent (2015), in her study “Linking healing and reconciliation for lasting peace in Bosnia and Herzegovina”, analyses the link between healing and reconciliation. According to her, many peacebuilding programs and processes are based on the distinction between healing and reconciliation, but when the link between healing and reconciliation is broken, peacebuilding creates experiences of secondary victimisation that undermine the process of healing can compromise the peace. Parent (2015) supported this argument by considering the case of Bosnia and Herzegovina. The results of his study show that the victims interviewed denounce the difficulty of accessing mental health services. Reduced access to psychosocial support and the nature of psychosocial assistance can lead to increased trauma, further limiting the possibilities for healing and reconciliation. According to (Parent, 2015), the main common factors - obstructing or hindering healing and reconciliation processes - were identified from interviews conducted as part of this field research. These factors are post-conflict responses that persist, can intensify and hinder healing and reconciliation processes, and increase the potential for future violence. According to her, two post-conflict psychological reactions were highlighted during the interviews: mistrust and fear. The author argues that other consequences could be identified as this study progresses. The results of previous studies confirm those of Parent (2015). This is the case Avdibegovic et al. (2008) who previously argued that in Bosnia and Herzegovina, political authorities provide minimal financial support for psychosocial support; the number of NGOs and foreign organizations dedicated to psychosocial work is declining and (Fassin and Rechtman, 2007) (Pandolfi 2010, Pupavac 2002), which also confirms that the carefully designed international psychosocial model leaves its

beneficiaries in a precarious situation, powerless and dependent (Fassin and Rechtman, 2007).

In their 2019 study, Actions pour la protection des droits de l'Homme (APDH) and the German Foundation Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung (KAS) analysed the reconciliation process in Côte d'Ivoire and found that the government has initiated different stages of the transitional justice process through the establishment of the National Commission of Inquiry (CNE), the Dialogue, Truth and Reconciliation Commission (CDVR), the military tribunal (TM) and the special investigation unit and instruction (CSEI). Unfortunately, the results of the study show that the government does not seem willing to reconcile or, at least, even if public initiatives exist, it may not seem willing enough to engage the country, on the path of reconciliation and lasting peace. According to the report, the initiatives have not failed but they appear not to have been effective. It turns out that political speeches are ambivalent in content and direction. At the same time as they advocate appeasement, it is not uncommon for them to be vehement and carry the seeds of violence. James Gibson investigates local perceptions and the impact of South African public attitudes towards amnesty (Gibson, 2002). The research is conducted among people who fought apartheid, the victims, their families, and ordinary people like you in 2000/2001. The question was whether the amnesty was fair or not. The results of the investigation showed that the amnesty is unfair, not only to the victims and their families, but also to "ordinary citizens". Perceptions of the fairness of amnesty change by almost 40 percentage points when other forms of procedural, retributive, restorative, and distributive justice are present. Gibson (2002) says monetary compensation has had the greatest influence on perceptions of fairness in granting amnesties. However, other types of justice, in particular restorative justice (apologies) have also had an influence.

Minde, Roop and Tronvoll (2019), in "The Turbulent Political History of Zanzibar and its Impact on Contemporary Conflict and Reconciliation" through semi-structured interviews with leaders and actors of the Zanzibar reconciliation process, as well as secondary literature. Commonwealth Muafaka I's attempts at reconciliation were doomed, largely due to the incumbent President's lack of political will. The failure of Muafaka I fuelled discord and discontent, leading to the post-election violence of 2000. Since then, Zanzibar has suffered three more institutionalized attempts at political

reconciliation with the establishment of a government of national unity. (GNU) in 2010 which unfortunately after only one mandate was dissolved. Benghellab (2016), "From myths to the realities of transitional justice. Therapeutic: Catharsis, (re) building of the nation and political legitimation" aims to question the foundations of transitional justice and to face the therapeutic, legal, and political missions in terms of observed results. Benghellab (2016) finds that specialists in transitional justice do not ask themselves why processes fail when they do. According to him, the structural causes of these failures are very rarely identified. The author adds that people think they understand the failures of JT only as flaws to be overcome, rather than as linked to the problematic nature of the mechanism itself. Benghellab (2016) maintains that lukewarm criticism suggests that it is necessary to perpetuate this mechanism with cosmetic reforms, complacent reforms so as not to enter an absolute delegitimization of the mechanism. He goes on to say that since transitional justice continues to be seen as a step of progress, no one wants to make deep and real reforms. Benghellab (2016) calls on states, international organisations, and non-governmental organizations to keep in mind the fundamental aspect of transitional justice, although underlying, and not to treat it as a primary redress mechanism or neutral of the social fabric, but only as a complementary tool to other devices and less admirable intentions. According to him, it is necessary to present this tool and this resource as a simple temporary and circumstantial remedy for deep societal wounds. It does not imply to hope to do anything other than to venture into new conceptual and truly alternative paths, such as the mechanisms of restorative justice. But once again, it calls for vigilance with the concepts of restoration which are often articulated with practices of forgiveness, which pose a new series of equally delicate questions. Using individual data, academics and practitioners want to understand reparations from the perspective of victims. David and Choi (2005), for example, used individual data collected from former political prisoners in the Czech Republic to analyse the impact of reparations programs. The results of the study showed that the financial compensation and reinstatement of previous professions satisfied the former prisoners. Unfortunately, former detainees were not satisfied with reconciliation measures, such as the author's apologies and telling the truth, which precluded any socio-political redress (David and Choi, 2005). Laplante and Theidon (2007), in their study in Peru, on the impact of reparations on the rural poor, found that victims' demand for justice was dominated by the need for farm animals, adequate housing or their children's education. The authors

found that, unlike Argentina, where the relatives of the disappeared refused to receive compensation, considering that it was a means for the State to escape responsibility criminal, Peruvian victims were forced to accept this compensation because of poverty and misery (Laplante and Theidon, 2007).

3.3 Restoration social ties and reconciliation

Marshall offers a certain definition of restorative justice:

“A process whereby the parties with a stake in a particular offense come together to resolve collectively how to deal with the aftermath of the offense and its implications for the future”

(Marshall, 1996, p.37).

This Marshall's definition of restorative justice is eminently open-ended. Due to the vagueness that characterises it, it leaves several questions unanswered: who is targeted by the reparation? what is it about re-establishing? Certainly, Marshall's intention is confined to a general universal description and does not aim at a theory of restorative justice, but by its very openness, his description contains the seeds of a theory of restorative justice. Indeed, restorative justice does not force situations to adapt to theories. On the contrary, it is based on a theory flexible and adaptable enough to apply at different levels and in a variety of contexts. Nor is a restorative approach limited to one person, but it also applies to groups and institutions. Braithwaite emphasises these important features of restorative justice, but along the way he falls into the trap of presenting the mechanisms of restorative justice as a simple alternative to retributive justice. In doing so, he risks losing sight of the unifying concept that explains and legitimises this solution as justice itself, which prevents it from offering a true theory of restorative justice. Ness (2002) goes beyond a simple description of the practice to identify some of the elements that define restorative justice. He notes some common elements that emerge from the corpus, limited in number but growing, concerning restorative justice. It is a definition of the crime as an attack on injured persons and against the social order, an effort to consider the personal damages suffered by all parties as well as the financial and legal obligations of the offenders, as well than the promise to invite all parties to respond to the crime (Ness, 2002). These common elements of restorative justice practices provide a better

understanding of the conception of justice that underlies these practices. However, Van Ness's explanation remains more descriptive than definitional.

3.4 Differentiation of justice

To understand the regime of justice as reparation, it is important to understand how this conception differs from other modern theories of justice. Three great theories of justice collide today: restitutive justice, corrective justice, and retributive justice. Restorative justice has some commonalities with each of these theories. Restorative justice pays them off for what they have best, while filling their gaps. As a common law concept, restitution conveys the idea that a gain that has been taken or misused must be returned. Restitution requires that in the name of justice, the perpetrator of an offense returns to the victim what he has taken from him, the idea being that by his actions, he has enriched himself at the expense of the latter. By renouncing the benefit of his actions and returning the stolen property to its rightful owner, the offender is righting the wrong that has been done. Therefore, restitution as a response to the moral question "something must be done" means that things must be put back to the state before the offense. The perpetrator must give back to his victim the very thing that was taken. The strength of restitution is that it is more victim-oriented than, for example, retribution. By emphasising returning what was taken back to the victim, restitution puts the injured party at the heart of any attempt to deliver justice. According to Van Ness, restitution has its roots in justice systems which regard a crime as harm suffered more by the victim than by the government (Ness, 2002). Restorative justice, too, looks at the harm committed by the perpetrator and the person harmed by the perpetrator. In other words, both restorative justice and restitutive justice are focused on the outcome of the action, not on the inherent nature of the action. However, restorative justice is not limited to victims. It extends to the offender and the community to respond to the harm suffered by the victim. This expanded focus is one of the products of the difference between restorative justice and restorative justice in terms of interpreting the harm resulting from the offense and what to do to remedy the situation. Restitution is not sufficient to redress the harm suffered by the victim after the offense. Justice as restitution is a narrow vision of a justice that simply straightens the scales by making sure that each party ends up as it started out. This justice has its eyes on the past since it is oriented towards the status quo ante. Restitution wants things to become as they were before the offense. By contrast, restorative justice is

not about restoring the status quo ante. As for corrective justice, it recognises the intangible aspect of the harm resulting from the actions of the offender. Using compensatory damages, corrective justice seeks to rectify the inequality created by the violation of the victim's rights (Weinrib, 1995). Therefore, corrective justice responds to the failure of restitution to deal with the non-material aspects of the harm resulting from the offense. Corrective justice lays down the precept that the offense is not only an infringement of the possession of material property by the victim, but an infringement of one of his rights. However, corrective justice offers the same response to such harm as restitution to material loss, that is, the transfer from the perpetrator to the victim of the offense. When we apply this notion of transfer to what is intangible, corrective justice reveals, paradoxically, the lack of logic in its notion that a transfer from the perpetrator to the victim of the offense will produce their equality. Restitutive justice and restorative justice are both constrained by the commitment to the notion of transfer to achieve equality. Retributive justice, for its part, does not share this commitment. In a sense, the concept advocated by retributive justice is in fact more closely associated with restorative justice than the other two concepts. Retributive justice and restorative justice share common conceptual ground in their commitment to establishing or restoring social equity between the perpetrator and the victim of a crime. The starting point of retributive justice is the repair of equality in the social fabric. Yet, as soon as one understands this shared commitment to repairing social equity, one begins to understand how restorative theory and retributive theory diverge from their conceptual common ground.

Retributive theory identifies the achievement of social equity with a particular set of historical practices (typical of a wide range of societies) often known as retribution. In other words, retributive justice names punishment as a necessary means of achieving equality; it identifies the very notion of reparation with that of punishment. It seeks to restore social fairness through retribution against the offender, isolating him from the rest of society. On the other hand, restorative justice addresses the problem of the choice of practices that can, in a certain context, achieve the objective of restoring social equity. Therefore, for restorative justice theory, identifying these practices requires social dialogue involving the perpetrator and victim of the offense, as well as the community, and requires the concrete consideration of the need of each of the parties to obtain redress (Bakan and Schneiderman, 1992).

3.5 The relational orientation of restorative justice

Thanks to this comparison with other conceptions of justice, important knowledge has been acquired about restorative justice. These insights are now used in the discussion below to describe the relational and conciliatory orientation of restorative justice. According to the description of justice, it is a response to a moral challenge: something must be done. Restorative justice says that to satisfy this moral sense, that "thing" that needs to be done is to establish or restore equality. This allows us to know why such a feeling exists in the absence of anything that disturbed the order. Therefore, if justice means equality, our moral sense will be (or should be) challenged whenever things are out of balance or unequal. However, we have seen that justice cannot deal with equality in abstraction. Rather, this equality must be social equity. If justice is a human concern, it must be centred on equality between humans. Therefore, justice must be about establishing or restoring social equity, not an abstract notion of moral equality.

Social equity therefore means equality in relationships. It exists when relations are such that each party enjoys its right to dignity, care, and respect. Restorative justice aims to restore relationships, to right the wrong, it is obvious that reparation cannot mean a return to the status quo ante, to the situation just before the offense. As such, restorative justice is fundamentally relational, and this is what sets it apart from other conceptions of justice. Indeed, the offense is not only the cause of the inequality, but also often the result of a pre-existing inequity. Therefore, restoring the situation to what it was before the offense will often not be enough to resolve the relationship problems that allowed or perpetuated the abuse. In fact, instead of aiming at the harm and ensuring that it does not happen again, we must focus on the state of the social relationship in which the offense took place and try to establish an ideal state of equality. The relational orientation of restorative justice is clear: while the harm of the offenses is the harm done to the targeted relationship, the offender also suffers the harm because he is also interested in those relationships. This is not to say that the only wrongs that concern restorative justice are abstract damage to relationships. In fact, both tangible and intangible harm (e.g., loss of property or income, medical costs, loss of sense of security, psychological damage, etc.) arise from the breakdown of social equity relationships. Relationships of dignity, care, and respect in equality (social equity) would not allow such damage. It is only in the event of a breakdown or lack of social fairness that the infringement occurs and harm results. When the harm

is felt by all parties involved in relationships damaged by the offense or conflict, it is clear why the restorative approach requires everyone's participation. It is therefore important to consider who "the parties" are and their roles in the application of restorative justice.

Restorative justice is an attempt to ensure the satisfaction of all those involved in the offense by giving them an active role in the resolution of the conflict. Thus, the restorative justice model benefits everyone because, beyond the state and the offender, it widens the circle of people interested in victims and the community. Restorative justice is part of a human logic that is likely to allow the victim, the perpetrator, and the community to obtain satisfaction and to be reconciled. Thus, from the victim's point of view, restorative justice measures provide an important framework by which their victimhood is recognised and their reparation, both material and symbolic, is fully accomplished. As for the offender, restorative justice is also interested in his needs by encouraging him to assume his responsibilities, to repair the harm done to the victim and to the community and to improve his behaviour, which will promote his social reintegration. Through the social (re) integration of the protagonists, the social bonds broken by the conflict are re-established and the peace of the community is restored.

The restorative justice process responds to the victim's need to be informed about the reasons and circumstances of the crime committed. The victim needs to know the truth by directly or indirectly asking questions about the offense and the perpetrator who primarily has this information (Salas, 2012). The answers to these questions can ease his suffering. Without the answers to these questions, the victim will feel frustrated and tend to blame themselves and others. For the victim, the satisfaction of the need for information is important to regain the sense of control that was acquired by the offender at the time of the offense (Bazemore and Schiff, 2001). In addition, the victim has the right to be heard, he needs to tell the story of what happened when meeting the perpetrator. Thanks to this freedom of expression, this right to speak, the emotional and psychological damage that the victim, her family and loved ones endured are brought to light and known to all. This recognition contributes to the healing of the victim, to the symbolisation of their experience of victimisation and to reconciliation between them and the perpetrator as well as with the community. The victim, by

speaking directly to the offender, can see him take responsibility for his actions, realise the consequences that flow from them, apologise, and swear that it will no longer harm the victim or others (Bennett 2007).

The victim desires to be released from the pain and anger that overwhelms him and wishes future safety for himself and for other potential victims; the desire for material compensation for the damage suffered is also present in some victims, but is generally not a priority (Aertsen, 2003; Umbreit et al., 2006). The victim who has had a restorative justice experience feels much better in several aspects: less fear of the aggressor, less feeling of risk of being a victim again, better feeling of security, less anger towards the aggressor, more high confidence in others, more self-confidence, less anxiety (Sherman and Strang, 1997, p. 65). In other words, this approach to justice helps alleviate the victim's fears and transcend the trauma that they have suffered. The victim can regain the sense of security and belonging violated because of the crime with the support of family, loved ones and communities. Unlike restorative justice, in the traditional criminal justice system, the victim suffers from a triple marginalisation (Schiff, 2007): he first suffers from a marginalisation caused by the perpetrator of the offense, then he suffers from a marginalisation caused by the family, relatives and members of the community who cannot give his lasting support, finally, he suffers from a marginalisation caused by the criminal trial because the interest that is in her carried ceases when the offender is found guilty. Restorative justice aims to ensure that the victim (direct and / or indirect) is repaired both materially and symbolically (Schiff, 2007). Material reparation is necessary for the victim to recover from the effects of the crime, but symbolic reparation can be even more important because it can make a substantial difference in the victim's life (Schiff, 2007). According to Strang (2004), an English criminologist, studies of victims over the past decade show that victims want symbolic reparation more, mainly an apology and the sincere expression of remorse than material reparation (Strang, 2004). In cooperation with the offender and, where appropriate, with members of the community, the victim can participate and determine the content of the most equitable reparation programme. Restorative justice does not exist only to meet the expectations of victims. Its interest is also in the needs of offenders.

3.6 The Relationship Between Reconciliation, Non-Recurrence, and Nation-Building

This section examines the interconnected relationships among reconciliation, non-recurrence, and nation-building in post-conflict and post-authoritarian societies. It explores how these elements work together to foster stability and peace, particularly in contexts marked by a legacy of historical violence, oppression, and discrimination. The analysis draws on case studies and empirical evidence to illustrate the significance of addressing these intertwined concepts for repairing social fabric, restoring trust among communities, and preventing the resurgence of past injustices. By analyzing the interactions among reconciliation, non-recurrence, and nation-building, this section aims to demonstrate the essential role these dimensions play in achieving long-term social stability.

The Role of reconciliation

Reconciliation serves as a crucial process designed to repair damaged relationships among individuals, communities, and governmental entities in the aftermath of conflict. Lederach (1997) posits that reconciliation encompasses the principles of truth, justice, mercy, and peace, which are essential for fostering coexistence and enhancing mutual understanding between former opponents. Central to the reconciliation process are truth-telling and the recognition of historical injustices, often facilitated by initiatives such as truth commissions and the documentation of history. A notable instance of this is the South African Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC), created to illuminate the atrocities committed during apartheid and affirm the experiences of its victims (Tutu, 1999). Furthermore, accountability mechanisms, including both restorative and retributive justice approaches such as judicial proceedings, amnesty arrangements, and reparations, play a vital role in promoting healing (United Nations, 2004). The enactment of symbolic gestures, such as public apologies and efforts to memorialize events, contributes to the development of a collective national identity (Gibson, 2004). In the absence of a comprehensive reconciliation process, societies may remain divided, with unresolved issues posing a risk of reigniting conflict and hindering efforts toward nation-building.

Ensuring non-recurrence

Non-recurrence emphasizes the creation of institutional, legal, and social structures designed to avert the repetition of previous injustices or violence. According to the United Nations (2015), three fundamental pillars are essential for achieving non-recurrence: reforms in legal and judicial systems, improvements in security sector governance, and advancements in educational and cultural practices. It is crucial to reinforce the rule of law and ensure accountability for offenders to restore public confidence in governmental institutions. The implementation of Gacaca courts in Rwanda serves as a notable example of integrating restorative justice principles while addressing the socio-political consequences of genocide (Clark, 2010; Hinton, 2017). Strengthening civilian oversight of security forces and removing political influence from the military are vital steps in mitigating the risks of authoritarianism and the resurgence of conflict. Additionally, initiatives aimed at transforming educational narratives, fostering pluralism, and countering hate speech play a significant role in reducing the likelihood of societal divisions re-emerging (Elkins & Ginsburg, 2020; Zartman, 2005). By embedding these reforms within legal and institutional frameworks, efforts toward non-recurrence ensure that reconciliation transcends mere superficiality, actively addressing the challenge of unresolved grievances that could lead to renewed violence.

The Process of Nation-Building

Nation-building is the broader process of forming a cohesive national identity, establishing robust institutions, and creating an inclusive, effective state. Fukuyama (2004) argues that nation-building requires both institutional and cultural elements, necessitating inclusive governance and active political participation. Attention to social and economic development is also crucial for enhancing civic identity and social cohesion. In post-genocide Rwanda, national unity policies promoted by the National Unity and Reconciliation Commission (NURC) have emphasized the importance of a unified national identity (Beswick, 2010; Umutesi, 2004). Rebuilding infrastructure, providing equitable economic opportunities, and addressing socio-economic disparities are vital for long-term stability (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012; Collier, 2009). A collective sense of belonging reinforced through national symbols and cultural integration can significantly bolster a state's legitimacy (Anderson, 1983).

Interplay Between Reconciliation and Non-Recurrence in Nation-Building

The processes of reconciliation and non-recurrence are fundamental components of effective nation-building. Reconciliation plays a crucial role in cultivating trust and collaboration among various communities, vital for the establishment of a stable nation. Concurrently, non-recurrence addresses historical injustices, creating a framework that fosters stability and mitigates the risk of renewed conflict that could undermine nation-building efforts. Furthermore, nation-building itself establishes the institutional foundation necessary for the successful implementation of reconciliation and non-recurrence strategies. A comprehensive and inclusive state apparatus is more capable of facilitating healing and averting future societal fractures.

Case Studies: South Africa and Rwanda

South Africa and Rwanda illustrate the complex and occasionally divergent relationships between reconciliation, non-recurrence, and nation-building. In South Africa, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) aimed to foster national healing by revealing historical injustices and offering conditional amnesties (Tutu, 1999). Nevertheless, enduring socio-economic disparities and a lack of substantial structural reforms have resulted in ongoing tensions and divisions (Gibson, 2004; Seekings, 2008). Deficiencies in non-recurrence initiatives, particularly regarding economic justice and institutional changes, have hindered comprehensive nation-building. Conversely, Rwanda's Gacaca courts have created a platform for restorative justice and the resolution of genocide-related cases (Clark, 2010; Hinton, 2017). The governance and security reforms promoted by the National Unity and Reconciliation Commission (NURC) have contributed to stability, although issues related to political repression continue to pose challenges (Beswick, 2010; Reyntjens, 2011).

The interconnectedness of reconciliation, non-recurrence, and nation-building is essential for fostering enduring peace and development. Reconciliation seeks to heal historical rifts, non-recurrence aims to avert future conflicts, and nation-building promotes long-term stability through inclusive governance and socioeconomic progress. Societies that neglect the integration of these processes risk experiencing instability, particularly in post-conflict environments where reconciliation initiatives lack sufficient institutional backing or where mechanisms to prevent recurrence fail to stop

the return of violence. Therefore, successful nation-building necessitates a comprehensive approach that incorporates elements of truth, justice, reform, and inclusion, cultivating a unified and resilient community. Addressing the interdependencies among reconciliation, non-recurrence, and nation-building is both crucial and urgent for developing strategies that ensure peace and promote development in post-conflict settings.

3.7 Recognition: Towards the development of a formal ethics

Honneth (2002) divides the concept of recognition into three distinct spheres: firstly, the sphere of intersubjective intimacy (love), secondly the sphere of legal relationships (respect) and thirdly the sphere of solidarity (esteem or recognition of capacities and talents of value to society). Honneth (2002) draws inspiration from Hegel's philosophy to develop the thesis according to which the three models of recognition form general presuppositions allowing the formation of the personal integrity of individuals. To give an empirical form to his research, Honneth relies on work carried out in social psychology. It is notably inspired by the work of Mead (2006) which is based on an empirical social psychology. Mead, like Hegel, refers the formation of individual identity to the experience of intersubjective recognition.

According to Mead, the individual builds and develops through interactive exchanges: "When a self appears, it always involves the experience of another. Consequently, we cannot realise ourselves unless we recognise the other in his relation to us" (p. 165-166), hence the concept that he develops of "the generalised other", namely "typical image of the alter ego which, acquired on the basis of concrete social experience, is internalised by the subject as a constant pole of reference for his action and his contribution to oneself" (Fraser, Nancy 2005: 161)

Mead (2006), with a particular interest in the psychology of childhood, argues that recognition is vital for the formation of individual identity. However, even if Honneth relies on social psychology to develop his theory and demonstrate that recognition is essential to the development of the individual, he wants to avoid doing philosophical anthropology by limiting his theory to the modern period. Honneth (2002) indeed believes that contempt is one of the products of modernity and more particularly has developed through three great phenomena resulting from bourgeois liberal modernity (the family, law, and work). Thus, it is bourgeois society which has given rise to

contempt and, as a corollary, the need for recognition as Honneth defines it in his theory. In doing so, it is therefore the relational dimension of individual identity that is affected through the spheres of recognition: love, law, and solidarity.

Honneth defines love as

"All primary relationships which, on the model of erotic, friendly or family relationships, involve strong emotional bonds between a small number of people"

(Honneth, 2002: 117).

These relationships constitute the basic premise of all "self-realisation which constitutes the

"Process by which a subject develops capacities and characters about which the reactions of his partners cause them to think that they have a unique value for their social environment"

(Honneth, 2002: 105).

In other words, there is a link of interdependence between the presence of enduring affective bonds and the individual's capacities to realise his own worth and to acquire "self-confidence". Therefore, the intimate relationships of love produce a kind of inward-looking confidence, which comforts the individual both in the expression of his needs and in the use of his capacities (Honneth, 2002: 208). The individual develops a relationship of trust in relation to himself, and it is only when the individual reaches a certain level of self-confidence that he can subsequently develop self-respect and esteem of self. The second form of recognition which makes it possible to preserve and broaden the conditions for reciprocal recognition between subjects is done through law. Legal recognition, or being recognised as a subject of law, ensures the freedom and autonomy of individuals. Therefore, legal recognition refers to individual rights. It follows the logic according to which rights have as their *raison d'être* the protection of the autonomy and freedom of individuals. According to Honneth, the object of recognition is the individual. Therefore, the law recognises individuals and requires them to recognise each other as subjects. In other words, legal recognition

presupposes the moral responsibility of all its members (Honneth, 2002: 139). According to Honneth, the law offers opportunities for moral development. On one hand, the law can develop in a universalist or particularistic sense. Honneth affirms indeed that the moral potential, inherent in the right, can be developed through social struggles, in the sense of universality as much as in the sense of a better adaptation to different contexts (p201). In other words, the law is fundamentally focused on universality but also has the capacity to legally recognise the particularity of individuals through the recognition of their social and cultural groups. On the other hand, Honneth maintains that the development of civic, social, political, economic, identity rights which are the fruit, objectified in institutions, of social struggles carried out by social groups with a view to having institutions recognised a certain number of expressed needs (Honneth, 2002), can evolve as much in a direction progressive as conservative. History has provided numerous examples of how certain social groups or political movements have advanced or regressed rights. For instance, let us remember the civic movements led by black Americans in the United States. They have succeeded in the long term in significantly reducing civic and political discrimination against African Americans. Conversely, Nazism brought about a regression of civil and political rights, particularly for certain groups, such as Jews, opponents of the regime, certain intellectuals, etc. According to Honneth (2002), it is the function of critical theory to assess the legitimacy of social struggles waged by political groups and movements which claim and seek to have their rights recognised. Current social struggles, whether ecological, anti-globalisation, feminist or those led by ethno-cultural minorities, deserve to be assessed in the light of internal normative criteria which make it possible to determine their progressive or conservative character. Social solidarity is the third sphere of recognition which attributes to the individual the capacity to develop through relations of reciprocal recognition. According to Honneth,

“Solidarity is conditioned by symmetrical esteem relations between individualised (and autonomous) subjects; to esteem oneself in this sense is to see oneself reciprocally in the light of values which give the qualities and capacities of the other a significant role in the common practice”

(Honneth, 2002: 157).

Therefore, social esteem is attributed to individuals in relation to their skills and accomplishments of value to society. It is the social and professional identities of everyone that are the object of recognition. What is more, social consideration or "symmetrical esteem relations" do not imply that all individuals must esteem each other to the same degree.

The use of the word symmetrical refers to the idea that "each subject receives, outside any collective classification, the possibility of perceiving himself in his qualities and capacities as a precious element of society (Honneth, 2002). Therefore, the different collective values and ethical goals present within society provide a "guiding framework that can assist and serve as a reference system for evaluating individual traits" (P148). Thus, individuals learn to appreciate themselves differently and to self-determine in the light of the values conveyed within social networks and identity groups.

The three spheres of recognition constitute a political ethic which makes it possible to determine what are the legitimate expectations likely to be recognised by members of society. First, intimate relationships are essential to develop a relationship of self-confidence. Then, legal relationships allow self-respect through the protection of individual rights. Finally, relationships of solidarity aim to achieve self-esteem through the recognition of skills and talents of value to society. By the distinction made between the sphere of law and the sphere of solidarity, we find that, on one hand, it is individuals who are the object of recognition, and, on the other hand, it is the skills and abilities of individuals that are valued. The theory of Honneth is therefore individualistic and ignores the importance of collective rights allowing the survival or protection of cultural identity.

3.8 Recognition and transitional justice

In his theory, Honneth (1996) focuses on the structural transformation of recognition. As stated previously, according to Honneth, the differentiation between three social spheres of recognition that are the private / intimate sphere, the sphere of citizenship and the sphere of labour relations, finds its origin in the development and modernity of capitalist society. These spheres of recognition respond to three modes of recognition: love (self-confidence), legal rights (self-respect) and social esteem (self-esteem) (Honneth, 1996, p. 129). This tripartite division contains a variety of mutually recognising relationships, from early childhood experiences to political and social life.

This heuristic concept can be applied to the context of mass violence and armed conflict. There are similar patterns of forms of aggressive non-recognition. First, survivors of armed conflict or mass violence generally experience emotional lethargy, anxiety, mistrust, anguish, fear, sexual disturbance, shame, estrangement, others, self-destructive behaviours and / or restless sleep. These post-traumatic signs are evidence of the devastating effects of armed conflict on self-confidence and self-esteem. In the legal field, non-recognition means the deprivation of the right to have rights (Arendt). The practice of torture, disappearances, sexual assaults, massacres, assassinations, etc. shatters the worlds of life and disrupts identities. At the same time, however, the experience of non-recognition gives rise to the struggle for justice and recognition.

A major controversy in current debates revolves around the question of whether recognition has a positive consequence on identity. According to the theory of Honneth, recognition is a prerequisite for achieving a positive relationship with oneself. In Taylor's (1992) argument on multiculturalism, the author focuses on the public recognition of difference which is equal respect. Taylor believes that the recognition of cultures and ways of life is a prerequisite for self-respect and effective autonomy. However, there are puzzling views that highlight the ambivalence intrinsic to recognition practices. Recognition is both the standard to which we certainly aspire, and the name given to the process that is constantly in danger of being destroyed (Butler 2004: 133). The goal of recognition processes is to recognise identities that are shattered by poor recognition or non-recognition. At the same time, these identities are formed by recognition. Taylor admits that non-recognition can cause harm such as a form of oppression and imprisonment. Non-recognition can also distort or reduce (Taylor 1992: 25). This lucidity leads to the fundamental conclusion that ignorance is the only possible form of recognition (Bedorf 2010). Each act of recognition is surely an act of ignorance because it is imprecise and approximate regarding the perceived and recognised dimensions of identity. Bertram and Celikates (2015) present a problematic approach to recognition, emphasising that recognition standards are established and (counter) tested in and through conflict (Bertram and Celikates, 2015). They must always be reconstituted repeatedly, and they only come true when individuals or groups are able to negotiate divergent normative demands.

Recognition is a process that arranges the experiences of suffering in a specific way. For example, an injured person becomes an officially recognised victim, belonging to a specific category of victim through the recognition process. The "victim" is a socially created category, a figure that is created in various logical formations. Prejudice is the core of victimisation from the point of view of origins. However, the injured individual becomes a victim through self-identification and attribution by others. This type of recognition process refers to official recognition of criminal acts and responsibility as well as varying degrees of respect for distinct forms of victimisation. Günther (2013) argues that there has been a total shift in public acceptance of victims, excluding the heroic and passive victim and improving the status of the "pure" victim. Public recognition of victims of crimes in a certain dimension of victimisation is what is sought in recognition processes. It presupposes reciprocal relations and allows struggle and agitation. In a 1999 report, the United Nations (UN) Commission for Historical Clarification estimated the death toll at 200,000 during the 40-year war in Guatemala, which began with the capture of the United Nations power by Armas in 1954 and ended in 1996. But the tragedy began in 1982, after the coup d'état of General Efraim Rios Montt and the creation of the Civilian Self-Defence Patrols (PACs), which are militiamen recruited by the army, by force if necessary, and whose mission is the eradication of the guerrillas. Removed from his post in 1983, General Rios Montt never really left the political scene. Despite numerous legal proceedings, including one against Menchú, winner of the Nobel Peace Prize in 1992, he has always managed to escape justice. His latest coup was to win a parliamentary mandate in the 2007 elections, which gave him impunity for four years. This example illustrates a situation where recognition conflicts arise between groups and individuals as well as between groups, on the other. In a scenario like this, the post bellum transition presupposes a relationship between individuals, some of whom were victims and other executioners, in extreme cases, in addition to relationships between members of the community of victims, a complex social range that goes from collaborators to resistance fighters.

To this, the participation of outside forces in the escalation of violence must be added. Thus, the brutal government repression of popular movements in South America was largely financed by foreign investors, especially the large fruit companies. The demand for recognition of the victims is then exported from the inside to the outside, to recognise the real culprits. There is a conflict of recognition when determining the

effective role of each of the parties and the meaning of their participation in the atrocities committed during the war. It is more than difficult, in these conditions, to aim for a strong identification with a common good, even if everyone says they are seeking peace and justice. It is indeed very difficult to imagine how a society deeply divided by a civil war, as it was the case in Guatemala, can arrive at a unified vision of itself for and by the pursuit of common goals. The Congo war case is just one example among many to illustrate the application of recognition in transitional justice. In the aftermath of Mobutu's dictatorship, the Democratic Congo (DRC) has experienced one of the deadliest wars since World War II. A Truth and Reconciliation Commission was established in 2003 and an investigation by the International Criminal Court was carried out.

Despite the establishment of the TRC, the transition process is particularly complex in the country, due to a conflict that was both a civil war and an interstate war. To use the theoretical model of recognition, conflicts of recognition are at the same time between states, social groups, and individuals. To give an example of a conflict of recognition, it is a question of determining which will be the most suitable and legitimate legal body to judge past abuses. If this is an international tribunal, this may come at the expense of recognising the new Congo's ability to bring war criminals to justice itself. But, given the interstate nature of the conflict and the country's political instability, justice is unlikely to be done without international mediation. In other contexts, this could happen without major problems, but we are talking about a state whose civil war is the direct legacy of colonisation. The fact remains that it was the Congolese government itself that appealed to the UN for the creation of an international tribunal. Because of the massive number of war crimes committed in Congo, it appears vital that the hundreds of people who played a decisive role in the atrocities committed during the war be tried, if necessary, by an ad hoc tribunal like the mixed tribunal (local and international authority) found in Sierra Leone (Rodella, 2003).

The Congolese case offers an example of conflicts of recognition between individual demands and collective demands. The disarmament of the militias also involves the re-education of the militiamen, many of whom were or are child soldiers having known no other family than that of their combat unit. The social reintegration of these

individuals together with the problem of lustration, i.e., the operation which consists in ensuring that the staff of the new administrations are not made up of criminals or guilty agents, testifies to two conflicting requests for recognition, that of the collective administrative transition and that of individuals whose rejection by society could lead them to take up arms again.

Recognition is ambiguous. It enables the destructive effects of armed conflicts and mass violence to be overcome and is seen as a prerequisite for regaining a positive relationship with oneself (self-determination, self-esteem, effective autonomy). While recognition involves such a fundamental ambiguity that, with self-recognition and self-esteem dependent on recognition by an authority figure, uncertainties may arise as to the actual results of recognition practices. The ongoing controversies over the prerequisites and consequences of transitional justice recall the need to continue to discover methods that can lead to peace. Many activists such as (Bertram and Celikates, 2015) believe that recognition is of utmost importance for victims. At the same time, however, it includes a risk of misunderstanding. Transitional justice specialists such as (Hamber, 2009; Brounéus 2010; Doak 2011) have been debating this double-sided piece of recognition effects for some time.

Conclusion

This chapter consisted of the presentation of restorative justice as a component of transitional justice, of the Truth Commission. This justice aims to give victims, offenders, and society the satisfying feeling that “justice has been done”. It promotes the psychological reconstruction of the victim, the accountability of crisis actors and the reduction of recidivism. Therefore, the adoption of Restorative Justice methods, in addition to the recommendations of the Ivorian Truth Commission, would be beneficial in the Reconciliation process in Côte d’Ivoire. This is why in the section of this chapter, it was a question of contextualizing Restorative Justice and reconciliation in the field of transitional justice, as well as within the Truth Commission. The second section determined the relationship between restorative justice and reconciliation. Or examines the contribution, the contribution of restorative justice in the reconciliation process.

CHAPTER FOUR: METHODOLOGY AND METHODS

This chapter explains how this study was undertaken. The chapter first examines the research paradigm and design framework used. Then presents the restoration of social bonds and reconciliation, purposive sampling, and snowballing sampling. This chapter also deals with the collection and processing of data through a review of the literature and interviews. For the interview, the categories of the interviewees were presented, as well as the line of inquiry and the methods of analysing the resulting data. Finally, ethical and gender considerations were examined.

4.1 The research paradigm

In research philosophy, there are philosophical paradigms that researchers employ in narrowing down their research. These paradigms, including pragmatism, positivism, realism and interpretivism, can be adopted depending on the kind of research that is being carried out. Kuhn (1962) argues that a paradigm is related to a set of opinions, procedures, and practices, which inform and shape the evolution of science. He adds that Paradigms provide scientists not only with a map, but also some of the essential directions for mapping. Using a paradigm, I acquired theory, methods, and standards together, usually in an extractable mixture (Kuhn, 1962, p. 109). In their contribution to the debate about paradigms in the social sciences, Guba, and Lincoln (1994) define a paradigm as a set of fundamental (or metaphysical) beliefs that deal with ultimate or first principles (1994, p. 107). The paradigm informs me of what is important, what is legitimate, what is reasonable about the current study (Sarantakos, 1993, p. 30). The answers to epistemological, ontological, and methodological (Sarantakos, 1993) questions are relevant in determining their paradigmatic persuasion in the arguments of researchers.

This thesis adopts an interpretivist paradigm. It has been adopted for this study because it is complementary to the aim of the research, which is to assess the impact of Truth Commission through restorative justice in Cote d'Ivoire. In what ways? This approach allows me to reach an understanding of the social constructs of victims' reparation through interpretations of meanings and the process of the Ivorian Truth Commission. According to Thanh and Thanh (2015), the interpretive paradigm allows researchers to view the world through the perceptions and experiences of participants and stakeholders who have worked closely in the social setting of the phenomenon

being research. Hence, in seeking answers for this research, I drawn on stakeholder experiences to interpret the impacts of the Ivorian Truth Commission.

4.2 Research design

The effectiveness of any investigation relies on a coherent and well-defined logical framework, often referred to as the "logical plan" (De Vaus, 2005, p. 9; Yin, 2011, p. 75). For the findings of a study to adequately address the research questions, Yin emphasizes that this logic encompasses the relationships among the research questions, the data to be gathered, and the strategies for data analysis (Yin, 2011, p. 76). This indicates that researchers must have a clear understanding of their research questions from the outset and ensure that these questions are aligned with the logical framework, thereby validating the research outcomes. The research question serves as a critical foundation for the research design, as De Vaus (2005, p. 9) notes that the purpose of a research plan is to guarantee that the evidence collected can effectively respond to the initial research questions with clarity.

To achieve this, researchers should consider the following inquiry: "In light of this theory or research question, what type of evidence is necessary to rigorously test the theory or provide a clear and persuasive answer to the question?" (De Vaus, 2005, p. 9). While the social sciences encompass various inquiry paradigms, the predominant ones are quantitative and qualitative, also referred to as positivist and interpretive, respectively. Guba and Lincoln (1994) further categorize these paradigms into four distinct types: positivism, post-positivism, critical theory, and constructivism. Kuhn, in his seminal work *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962), challenged the notion that scientific progress is merely the accumulation of truths, proposing instead that scientific advancement occurs through paradigm shifts that foster new perspectives and enhance knowledge development.

Kuhn's thesis thus proposed the necessity of a paradigm shift. He contends that a paradigm encompasses a collection of beliefs, procedures, and practices that guide and influence the progression of scientific inquiry (Kuhn, 1962). He ultimately asserts that "Paradigms provide scientists not only with a map, but also some of the essential directions for mapping. By using a paradigm, the researcher has 'acquired theory, methods, and standards together, usually in an extractable mixture'" (Kuhn, 1971, p. 109). In their exploration of paradigms within the social sciences, Guba and Lincoln

(1994) characterize a paradigm as "a set of fundamental (or metaphysical) beliefs that deal with ultimate or first principles" (1994: 107). This paradigm delineates "what is important, what is legitimate, what is reasonable" (Sarantakos, 1993, p. 30) regarding the current research. The responses to epistemological, ontological, and methodological inquiries are crucial for establishing researchers' paradigmatic inclinations. The positivist tradition, initiated by Auguste Comte, aimed to emulate the methodologies of the natural sciences, positing that an understanding of the social realm should be rooted in pragmatism, with social laws derived from natural phenomena. Conversely, Kantian philosophy emphasizes the necessity of interpreting human experiences to derive meaning, rather than solely relying on natural observation. This perspective has evolved into what is now recognized as the qualitative tradition. Selecting an appropriate research method is a nuanced task, as the chosen method must align with the research objectives, as noted by Devine:

"Qualitative and quantitative methods involve collecting data in different ways, and the crucial question is whether the choice of method is appropriate for the theoretical and empirical questions that I seek to address"

(Devine, 2002, p202)

All research endeavours, regardless of their methodological differences, ultimately seek to explore the social realities and various traditions of the world. Halfpenny (1979) delineated the distinctions between qualitative and quantitative research methods. He characterizes qualitative methods as soft, flexible, subjective, political, case" studies that are speculative and grounded, whereas quantitative methods are portrayed as hard, fixed, objective, value-free, involving surveys, hypothesis testing, and abstract analysis.

The research design framework depicted in Figure 1, below, is integral to this thesis, providing a structured approach that guides both the research process and the analysis that follows. This framework embodies a thorough and systematic methodology that aligns with the primary research objectives.

This framework outlines the methodologies and approaches utilised in the research, accompanied by a figure 1 that visually represents its structure. The first section, *Evaluation Framework Design and Testing*, as detailed in Chapter 5, establishes the

framework's overarching purpose and systematically evaluates the effectiveness of the Ivorian Truth Commission by defining the evaluation criteria. Following this, the component on "Primary & Secondary Qualitative Research," also found in Chapter 5, describes the qualitative methodologies employed, including in-depth interviews and document analysis, which provide essential data for assessing the Commission's effectiveness. The participant categories, encompassing the Governance Regime, the Commissioners, and Civil Society, are discussed in Chapter 5, outlining the selection process for these participants. Additionally, the analysis of various legal and official documents, such as government reports and NGO assessments, is covered, linking back to both qualitative research and governance aspects, thereby offering a legal context for evaluating the Commission. Finally, Chapter 6 presents a synthesis of the insights gleaned from these components, illustrating how the qualitative data, governance analysis, and legal documents collectively contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the Ivorian Truth Commission's effectiveness and impact.

By following the framework illustrated in Figure 1 below, the thesis is crafted to ensure that every phase of the research process is purposefully aligned with the primary aim: to investigate and comprehend the intricate factors that affect the assessment of the Ivorian truth commission within the framework of restorative justice. This structure not only offers a clear and logical pathway for the research but also accommodates flexibility to address unforeseen obstacles and incorporate new findings. As a result, it functions as a versatile instrument for organizing and interpreting data throughout the research endeavour.

In conclusion, Figure 1 serves as a crucial reference point, steering the reader through the complexities of the research design while highlighting the interrelatedness of each phase and its role in fulfilling the objectives of the thesis.

Figure 1: Research Design [Author]

4.3 Criteria for evaluating the truth commission.

In the following chapter, seven criteria are proposed to evaluate the impact of the truth commission through restorative justice. The selected criteria follow three stages of the Commission's process, before its creation, during the term of its mandate and to act on the recommendations of the final report. Indeed, the creation of the CDVR was not the subject of a consensus between the stakeholders of the 2011 post-electoral crisis in Côte d'Ivoire but was established solely from the will of the power in place. Has it achieved its objective of seeking the truth and ensuring the reconciliation of the stakeholders in the crisis? Have all the victims been identified and considered? Can we ensure after this mandate of the CDVR, that resentments are dissipated from the hearts of the victims and that Côte d'Ivoire is safe from any resurgence of conflict? These are all questions that lead me to the following development.

4.3.1 Restoring social ties and reconciliation: before the Commission

In the previous section, criteria for organising the relational and conciliatory orientation of restorative justice are outlined. To examine the remedial and conciliating potentialities of the design and practices of the CDVR before its establishment, an evaluation criteria (*CR-1*) *CDVR as a Negotiated Institution* is proposed. The criterion consists of knowing whether all parties have been involved in setting up the commission by checking whether the mandate and appointments are negotiated by all

stakeholders. Togo presents an example of the establishment of a truth and reconciliation commission which saw the participation of all parties. Indeed, the Truth, Justice and Reconciliation Commission of Togo was set up by presidential decree on February 25, 2009, following national consultations conducted from April to July 2008, by the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights. 'Male, at the invitation of the Togolese Government (Barrigah, 2013). As a reminder, according to Bishop Nicodème Barrigah, the post-electoral crisis of 2005 in Togo ended in more than five hundred deaths. Following this crisis, national dialogue sessions were organized by a representative party of the protagonists of the crisis which led to the signing of the Comprehensive Political Agreement (GPA) of August 20, 2006, (Ahadzi-Nonou, 2014). Ahadzi-Nonou adds that in points 2.2 and 2.4, this agreement recommends the creation of a commission responsible for shedding light on acts of political violence committed in the past and studying the modalities of appeasement of victims, as well as the establishment of a commission which will propose measures likely to promote pardon and national reconciliation. Following broad national popular consultations conducted under the leadership of the local office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR), from April to July 2008, at the request of the Togolese government, it was decided to create a truth and reconciliation commission. It is within this framework that the Head of State adopted, in the Council of Ministers, on February 25, 2009, Decree No. 2009-0461 / PR establishing the Truth, Justice and Reconciliation commission. It was the national consultations that therefore defined the criteria used to establish this commission. Regarding the first criteria (CR-1) relating to *CDVR* as a Negotiated Institution, the composition of the CVJR was guided by popular consultations which excluded certain socio-professional categories from the commission, such as the army, lawyers. and political parties. More limited consultations were conducted by the Prime Minister with civil society organisations, academics, researchers, and the traditional chieftdom. Names of high personalities were proposed at the level of each organisation. It is following all these steps that, by decree n ° 2009-147 / PR of May 27, 2009, the composition of the Togolese CVJR was determined of eleven members, including two religious' leaders, four academics, including one representative of the Order of Physicians, three members of civil society defenders of human rights, a traditional chief and a former minister considered as a privileged witness of the political evolution of Togo since the colonial period (Ahadzi-Nonou, K., 2014).

Regarding the mandate of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission, the example of Timor-Leste is instructive. In Timor-Leste, a committee has been set up with representatives of national organisations such as human rights groups, groups representing women and youth, religious groups, representatives of the National Congress for the reconstruction of Timor-Leste, the Commission for Justice and Peace of the Catholic Church and several other national associations. International organisations such as the United Nations Transitional Administration in East Timor and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees served on the committee. This committee conducted community consultations to better understand the attitude of the populations regarding reconciliation. The results broadened the mandate of the Commission to include a process of reconciliation using traditional community practices, as well as the need for the Commission to examine the imposed widespread famine (OHCHR, 2009, p. 6). Legislation is another way to promote the involvement of all parties in the process of establishing a commission. The participation of all parties in the drafting of laws can facilitate, for example, compliance with international standards and best practices. Parties including civil society, political parties and public can commit to working with government to draft legislation or prepare a draft and submit it to government for review. For example, in Kenya, the Multisectoral Working Group on the Truth, Justice and Reconciliation Commission, a coalition of civil society organisations and the Kenya National Human Rights Commission, worked with the government to draft the legislation, while in Sierra Leone the NGOs, Truth and Reconciliation Working Group drafted a bill and presented it to the government (Brankovic, 2010). In South Africa, the need for new legislation to establish the Truth and Reconciliation Commission has encouraged the participation of civil society, NGOs, and the public in the process of drafting this legislation. As a result,

"a wide range of political and civil society organisations were involved in the discussions leading up to the final draft which was approved for presentation to parliament"

(Van der Merwe, Dewhirst, and Hamber, 1999, p. 57).

When the final draft was published, some NGOs did not approve the legislation and proposed amendments including limiting amnesties to as few cases as possible, providing victim-offender mediation, strengthening the role of victims in the

commission process, etc. (Van der Merwe, Dewhirst, and Hamber, 1999, p. 59). These amendments were accepted by South African Justice Minister Dullah Omar and included in the final draft (Van der Merwe, Dewhirst, and Hamber, 1999, p. 59).

These examples show that the regimes in power have involved the various parties in the establishment of their Truth and Reconciliation Commissions. The criteria also show that commission mandates and commissioner appointments have been negotiated by all parties.

4.3.2 Restoring social ties and reconciliation: during the mandate

To examine the restorative and conciliatory potentialities of the design and practices of CDVR during its mandate, I developed three evaluation criteria (CR-2) CDVR as an Inclusive Process, (CR-3) Focused on the victim and Empowerment in the CDVR's Context and (CR-4) CDVR and Truth-Telling. During the period of the establishment of truth and reconciliation commissions and the submission of final reports, truth and reconciliation commissions carry out mandates entrusted to them such as investigating and tracing victims. To do this, commissions collect information and evidence from victims, witnesses, the public and public agencies. For the commission to be seen as restorative and conciliatory during its tenure, first and foremost, victims, offenders, witnesses, the public and NGOs must participate and engage in the commission process (CR-2). This requires that the commissions create the conditions to meet with victims, offenders, witnesses, the public and NGOs and that they be willing to meet with the commissions. In Canada, the work of the truth and reconciliation commission began in 2009 and public hearings in 2010. From 2010 to 2014, seven national events, community activities, commemoration ceremonies, sharing circles and hearings (public and private) took place in large cities in Canada (Roussel, 2015). Among the activities included, the hearings included public testimonies, private depositions, speaking circles where Aboriginal people spoke before institutional representatives reacted in turn as well as the possibility for representatives of churches, government institutions. or other groups to present public expressions of reconciliation (Roussel, 2015). Regarding the criteria (CR-3) Centred on the victim and (CR-4) CDVR and Truth-Telling, according to Roussel (2015), all those who participated in one or more activities of Canada's Truth and Reconciliation Commission were able to measure the intensity of what was taking place there, in an

atmosphere of great dignity: moving testimonies, silent and respectful listening on the part of the ecclesial representatives, tears and anger, expressions of dignity and love of his own. Approximately 6,750 testimonies from survivors were heard, especially former residents or members of their families (Roussel, 2015). A form posted on the Canadian Commission website gave survivors the opportunity to record their testimony. Individual interviews were conducted with former employees (or their children) of residential schools. According to the Canadian Commission, 155,000 people attended the national events, which were joined by 9,000 registered residential school survivors (Jaccoud, 2016).

Latin American truth and reconciliation commissions are good examples that illustrate criteria (CR-3) and (CR-4). In Latin America, the commissions gathered information from victims and human rights organisations or religious groups working closely with victims. Argentina's Truth and Reconciliation Commission, for example, compiled 7,000 statements registering 8,960 (missing) victims. According to Hayner (2010), most of the country's human rights organisations contributed to the investigation by providing information on missing persons (Hayner, 2010). El Salvador's Truth Commission had the assistance of victims and national and international human rights groups to report on human rights violations. The Commission registered over 22,000 complaints of acts of violence that occurred during the period January 1980 and July 1991. 7,000 acts of violence were reported by victims themselves and by witnesses at the offices of the Commission. The other acts of violence were received through governmental and non-governmental organisations (Truth Commission for El Salvador, 1993). In Chile, the Commission collected testimonies from families of missing or killed persons based on numerous files from non-governmental and religious organisations (Crocker, 1998). The South African Truth and Reconciliation Commission makes explicit reference to restorative justice in its report. The commission clarifies the meaning of this concept which it makes an essential principle to restore the dignity of victims. According to the South African commission, restorative justice redefines crime by focusing on the harm done rather than the offense committed against laws (whether domestic or international) or against a state. The commission is centred on reparation and aims at the healing of victims, perpetrators, their families, and the community, which it encourages to get directly involved in the resolution of the conflict, with the help of legal experts and law enforcement officers.

the state (Truth and Reconciliation Commission, 1998, vol. 1, Ch. 5, para. 82). To do this, the commission relies on the accounts of the victims, but also on those of the aggressors to know and perhaps, to understand the reasons for their acts, to draw the most complete possible portrait of what is happening. Indeed, many of those who heard the accounts of the victims encountered, for the first time, the human face of the silent or unknown victims of past conflicts (TRC, 1998, vol. 1, Ch. 5, paragraph 90).

Rwanda is also a good example of criteria (CR-2), (CR-3) and (CR-4). The post-genocide gacaca is based on the massive participation of the population in the search for and the achievement of justice (Dumas, 2014). Their decentralisation makes them very accessible and promotes the participation of all actors: (i) the survivors (mainly Tutsi and Hutus), (ii) the Tutsi refugees who return after several years or generations, (iii) the accused who if they are absent from their village, will be transported to stand trial, (iv) the freed persons having already confessed their crimes in prison and who can denounce other people, suspected and unsuspected Hutus. The victims, the attackers and the local community gathered almost at the scene of the massacres. The meetings take place not far from people's homes, in their local language, with simple procedures and at the beginning without too much delay in the judgments (Mabiala, 2009) and give voice to the victims. For Rwandans, these characteristics make gacaca a more legitimate "court" than the criminal court (Ingelaere, 2008; Apuuli, 2009; Clark, 2009; Mabiala, 2009; May 2010). Their decentralisation would also have helped reconciliation by recreating a link between the community and the perpetrators (May, 2010). For all these reasons, they constitute a unique form of post-conflict or transitional justice (Clark, 2009; Dumas, 2014, p.263).

This section has shown that all conflict actors including the public, governmental and non-governmental organisations have been involved in the discussions of truth commissions. The criteria also showed that the commissions approached victims, offenders, the public, governmental and non-governmental organisations to collect information on conflicts and victims.

4.3.3 Restoring social ties: following the final report

To examine the restorative and conciliatory potential of the design and practices of the CDVR after its mandate, three evaluation criteria are proposed: (CR-5) Recognition of migrants' identities and overcoming the denial of injustice, (CR-6), Restore the dignity and dignity of survivors. Self-respect and (CR-7) Flexibility of reparation programs. To verify these criteria, the researcher first uses the final report of the commission and then examines the perceptions of victims, survivors, the public and national and international organizations. In Rwanda, by shedding light on the conditions in which many crimes were committed, the gacaca nevertheless contributed to the recognition of the suffering of the victims in addition to providing answers to survivors who had remained without news of their relatives. (Rosoux, 2009). They also provided an opportunity for offenders to recognise their responsibility and their wrongs in the genocide (Rondeau, 2016). However, many Rwandans insist on the difference between, on one hand, going to court, confessing their crimes, receiving a reduction of sentence, and being released from prison and, on the other hand, recognising moral responsibility, committed crimes, and expressing remorse (Burnet, 2010).

South Africa's Truth and Reconciliation Commission is a very good example that covers all the criteria in this section. Indeed, the law on the South African truth and reconciliation commission has set up three sub-committees: The Human Rights Committee (HRC), responsible for listing and investigating human rights violations; the Amnesty Committee, responsible for granting amnesty and the Reparation and Rehabilitation Committee (RRC), responsible for making recommendations and developing measures to be taken to provide reparations to victims of gross human rights violations. For 18 months, the Reparation and Rehabilitation Committee collected information from victims, survivors, representatives of NGOs and governmental and non-governmental organisations and academic institutions through testimonies and consultative workshops. These consultative workshops held across the country aimed to "a) assess the harm suffered; b) estimate the needs and expectations of victims; (c) establish criteria to identify victims with urgent needs; and d) develop proposals for long-term reparations and rehabilitation measures" (Colvin, 2003, p.16). In determining the criteria for awarding reparations, the Reparation and Rehabilitation Committee (RRC) relied on the final report and findings of the human rights and amnesty committees. The RRC devoted considerable time to formulating

its recommendations and established principles as the foundations of its recommendations such as development priority, cultural opportunity, community as a basis, promotion of healing and reconciliation (Buford and van der Merwe, 2004). To apply these principles, the Reparation and Rehabilitation Committee recommended flexibility in the reparation's programmes including emergency provisions for reparations, community rehabilitation programmes, symbolic reparations, institutional reform, individual reparation allowance (Buford and Van der Merwe, 2004). Emergency provisions for reparation consisted of coming to the aid of people in urgent need, guaranteeing them access to appropriate services and facilities. Emergency provisions for reparation could include medical, emotional, educational, material, and symbolic needs. Community rehabilitation programmes promoted healing and healing of communities, and these remedial measures included national demilitarisation, relocation of displaced persons, rehabilitation of perpetrators and their families, establishment of psychological support services and training centres. Symbolic reparations consisted of restoring the dignity of victims and survivors of gross human rights violations and these measures included the issuance of death certificates, exhumations, the celebration of new burials and ceremonies, removal of criminal records, renaming of streets and celebration of ceremonies. Institutional reform aimed to adopt administrative, legal, and institutional measures aimed at ensuring the non-recurrence of human rights violations. The individual reparation allowance consisted of financial compensation which was based on three components: an amount to recognise suffering, an amount to allow access to services and facilities; and an amount to meet the daily expenses according to the current economic situation of the person requesting compensation (Buford and Van der Merwe, 2004).

This section showed that truth commissions issued final reports and made recommendations. The recommendations included flexibility of programmes including symbolic reparations.

4.4 Researcher positionality and its impact on the thesis

Researcher positionality refers to the necessity of acknowledging how a researcher's identity, background, beliefs, and experiences shape the research process. This concept encompasses various factors such as gender, race, socio-economic status, education, and professional experiences. In qualitative research (where the

researcher is directly involved in data collection and interpretation) positionality is of paramount importance. Ignoring it can lead to biased findings; conversely, recognising and addressing it fosters transparency, reflexivity, and ethical rigor (Sparkes & Smith, 2008; Creswell & Poth, 2018).

Influence on research topic selection

Researcher positionality significantly influences the selection of research topics, methodologies, participant engagement, and data interpretation (Holmes, 2020). Scholars often gravitate towards subjects that reflect their own experiences and values. For instance, my background in Côte d'Ivoire has deeply shaped my understanding of the historical and ongoing political conflicts in the country. This personal narrative adds authenticity and depth to the research; however, it necessitates a reflexive approach to ensure that my biases do not eclipse alternative viewpoints (Morrow, 2005).

In my study, I chose to conduct in-depth interviews rather than rely on surveys, emphasizing the importance of personal narratives that provide contextual depth. My growing knowledge of the literature surrounding transitional justice, particularly regarding the complexities of victimhood and reconciliation processes, informed my exploration of specific themes. Additionally, my personal experiences and interest in these issues motivated me to delve deeper into how individuals navigate their narratives within the broader context of transitional justice. While this focus enriches the research, it is crucial to maintain a balance by elevating the participants' voices to prevent my interpretations from dominating their stories. To mitigate potential bias, I incorporated diverse data sources, such as interviews and archival research, which facilitated a more comprehensive understanding and diminished reliance on my personal assumptions (Flick, 2018; Hesse-Biber, 2010).

Impact on research interaction

Engaging with the community being researched can enhance trust and lead to more profound insights; however, it may also result in biases, as the researcher might unconsciously assume certain cultural norms (Dwyer & Buckle, 2009).

As an Ivorian, my shared cultural heritage helped establish rapport with many participants, facilitating open and honest dialogue. However, I recognized that

individual experiences and perspectives varied significantly based on factors such as regional backgrounds, socio-economic status, and personal histories relating to the conflict. This diversity meant that while my cultural background fostered some initial connections, it was crucial to approach each participant's narrative with sensitivity and an awareness of their unique circumstances. Despite this advantage, I remained aware of the potential biases that could stem from my close connection to the community, such as the risk of participants feeling pressured to provide responses that aligned with my expectations or cultural norms. For instance, some individuals might have been hesitant to share critical views about the CDVR or other local entities, fearing that doing so might disrupt the sense of solidarity within the community or reflect poorly on their personal affiliations. To mitigate this issue, I crafted a positionality statement to ensure transparency about my background and utilized culturally sensitive engagement techniques to cultivate trust with the participants.

Challenges in data interpretation

Data interpretation presents significant challenges, as two researchers examining the same dataset may arrive at divergent conclusions influenced by their individual backgrounds (Peshkin, 1988). My identity as an Ivorian has led me to focus on themes of institutional inequalities, which may have caused me to overlook other vital issues, such as human rights abuses. This situation highlights the importance of recognizing how personal viewpoints can shape research interpretations (Mason, 2002).

To bolster credibility and mitigate biases, I adopted a reflexive approach, critically examining how my identity and preconceptions affect the research process (Finlay, 2002). I included a positionality statement to elucidate my background and the potential biases that may inform my interpretations. As noted by England (1994), such statements enhance transparency by explicitly acknowledging biases. While my experiences offer valuable insights into the political crises in Côte d'Ivoire, it was essential to actively seek and incorporate alternative viewpoints to ensure a well-rounded analysis.

To support reflexivity, I kept a reflexive journal throughout the research process, which recorded biases, assumptions, and emotional reactions related to the study. This practice, emphasized by Finlay (2002) as a crucial element of qualitative reflexivity,

allowed for deeper self-examination. Additionally, I engaged with colleagues from various political and professional backgrounds, which enriched my analyses and helped to counteract subjective biases.

Methodological triangulation

In accordance with the indigenous-centred approaches advocated by Smith (2012), I employed a variety of research methods to enhance the validity of my findings and reduce reliance on a singular viewpoint. I integrated interviews with archival research within the context of transitional justice, thereby deepening the comprehension of the relevant issues. Denzin's (1978) notion of triangulation highlights the importance of utilizing multiple data sources to strengthen the credibility and reliability of research outcomes.

Researcher positionality plays a crucial role in influencing every stage of the research process, encompassing everything from the selection of topics to the interpretation of data. By engaging in reflexivity using positionality statements, maintaining a research journal, collaborating with a diverse range of colleagues, and employing methodological triangulation, I sought to reduce biases and improve the overall integrity of my research. Instead of perceiving positionality as a constraint, researchers should recognize it as a valuable opportunity to conduct more profound, ethical, and transparent inquiries. Acknowledging the complex relationship between identity and research practices can result in more significant contributions to qualitative scholarship. This approach not only enhances the depth of analysis but also cultivates an atmosphere of trust and ethical responsibility within the research process.

4.5 Ethical approval

Research ethics encompasses the moral principles and values that direct researchers' activities, ensuring participant safety and the confidentiality of personal information gathered during studies. Violations of ethical standards in academia can result in significant repercussions, such as damage to reputation, erosion of trust, and possible legal ramifications (Resnik, 2018). Therefore, it is essential to uphold ethical guidelines to safeguard the rights of research participants, especially in sensitive situations. The remainder of this section reviews the key ethical principles guiding research, explores

common ethical dilemmas faced by researchers, and discusses the importance of informed consent and confidentiality in maintaining ethical standards.

Ethical considerations in the context of Côte d'Ivoire

Jones (2000) highlights the necessity for researchers to reflect on the ethical ramifications of their methodologies and the values they embody. In the analysis of conflicts in Côte d'Ivoire, the notion of "Ivoirité" stands out as a critical and delicate topic. Initially aimed at enhancing national sovereignty and cultural identity, "Ivoirité" has transformed into a divisive concept that has fueled xenophobic rhetoric and violence against those deemed non-Ivorian, particularly individuals with Malinke surnames (Vidal & Le Pape, 2003; Ake, 2018; Kone, 2019). Scholars contend that this exclusivist ideology has intensified societal rifts and played a role in the violence that has plagued the nation's political environment, particularly during the civil conflicts of the early 2000s and the post-election crisis of 2010-2011 (Gervais & Raveaud, 2018; Onguéné, 2020). This reality necessitates sensitivity from researchers in addressing issues related to identity politics, ethnic tensions, and the potential for violence, ensuring that their work contributes to understanding rather than exacerbating existing societal divisions. Comprehending the implications of "Ivoirité" is essential for analysing the socio-political dynamics of Côte d'Ivoire while upholding ethical principles that prioritize the safety and confidentiality of participants.

Adherence to ethical protocols

The study rigorously followed all ethical protocols necessary for research involving human subjects. It received approval from the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland on May 3, 2021. This approval was instrumental in ensuring that the research was conducted in a responsible and ethical manner, avoiding harm to participants or the wider community. I committed to maintaining accuracy and honesty throughout the research, striving for fairness and respect for all individuals involved.

Ethical implications and participant protection

The ethical dimensions of my research focus on the importance of conducting studies with responsibility and integrity, particularly emphasizing the safeguarding of participants' confidentiality. In Côte d'Ivoire, numerous respondents voiced concerns about the risk of being identified, fearing potential repercussions such as arrest, imprisonment by authorities, violence from rebel factions, or threats to their families (Mäkelä, 2015; Hamber, 2018). To address these concerns, interviews were conducted discreetly, particularly concerning how participants were approached and the locations where interviews were held. Ensuring confidentiality and safety was paramount, which involved carefully selecting interview sites that felt secure and private to the participants, such as community centers or trusted local spaces. Participants were approached with sensitivity, emphasizing the voluntary nature of their involvement and the importance of their narratives. This approach aimed to foster a trusting environment, allowing participants to share their experiences openly, without fear of retribution or judgment.

The importance of informed consent

To secure informed consent from participants, I provided them with a comprehensive information sheet outlining the research objectives, potential benefits, the nature of their participation, associated risks, legal rights, and assurances of confidentiality (a copy of this information sheet can be found in the appendices). It is essential to ensure that participants fully understand and voluntarily agree to take part, as this is a cornerstone of ethical research practices in sensitive contexts (Flicker & Lunt, 2010).

Participant selection and anonymity

Participants were chosen based on their academic or professional qualifications, relevant experiences, and their connection to the research topic, employing purposive sampling methods. Potential interviewees were identified through academic networks, professional organizations, and community groups related to the subject matter. Once identified, I approached them via email or personal communication, explaining the research objectives and inviting them to participate in the study. This approach was designed to guarantee that the participants possessed adequate knowledge and relevance to the research objectives, thereby bolstering the study's validity (Ritchie et

al., 2013). In accordance with the ethics application, pseudonyms were assigned to all participants after the interviews to safeguard their identities, a practice that aligns with ethical standards in qualitative research (Liamputtong, 2007; Guillemin & Gillam, 2004). Additionally, ensuring confidentiality not only protects the identities of participants but also cultivates trust and promotes open communication, which is vital in sensitive research environments (McLaughlin & Braun, 2019). Given the potential vulnerabilities of specific groups in conflict situations, meticulous attention to ethical considerations is crucial for maintaining the integrity of the research process.

In summary, establishing a foundation of robust ethical practices in research serves to safeguard participants and simultaneously bolsters the credibility and integrity of the research endeavour. By addressing the ethical challenges associated with sensitive subjects like "Ivoirité" and committing to strict compliance with ethical guidelines, this study seeks to provide valuable insights while prioritizing the rights and well-being of all parties involved.

4.6 Purposive sampling

Purposive sampling also known as judgment, selective or subjective sampling was applied as part of this research process. Purposive sampling is a sampling technique in which the researcher relies on his or her own judgment to choose participants and interviewees for the study (Campbell and al., 2020). It is a non-probability sampling method. The reason for choosing this type of sampling is the better adequacy of the sample to the research objectives, thus improving the rigor of the study and the reliability of the data and results.

As part of this study, a Purposive sampling of 35 participants was carried out. The sampling targeted, leaders of political parties, government officials, former CDVR staff, CONARIV commissioners, members of victims' associations, victims of injustice, parliamentarians, academics, media staff, religious authorities and civil society organisations who have a solid knowledge of the Ivorian conflicts and of the process of the Truth and Reconciliation Commissions. Victims of injustices were contacted through non-governmental organisations such as the Collective of Victims in Côte d'Ivoire (CVCI) which work in the regions as well as through existing government networks such as CONARIV and PNCS. Officials were contacted by an official letter addressed to the first person in charge of each organisation to be interviewed.

4.7 Snowball sampling

Snowball sampling was also applied as part of the research process. Also known as chain-referral sampling, Snowball sampling is a non-probability sampling method used when characteristics to be possessed by samples are rare and difficult to find (Dane, 2011). This technique involves obtaining suggestions for other participants from those the researcher has already observed.

Indeed, during this research process, it happened that during the conversations with the first interviewees, there was a need to interview certain participants who were not planned in the schedule. In addition, certain participants scheduled in the calendar, such as certain officials were not available or did not respond to the letters. According to Biernacki and Waldorf (1981), the sensitivities surrounding the research topic necessitated referrals from individuals who knew possible interviewees who would have been important to the research (1981, p. 141). This sampling method can be advantageous to reach populations such as "the elite" (Atkinson and Flint, 2004, p. 2) most of whom would initially be uncomfortable opening to someone they do not know about a sensitive subject. Given the insecure situation in Côte d'Ivoire and the nature of the subject, some political or administrative elites refused to discuss this sensitive subject of reconciliation. According to Noy (2008), from the point of view of this contribution "they are not excluded by hegemonic forces, but being part of hegemony, exclude themselves" from discussing this subject in public (Noy, 2008, p. 331).

4.8 Primary data sources

Primary data for this thesis were interviews as a method of research and investigation. The main justification for this method was scope for generating information which could not be found using a documentary approach alone, as well as seeking a range of different positional perspectives, behaviours, experiences, thoughts, feelings, and attitudes. Interview questions are prepared before it is set up. Interviews therefore took place with some elite agents, political leaders, representatives of national and international NGOs, academics, victims of injustices, opinion leaders from civil society, as well as officials of victims' organisations. Plesner (2011) points out that the idea of "elite" interviewing is a relative term, depending on context. One characteristic of these groups is that access can be a challenge (Desmond, 2004). In this study, elite interviewing is relevant as some interviewees have worked in important political roles,

including holders of ministerial posts, presidents of the political parties and representatives of national or international organisations. The elites interviewed were privileged witnesses, either because their professional occupation allows them to have knowledge of the activities of CDVR and CONARIV or of the reconciliation process (Harvey, 2011; Lilleker, 2003), or because they themselves carried out previous research on the same theme or on similar topics (Zuckerman, 1972).

This primary data collection consists of in-depth qualitative research interviews. Following Kvale and Brinkmann's work, there are predominantly open questions, which are followed up as needed during the interview, requiring a flexibility (2009) which improves with practice. I engaged at this stage, with the participant to gather his points of view and his interpretations of certain phenomena relevant to the research questions. Notably, this also means that the qualitative interview data may be ambiguous and, as we are dealing with subjective perceptions, can even be contradictory in places (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009). The interviews are, however, able to provide us with exploratory data on relatively new phenomena that have not yet been the subject of much research (Wilkinson 2009). This thesis aims to carry out an evaluation of CDVR, and this evaluation can be considered as an exploratory study. Qualitative research interviews are mostly conversation-related and are interactive in nature. Therefore, a knowledge of the subject of the interview is necessary to discover the subjective perspectives of the participants on the conception of CDVR. The interview questions are therefore developed based on a review of the existing literature on truth commissions, restorative justice, recognition theory and Ivorian conflicts.

Data collection tools interviews and the interview guide

Semi-structured interviews were the primary data collection tool for this part of the investigation, using an interview guide developed by drawing on knowledge from the literature review and conceptual framework in the thesis.

In Corbetta's views the qualitative interview ought to be a conversation that has the following characteristics:

- 1) It is elicited by the interviewer.
- 2) Interviewees are selected by a data-gathering plan.

- 3) A considerable number of subjects are interviewed.
- 4) It is guided by the interviewer.
- 5) It is based on a flexible, non-standardised pattern of questioning

(Corbetta, 2003, p. 264).

In this case, a purposive sample was used for the data gathering plan. Interviewees were selected based on this in numbers that would fulfil the requirements of the research questions. Flexibility of questioning allowed careful attention to be paid to the worldview of the interviewees, paying attention to their language, what they said and how they said it (Legard, Keegan and Ward, 2003; Patton, 1990).

I made interview notes during the conversations, including preliminary reflections on what interviewees were saying and areas to learn more about both during and afterwards.

4.9 The sample

Pires sees the sample as designating a small quantity of something to illuminate certain general aspects of the problem (1997, p. 122). In other words, the idea of the sample is closely linked to the idea of the transferability of the knowledge that will be produced by the research. The issue of the sample, then, turns out to be of strategic and central importance because the type of sample chosen will guide, colour, and frame the process of interpreting the results of the research, both in terms of explanatory power and in wealth and credibility. In this study, I chose a reduced number of cases according to criteria I have defined. According to Corbetta, sampling offers advantages relating to the cost of data collection, the time required for data collection and processing, the organisation, and the resulting expense, and allows for depth and precision (2003, p. 211). As previously indicated, the sample for this study was composed of political party leaders, government officials, former CDVR staff, CONARIV commissioners, members of victims' associations, victims of injustices, parliamentarians, academics, media staff, religious authorities, and civil society organisations.

The characteristics of the sample can be found in Table 2 below. Interview participants were selected based on their expertise in the four main areas of this research:

- transitional justice.
- restorative justice.
- CDVR and
- the history of Ivorian conflicts.

Table 2: Characteristics of the Sample

N•	ORGANISATIONS	N=	CITED IN THESIS AS
	Governance regime	7	
1	Current and formers Ministers of government	2	Governance, GM
2	Current and formers Members of parliament	3	Governance, PM
3	Officers of the army and the police	2	Governance, OP
	Formers commissioners	8	
4	CDVR	3	Commissioner, CD
5	CONARIV	3	Commissioner, CO
6	PNCS	2	Commissioner, PN
	Civil society	20	
7	Political parties & leaders	6	Civil society, PP
8	Human right defenders	4	Civil society, HR
9	Students	2	Civil society, ST
10	Victims' representative	1	Civil society, VR
11	Doctors with expertise	2	Civil society, DR
12	Jurists	2	Civil society, JU
13	Media	3	Civil society, ME
	TOTAL	35	

Source: Author

Based on this, interviews can provide relevant data on subjective experiences and opinions regarding restorative practices and recognition of CDVR. This can produce data capable of evaluating the success or failure of the organisation. Interviews were conducted in person or, failing that, by telephone if possible. Face-to-face interviews are the preferred method of interviewing as they allow a certain relationship to be established with the participants. Telephone interview mode was considered if

participants are unavailable. For in-person interviews, I used a voice recorder to record participants' responses. On the other hand, during telephone interviews, I took notes to record the interview data. The interviewees were identified since their academic or professional backgrounds, their experience and their proximity or interest in the research theme. Either way, it was essential that only these defined criteria were considered when selecting who participated in the research.

Assumptions and types of the study sample

Purposive sampling and snowball sampling were the two sampling techniques used in this study. The reasoned sample is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the purpose of the study and known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling (May 1997). Snowball sampling also refers to a non-probability sampling technique in which I began with a small population of known individuals and expands the sample by asking the first participants to identify others who should participate in the sample study. This technique is used in this study because I wished to work with a population that may be difficult to identify or locate given the security situation in Côte d'Ivoire. The sampling used in this study was based on the following key assumptions: 1) That the sampling is representative and competent to answer the research question; 2) That the data cover all aspects of the Truth and Reconciliation Commissions process; 3) That sampling leads to saturation and replication and that it represents both sexes as well as young and old to give a balanced analysis of the results; 4) That the sample provide a basis for triangulation regarding regions, gender, categories and injustices committed; 5) That the sample include a variety, for example, composed of leaders of political parties, government officials, former CDVR staff, members of victims' associations, victims of injustices, parliamentarians, academics, media staff, religious authorities and civil society organisations, etc. so that the data obtained are representative of the variety.

4.10 Data collection and analysis methods

The study employed semi-structured interviews to collect in-depth insights from various stakeholders, including victims, ex-combatants, policymakers, and civil society representatives. This qualitative approach provided a nuanced understanding of the perceived effectiveness and limitations of the CDVR in promoting restorative justice in Côte d'Ivoire. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data, the interview process

followed a structured methodology, including verbatim transcription and a coding process, as well as the use of an organized grid. All interviews were transcribed word-for-word to preserve the authenticity of respondents' statements, ensuring that no nuances or contextual meanings were lost.

Thematic analysis and organisation

Initial themes were identified through a close reading of transcripts, allowing key issues to emerge naturally from the data. These themes were then categorized under broader concepts of restorative justice, aligning with the theoretical framework of truth and reconciliation processes. The grid facilitated systematic organization of themes, helping to identify patterns of convergence and divergence among different stakeholders. The analysis revealed five major themes: Perceptions of Justice, Effectiveness of Dialogue, Inclusivity and Representation, Trust in Institutions, and Reparations, which encapsulate the perspectives of interviewees regarding the CDVR's impact and shortcomings.

Data were collected and analysed by following the steps below:

- First, after reading the transcripts, I identified and classify the important information according to the two pre-established conditions: the three stages of the establishment and functioning of the commissions and the interactions between the actors within each stage. In the previous sections, I defined the three stages which: before the establishment of the commission, during its work and following the recommendations of the final report.
- Second, I created an organised grid with the same two pre-established conditions (the three steps and the specific interactions). I inserted all the data from each interview into this grid, noting who said what in a separate column.
- Finally, I divided this data according to the corresponding evaluation criteria. At this point, I began to evaluate the commissions. I examined the data collected using the evaluation criteria pre-established in the previous sections. By evaluating whether these criteria are met or not, I defined the existence of a restorative potential or not in the creation and operation of Ivorian commissions. Interviews with elite agents helped I to further refine the criteria for evaluating the commissions. The data collected during the interviews also supported the

documentary data. Therefore, I used the evidence gathered by the two techniques to assess whether the assessment criteria of the commissions are met to support the existence of restoration potential.

Methodological approach to triangulation

To enhance the reliability and validity of the findings, this study employed a triangulation approach, cross-referencing data from multiple sources and methodologies. This process ensured a more comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of the Commission for Dialogue, Truth, and Reconciliation (CDVR) and its impact on post-conflict justice and reconciliation in Côte d'Ivoire. By integrating various perspectives and data sources, the study aimed to create a robust framework for analysing the reconciliation process.

Cross-referencing data sources

One of the primary methods of triangulation was the comparison of data gathered from interviews with official documents and reports. The testimonies and perspectives of stakeholders were systematically compared with official CDVR reports, government communications, and publicly available statements from policymakers. This cross-verification helped determine whether the claims made by stakeholders aligned with or diverged from the officially recorded outcomes of the reconciliation process. The study also incorporated assessments from independent organizations, such as human rights groups and international bodies, to provide an unbiased view of the commission's achievements and shortcomings. Reports from institutions like the United Nations, Amnesty International, and local NGOs were used to verify whether the CDVR's actions matched its stated goals, helping to minimize biases that could arise from relying solely on personal accounts or government narratives.

Comparative case study for contextual understanding

To place Côte d'Ivoire's reconciliation process in a broader context, this study adopted a comparative case study approach. The effectiveness of the CDVR was assessed in relation to similar truth commissions in other post-conflict societies, particularly South Africa's Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) and Rwanda's Gacaca courts. These cases provided valuable insights into best practices and limitations in transitional justice. The study focused on critical indicators such as the level of victim participation, accountability for perpetrators, consultation, inclusiveness, the role of

political actors, and the long-term impact on national cohesion. By comparing these factors across different countries, it became possible to identify strengths and weaknesses in Côte d'Ivoire's approach and highlight areas for improvement.

Strengthening credibility and reliability of findings

Triangulation strengthened the credibility of this study by ensuring that conclusions were drawn from diverse and corroborated sources. The combination of official records, independent evaluations, and comparative case studies provided a more nuanced understanding of the successes and challenges of the CDVR. This methodological approach reinforced the study's reliability, making its findings more applicable to broader discussions on post-conflict reconciliation in Côte d'Ivoire and beyond. The triangulation process enabled a multi-dimensional analysis of the reconciliation framework, emphasizing the importance of incorporating various perspectives for effective transitional justice mechanisms.

4.11 Trust and interviewing

Distrust means that there is always reluctance to obtain information from an unknown person. Even if one person agrees to provide information, it does not mean that other people will. In general, behaviours differ from one individual to another towards an interviewer. Therefore, my first concern was to break this mistrust by establishing a form of trust between the interviewees, to get them to open, to speak, to remain neutral, natural and to avoid labelling us. Indeed, as Kaufmann (1996) argued, for one reason or another, research interviewees do not always tell the truth. There are different perspectives and points of manipulation and untruth in every research. It is therefore important to identify these and understand with them through specific investigation protocols. To make my results reliable, I worked to reduce these risks as much as possible. To get around this kind of obstacle, I first proceeded to an introduction and specify that the information collected was used for academic purposes only. If there is a need to make group or individual presentations, I did so. Then, I guaranteed the confidentiality of the information to interviewees. Identifying them by name was optional, and I clearly indicated this to the respondents from the first contact. I hoped that this process would encourage the consent of informants. This step is very important because it allows to obtain the cooperation of the

respondents, while reassuring them (Jones, 2000). An inappropriate or uncourteous attitude the interviewer's part may be perceived by informants as an interference with their privacy. To avoid this kind of interpretation, I took the necessary precautions to approach certain topics with great caution. Informed by the work of other social scientists, (Creswell, 1994; Marshall and Rossman, 2014) the values, rights, wants and needs of respondents must be protected and respected. If, even inadvertently, I have frustrated a respondent, this can be detrimental. If this frustration does not always push the subject concerned to refuse cooperation, it in any case pushes him to hesitant or suspicious communication with erroneous information. To prevent this frustration from harming the results of the study, a responsible procedure is to have audio recordings of the interviews, with prior authorisation from the source. If some respondents would not agree to have their words recorded, they may be contented with taking notes.

Painful truths and fidelity to the information gathered

I proceeded, immediately after the interviews, with the transcription to analyse and interpret the data. Because of the political situation and the fear of some interviewees, my ethical approval did not require their names in this study. I feared that this provision would make some respondents uncomfortable, to whom I have promised confidentiality. However, I appended the list of the personalities interviewed as well as the interview guides. All interviews were transcribed in French first, the language of the interviews, and then in English. This is a way for me to faithfully transcribe what the respondents say so as not to stray from their context during analysis and interpretation. Despite this duty of reserve and objectivity, I believed that it is impossible to conduct a study on reconciliation without engaging with this traumatic past. These testimonies may at times be shocking, but they would reflect the points of view of interviewees and sources.

4.12 Secondary data sources

To better understand the research theme, I also drew on a variety of secondary data sources. The first corpus concerns reports, legal texts and official documents related to research. I thus brought together the reports of the PNCS, CONARIV and the late CDVR, the Military Tribunal (TM), the National Commission of Inquiry (CNE), the Ministry of Reconciliation, Ministry of Justice, the Ministry of Solidarity, as well as those

special parliamentary committees of inquiry relating to the PNCS. I collected the reports of these mechanisms from their establishment to 2020. Regarding the defunct CDVR, I collected its reports from its establishment until its replacement by CONARIV. The second corpus concerns documents produced by national and international organisations, NGOs, and civil society associations. I was reassured that these organisations are involved in research on reconciliation and social cohesion in Côte d'Ivoire. This corpus mainly contains the annual reports, publications, and press conferences of the leaders of the collective of victims in Côte d'Ivoire (CVCI), the International Centre for Transitional Justice (ICTJ), the Action for the Protection of the Rights of Man (APDH). The choice of these NGOs is justified by the fact that the CVCI is the largest organisation representing the interests of victims. As a result, it follows the national reconciliation process very closely and knows better than anyone the socio-economic situation of the victims. The APDH conducts studies and conducts public debates, particularly on the Ivorian crises, their consequences, reconciliation, and the building of lasting peace. APDH has already published on the reconciliation process in Côte d'Ivoire. ICTJ advises the National Social Cohesion Program (PNCS), the Ministry of Solidarity, Social Cohesion and Compensation for Victims, the Dialogue, Truth, and Reconciliation Commission (CDVR) and the National Commission for Reconciliation and Compensation for Victims (CONARIV) on how to define reparations based on effective consultations with victims, registering victims, combining existing databases and reaching previously excluded victims (especially more remote areas).

Finally, the last corpus concerns documents relating to the recent history of Côte d'Ivoire. These are writings that focus on the Ivorian conflicts, on the notions of reparation and reconciliation and consisted of books and press information (public and private, national, and international).

Conclusion

Involving all conflict actors, as well as governmental and non-governmental organizations, is crucial for establishing consensus in the legislation, mandate, powers, and processes related to truth and reconciliation commissions. Successful reconciliation initiatives have demonstrated that including various parties and the public in the establishment and operation of such commissions enhances their

effectiveness. To examine the remedial and conciliatory potential of the CDVR, the researcher will apply established criteria rooted in the principles of restorative justice. The next chapter will outline the evaluation framework designed to effectively assess the impacts of the CDVR within the context of restorative justice in the specific case study.

CHAPTER FIVE: EVALUATION FRAMEWORK DESIGN

The aim of this chapter is to establish the CDVR evaluation framework. It first explains why theories of recognition, and theories of change are used in this research. Next, the chapter explains the importance of evaluating truth commissions. Finally, it defines the evaluation criteria according to the principles and programmes of restorative justice. These evaluation criteria make it possible, in chapter 6, to evaluate CDVR through restorative justice.

5.1 Theories of recognition

In his work, *Journey of Recognition* (2004), Ricoeur (1913-2005) emphasised that recognition is not a univocal term. It is a term which admits multiple meanings ranging from the cognitive level (recognising a shape, a face, etc.) to the legal level (recognition of debt, recognizing an act, etc.) via the moral level (feeling or unrecognized, ask to be recognized) to which arises the conceptual meaning which is found in the principle of what we classify today under the generic title of theories of recognition (from Hegel to Honneth, Renault, Dejours or Fraser via Kojève or Lacan). As Kojève (1947), Honneth (1992) or Taylor (1992) have each highlighted in their own way, it was Hegel who was the first to remove recognition (*Anerkennung*) from the rank of a key concept in moral and political philosophy. The first decisive element to underline is that if the theme of recognition has gradually established itself as a centre of moral, political, and social reflection to the point of being qualified as a new total social phenomenon (Caille, 2007), it is not in the name of a decision or a turning point that could be analysed on a strictly theoretical level. This is due to a transformation in the discourse of social actors who, on the political, social and cultural level, have themselves adopted this lexicon of recognition to describe the dynamics of the struggles they engage in or, upstream of these struggles and in a consequently more negative mode, the suffering generated by the denial of recognition (Fischbach, 1999, p. 5-6; Renault, 2004, 2008).

This struggle, the goal of which is recognition, manifests itself in many ways and takes pathological forms from time to time. However, this struggle generally comes as a reaction to situations of denial of recognition experienced by the actors concerned as such. These situations of denial of recognition most often take the form of denial of dignity or identity. The struggle for recognition turns into a reality of a struggle against

denial of recognition whose goal is dignity or identity. This deciphering of the social struggle contrasts with the grid which reduces the conflictual at the heart of the social to a struggle for survival.

An unprecedented change would even have taken place in the struggle for social justice. Alain Caille (2004) points out that for two centuries, the bulk of social conflict in modern societies has been about economic inequalities. For the past two or three decades, on the contrary, this social conflict has been organised around the question of recognition (Caille, 2004, p. 5). The demand for recognition is made everywhere, be it gender, sexuality, ethnic, cultural, or religious minorities, economic conflicts, or victims in periods of transitional justice (Nadeau, 2009, pp. 115–142). The demand for recognition is transformed nowadays into a question of citizenship, a social question and suggests integration into contemporary societies, considering both the common humanity of all and human diversity. The request for recognition takes the form of a request for fundamental rights, specific rights that we seek to include in the list of fundamental rights.

By deploying in situations of denial of recognition, such as contempt, humiliation, non-respect, disapproval or even invisibility (Voirol, 2004, p. 322), the struggle for recognition shows all its emancipatory aim. It reflects a legitimate requirement and aims to provide the various difficult actors and social groups with intersubjective supports for redressing the relationship with themselves and with others for a minimum of autonomy. If the struggle comes in reaction to situations of social contempt, it is because of the constitutive vulnerability of human subjects. This arises from the fact that the human subject exists only outside of himself, in intersubjectivity, in the desire and dependence of others. The human community is the place of the formation of the human personality. The different actors need to have access to the conditions for positively forming their identity. Individual existence would be unthinkable without a minimum of trust in the world and in others. Otherness is the basis of subjectivity, it is the fundamental condition of its reality, of its effectiveness. Just as subjectivity only arises in intersubjectivity as such, it is also inter-subjectively vulnerable. Social interaction can alter social relations and to the limit deprive certain actors of the minimum conditions essential for their achievement. The young black experience described by Ralph Ellison (Christophe, 1998) in his novel "Invisible Man, Who Do You

Sing For?" is illustrative in this perspective. In an American society where xenophobia, racism and even nationalism are commonplace, this young black "American" was confronted with the experience of invisibility because he is deprived of the emotional, legal, and social supports of esteem of most of the American white population. Like this young black man, this romantic character whose image reflects well a pathology of American society before the 1960s, there are many people and social categories in the world including in Côte d'Ivoire who suffer from their situation of anonymity and invisible humans, of humiliation and domination in contemporary societies where situations of injustice are increasingly garish and trivialised (Dejours, 1998).

In his essay "The Politics of Recognition" Taylor (1997, pp.41-99) argues that democracy requires a political community where citizens share common goals and recognise their members as 'they share these same goals. According to him, citizens must experience a strong sense of patriotism, understood in the sense of "strong identification with a common good". This conception of democracy poses important problems, for those who see in the democratic community first and foremost a community of individuals who can certainly act as a group, but which is first and foremost the regrouping of identities. distinct. Taylor is aware of the danger, and this is why, according to him, any society must provide mechanisms where exclusion cannot take place without legitimate reasons. So, he believes that identification with a common good is not contrary to the pluralism of contemporary societies. Differences are just as many points from which individuals start to converge towards a common goal. The recognition model that Taylor recommends would have the advantage, in a transitional context, of presenting a conceptual framework for collectively valid demands both politically and legally. A priori, requests for recognition based on the idea of the common good can be understood as conditions of possibility for more precise claims from individuals. Taylor published in 1992 a major work in political philosophy, *Multiculturalism: Difference and Democracy* (Taylor, 1992, p. 144), in which he tackled the question of the recognition of ethnocultural minorities from the point of view of state public institutions. It examines the question of whether liberal democracies should meet the demands of recognition of citizens based on their collective identity. According to Taylor, because individuals derive their identity from the group in which they have been socialised, he concludes that failure to recognise the specific needs of ethnocultural groups, or that misrecognising or ignoring their

specific requirements results in a denial of fundamental rights. In this sense, institutions should not “remain blind” to these differences but rather recognise them. Taylor thus tries to build a theoretical model from which it is possible to reconcile the recognition of equal dignity and that of difference.

To develop his thesis, Taylor uses the Hegelian presupposition of the intersubjectivity of human identity and affirms, like Honneth, the intrinsic link between the concept of recognition and the formation of the modern identity of individuals. In studying the evolution of human identity, Taylor argues that with modernity two important social phenomena have occurred. First, there was a shift between the concept of honour based on social hierarchies and the concept of dignity which grants de facto a form of equal recognition valid for all citizens. In democracies, therefore, egalitarian forms of recognition have developed. Moreover, with modernity, appears, according to Taylor, the "principle of originality" (1992, p. 47-8) according to which every individual has the possibility of leading his life as he sees fit:

“Each of our voices has something unique to say. Not only do I not have to model my life on the demands of exterior conformism; I cannot even find a model of life outside of myself. I can only find it in myself”.

(Taylor, 1992, p. 48)

The principle of originality is however inscribed within the dialogical character of the individual. To discover himself and find his uniqueness, the individual must relate to others. In other words, the identity of individuals is dependent on relations of recognition.

Based on the postulate that identity is partially formed by recognition or lack of it, or even by the misperception of others, Taylor asserts that a person or a group of people can suffer harm or harm. real distortion if the people or society around them conveys a limited demeaning or contemptible image of themselves. Non-recognition or inadequate recognition can cause harm and constitute a form of oppression, trapping some in a false, distorted, and reduced way of being (Taylor, 1992, pp. 41–42). Taylor adds that, it is thus from the concept of recognition that it is possible to explain the emergence of new social movements whose demands are cultural, and identity based. Indeed, the author believes that social movements have undergone an evolution in

which they have moved from the struggle for equal rights to the struggle for the recognition of cultural difference. Indeed, the rights claimed by social movements would no longer be rights for equality, but rather the expression of specific needs expressed by communities. According to Taylor, this evolution within the demands led by social movements perhaps makes the notion of universal and equally applicable rights obsolete but rather requires in return the establishment of policies of recognition of difference.

Honneth recognises, like Taylor, the Hegelian presupposition of the intersubjectivity of human identity as well as the intrinsic link between recognition and the formation of personal identity. However, the concept of recognition developed by Honneth remains, at the conceptual level, very different from that developed by Taylor. First, Honneth opposes the linear historical view of social movements according to which social struggles have shifted from the struggle for legal equality to the struggle for the recognition of cultural difference (Honneth, 2002, p. 122). According to Honneth, the new social movements are not uniquely identity-based but rather are determined by several dimensions at the same time; their cultural, political, economic or identity characteristics are more intertwined than they are dissociated (*ibid.* pp.122-124).

Thus, the concept of recognition developed by Taylor is exclusively cultural and identity, while the concept of recognition defined by Honneth rather brings together all forms of cultural and socio-economic conflicts. It therefore appears that the two authors do not speak of the same concept of recognition, one not being more valid than the other insofar as they fall within different theoretical fields. For Honneth, the concept of recognition, serving as a normative foundation for critical theory, is not limited to the identity paradigm. Indeed, the concept of recognition constitutes, unlike Taylor's proposition, the central normative principle making it possible to encompass all forms of protest, both those linked to the identity paradigm and those linked to material redistribution:

"The conceptual framework of recognition is of central importance not because it expresses the objectives of a new type of social movement, but because it has proven to be that appropriate tool for categorically unlocking social experiences of injustice as a whole"

(Honneth, 2002, p. 133)

For Honneth, the concept of recognition is not contingent on the emergence of contemporary social phenomena. Rather, he develops the concept of recognition with the aim of finding a normative criterion that makes it possible to identify the different forms of social pathologies present in society. One of the fundamental principles of critical theory is to succeed in linking the normative foundations to a theory of the social. Following the principle of “transcendence in social immanence” (Fraser and Honneth, 2003, p. 238). Honneth makes a normative reconstruction from the social experience which allows him to develop the concept of recognition. Here is, more precisely, how Honneth responds, using the concept of recognition, to the challenge posed by critical theory:

“The idea is that the principle of recognition is in a way social. This, therefore, is the link between the theory of the social and the normative foundation. I believe that any critical theory must maintain this link to be able to develop its own normative criteria from a complete theory of the social. This constitutes the fundamental difference from the Kantian tradition. The normative criteria that we take as the basis of a critique of society or of certain forms of socialisation must not only be acquired through reflection and rational construction but must be part of the social. I have designed my own work as part of this project and recognition theory is an attempt to demonstrate this link between social and internal normative principles”

(Honneth, 2006, p. 154).

Thus, Honneth develops the concept of recognition from a theoretical perspective different from that of Taylor. While the concept of recognition, according to Taylor, makes it possible to explain the emergence of new social movements linked to cultural and identity claims, the concept of recognition makes it possible, according to Honneth, to encompass all forms of contest. Representing a form of immanence in transcendence, the concept of recognition responds to the requirements of critical theory; this is the reason why the concept of recognition can serve as a normative foundation for critical theory.

5.2 Evaluation of impact through theory-based approach

The evaluation of the impact of setting up the Truth and Reconciliation Commission is becoming increasingly important. It can be carried out at all stages, from its establishment to the implementation of operations, as well as its real relevance and regulation. This exercise is systematic and objective to draw lessons for improving policy and practice, as well as increasing accountability (Glouberman, 2002). The evaluations make it possible, on the one hand, to reflect on the events leading to the establishment of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission and the reactions aroused by it and, on the other hand, to determine the possibility of modifying the procedures to improve the functioning of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission in the future (Hallam, 1999).

To evaluate the procedure for setting the CDVR, it is necessary to use an appropriate approach and methodology. There are two stages to the assessment: first, gathering evidence to conclude that something is the case; and second, to judge these conclusions against pre-established criteria. Evaluation promotes change by taking recommendations into account and by the debates it generates between the actors concerned. The evaluation must therefore open both a new understanding of reality and an ability to act differently: A new understanding of reality: The role of evaluation consists precisely in the constitution of a position "out of step" in relation to ordinary statements which are often too massive and deliberately vague (or consensual) to give rise to contradictory debate (CRDSU, 1995). The evaluation therefore carries in itself a great potential for controversy. The actors cannot completely ignore the information resulting from it. Even if they wish to discredit them, they must develop an argument allowing them to reject them. The actors must have a process of deliberation that makes it possible to give meaning to these data and to agree on an interpretation that is viable for practice. The practice of evaluation must therefore always be attentive to this inseparable link between the production of information and the production of understanding in an organised environment (Contandriopoulos *et al.*, 2000). In the literature and in practice, there are many debates on the notion of "impact" and how to account for it. Some authors assimilate impact assessment to an experimental form based on the principle of constituting one or more groups of so-called "experimental" (or treatment) and a group called "control" (formed in a random). This approach, whose objectivity remains questionable, called Randomised Controlled Trial (RCT), is based

on the principles of randomisation and random sampling. Once the duration of any intervention is fixed and the time necessary for the expected results to occur, it compares the effects observed among the different groups (treatment and control) to isolate the effect related to the intervention. Finally, the RCT consists in evaluating by means of a set of pre-established indicators, the capacity of the project or more than an intervention, to achieve or not its objectives. This approach has the advantage of establishing solid cause-effect links that link the outcome to the intervention. More generally, the term impact is constitutive of a diversity of elements which calls for a classification into drawers (Graugnard, G and Heeren, N, 1999). Thus, in this logic of drawers, we can retain the following definition:

“The impact of a development action is the situation resulting from all the significant and lasting changes, positive or negative, planned, or unforeseen, in the life and environment of individuals and groups and for which a direct or indirect causal link can be established with the development action”

(Graugnard and Heeren, 1999).

It should be noted that in the design of a project or a programme, predicting the impact presents even more difficulties than anticipating the effects, so much so that many factors independent of the project are likely to combine with the results and effects of the action. According to the OECD (2008), impact is generally defined as the set of changes that result directly or indirectly from an action. This analysis can concern the individual, his family, a company or the local or national environment, depending on several domains (economic, social, anthropological, health, etc.) (OECD, 2008: Annex 1). Impact measurement is usually tied to a specific area, objectives, and interests of different stakeholders. The impact of a project generally qualifies the set of changes induced by the achievements. For the beneficiaries of a project, it represents the changes that have occurred in their living conditions as they themselves and their partners perceive them as well as any lasting change in their environment to which the project contributed, whether positive or negative, wanted, or unforeseen. We often speak of the impact of a project in reference to the general objective or finality, at the highest level of the hierarchy of objectives (OECD, 2008: Annex 1).

In this thesis, how the process works requires how the Truth Commission promotes reconciliation by seeking restorative potential in its process. Why has a truth commission worked like this requires the terms of a truth commission to contribute to reconciliation? Answering these questions requires presenting an explanation of impact, an impact assessment based on a theory of change. To do this, we must make an explicit choice, which explains how and why truth commissions help to promote reconciliation.

The following section presents the conceptual and analytical framework for examining the impacts of truth commissions, the theory of change that explains how truth commissions should work to bring about change. Second, the empirical component which is the evaluation criterion is presented.

5.3 A theory of change (TOC)

In recent years, to improve the quality of interventions within the framework of development projects, the emphasis has now been placed on a deep analysis of social change. For the development of a project or programme, the current need for some donors is to perceive the real change that was visible, and the methodology used to achieve it. To address all these concerns, a new tool has emerged. This is the theory of change. It draws its source from the theory of social change. In 1970, the Brazilian educator, Freire, made a plea to allow the populations to speak about their belief in poverty and how they think to solve it, as well as the actions which must be carried out to overcome this difficulty. This is how the theory first appeared. The theory followed a silent course until 1990 when it resurfaced, following Weiss's statement. Faced with the difficulties encountered by project evaluators, Weiss published an article in 1995. According to him, it was difficult to properly evaluate several projects because there was no connection between activities and results, (Weiss, 1995) cited by (Cathy 2013). Some authors consider this date to be the beginning of the history of the theory of change. "The theory of change emerged in the mid-1990s in response to the challenge of evaluating the impact of complex development programs. Its purpose now is to address the issues that evaluators face when trying to assess the impact of complex, social development programs. This involved making assumptions, a lack of clarity about how the change process was developing and given insufficient attention to the sequences of change necessary for the long-term goals to be achieved", (O " Flynn

2012) cited by (O'Flynn & Clare, 2015, P. 1). Then it was the Aspen Research Institute that developed the first guide to the theory of change in projects. The theory of change is a process. It promotes continuous and deep reflection. The benefits of using it as a planning tool are numerous:

“It develops a common understanding among all partners of what an organisation or project is trying to change and how to get there. It can enhance the clarity, efficiency and purpose of organisations and programmes. It provides a framework for monitoring, evaluation, and impact assessment. It helps to improve the partnership by helping to identify strategic partners and by supporting transparent exchanges around change. It empowers people to become more active and get involved in the execution of programmes”, (Cathy, 2011), P. 4. Weiss said that ‘A programme is a theory, and an evaluation is its test. To organise the evaluation to provide responsible testing, the evaluator needs to understand the theory on which the programme is based”

(Weiss (1998) cited in De Reviere (2012).

With the theory of change, the evaluation serves to confirm or not the basic assumptions made by the project. With this tool, any project execution is part of an action research framework.

Theory of change is described as a flexible approach designed to encourage critical thinking in the design, execution, and evaluation phases of development activities. Vogel (2012) indicates that “the mode of thinking specific to theories of change” is increasingly popular among many actors in international development. For Vogel (2012), a theory of change is a process of analysis and learning that provides elements to support critical thinking throughout the program cycle. It is also a flexible approach that can usefully foster innovation in programmatic strategies, so that it can react and adapt to a changing context. The terms used to describe the models describing the logic of the interventions are very varied; we are mainly talking about programme theory, logic model, theory of change, chain of effects or results, theory of action, theory of implementation, and it may be that there is no have no consensus on the terminology or meaning of the terms. Patton (Patton, 2008, pp. 336–340), just like Funnell and Rogers (2011, pp. 15–34), even discussed their characteristics and

presented their history. The study focused on the theory of change that is the subject of this study. Theories of change are used in many ways, both for the development, management, and evaluation of interventions. This study also focuses on the use of theories of change for the evaluation of interventions in a reconciliation process. James (2011), Vogel (2012), and Stein and Valters (2012) analysed the use of theories of change, and they all noted that beyond a consensus on what a theory of change is, for example models showing how the intervention should work, they observe several interpretations of how to develop and describe theories of change.

The few key terms that appear in theories of change are outcomes, intervention, and chain of effects. The results contain the proximal effects, the intermediate effects as well as the impacts which are the last results before well-being. The intervention describes activities implemented to produce a desirable difference in outcomes. To understand whether an intervention works and how it works, it is important to understand how the activities of that intervention are expected to produce the expected results. In other words, we must understand a) the causal path between activities and outcomes from proximal effects to impacts; b) causal assumptions that show why and under what conditions causal links are supposed to work. In the case of an intervention, these causal links are also known as the results chain, logic model, and effect chains. This study also focused on the term "chain of effects" which shows the causal links between the different stages from activities to impacts. A theory of change adds the causal assumptions that underlie each of its links to the chain of effects, in other words, it specifies what must happen for the causal links to materialize. The theory of change indicates how the change is supposed to happen (ex-ante case) or happened (ex post case).

The theory of change is

“a way of describing how a group hopes to achieve a given long-term goal. This is not a method designed specifically to measure impact, as it primarily serves as a tool to help develop solutions to complex social problems”

(Anderson, 2005, p. 1).

The evaluative concept of theories of change has developed programme theory, with added recognition of how things happen and who enacts them (Vogel, 2012).

Incorporating this practise from the beginning of an analysis is an especially strong approach. Developing a theory of change, therefore, requires the following, staged approach:

1. "Define the targeted change, long term.
2. Specify the different changes that must occur beforehand for the ultimate change to become possible.
3. Explain the assumptions and values that underlie the reasoning.
4. Specify the link between this reasoning and the intervention

(De Reviere, 2012, p. 3).

As an objective of transitional justice, reconciliation is the process of restoring cordial relations between perpetrators and their victims, leading to peace. The question is whether the parties to the conflict can establish a common foundation for a state and an acceptance of the atrocities of the past. The sense of justice for victims of violations and their families is closely linked to reconciliation. A sense of justice is necessary for the healing of personal and psychological wounds which enables reconciliation. It also limits the grounds for murderous retaliation. Reconciliation further requires a concerted effort to educate the public about the process of accountability, so that they can see this process as a legitimate tool for the pursuit of social and political cohesion. Reconciliation depends on the mandate, the objectives and above all the process of the Truth Commission.

5.4 Criteria to evaluate the Truth Commission

Seven criteria (CR-1 to CR-7) to evaluate the Truth Commission through restorative justice are developed. Restorative justice being a justice based on the participation and engagement of all those involved in conflicts includes principles and programmes such as inclusion, negotiation, reparation, truth-telling, and restoration. These are the principles that constitute the CDVR evaluation criteria. The aim was to determine how restorative justice is present or absent in the design of CDVR and its implementation. By analysing the levels of participation or inclusion of all parties, whether in its dimension of negotiation, recognition or application, the study was able to assess the existence of the participatory relationships that a Truth Commission generates. It is important, as a first step, to clarify the criteria developed so that the conceptual framework of restorative justice can be applied to research data sources. This allowed

to evaluate how restorative justice is present or absent in the design of CDVR and its implementation.

5.4.1 Criterion 1 (CR-1): CDVR as a Negotiated Institution

Truth commissions are generally established by law, offering power like those of a judicial institution. This requires an instrument of legal value superior to an executive decree. Further, the establishment of a law may be seen by some as possessing greater democratic legitimacy. Conversely, the failure of a legislative process can undermine the instrument that establishes the truth commission. Examples of this can be seen in several cases. For example, Morocco, El Salvador, Indonesia and Nepal all had different experiences because of how they were originated. The legitimacy of the government, or the length and transparency of the process are particularly important. Establishment by statute is especially useful for success, commissions established by other means can also meet their objectives. Various, commissions have been established by royal decree (Morocco), United Nations Transitional Administration ordinance (East Timor) or through peace accords (El Salvador). The quality of commissioners taking lead also has an important bearing on success. Most of the commissions are unique experiences, and commissioners' message and legitimacy can rest on their intellectual and organisational skills, to conceptualise and oversee a complex.

5.4.2 Criterion 2 (CR-2): CDVR as an Inclusive Process

Participation and engagement in TRCs are a critical part of restorative justice, where it is necessary to include every group which have suffered injustice, though a formal, structured process. Inclusion can be conceptualised along several dimensions, such as how much and how many victims, families of victims and communities participated, it is important also that those involved in perpetrating injustice are involved in the TC including, for example, rebels and any national army activities related to the reconciliation process. Participation and engagement also concern consultations at national level. The function of these is to stimulate discussion and negotiation between different components of government and society. This activity is designed to work through multiple perspectives, generate proposals and specify pathways forward. National consultations may occur through opinion polls, forums, focus groups or meetings between groups or representatives of the various stakeholders. The choice

of a consultative approaches to the establishment and operation of a consultation and TC practices is one of the most notable aspects of a successful approach (OHCHR, section II, 4–5). Specifically, the consultation represents an enrichment for the design of an instrument of transitional justice and is seen as a means of encouraging legitimacy. Participation and engagement also refer to how restoration processes take place and their planned outcomes. For this thesis, the question of the extent to which the CDVR is an inclusive process where different stakeholders contribute to its establishment and running will be investigated. Conversely, it is also important to understand who has *not* been included when considering the extent to which all parties affected by the Ivorian conflicts have had the opportunity to participate in the process of establishing and maintaining the reconciliation commission. Interviews and the design of a purposive sample are therefore important to understanding involvement in the reconciliation process.

5.4.3 Criterion 3 (CR-3): Focused on the victim and Empowerment in the TRC's Context

In a victim-centred approach, the safety, wishes and well-being of the victim come first in all matters and proceedings. Too often, however, victims must wait long periods of time to obtain essential services. This thesis focuses on empowering survivors to tell their stories of how the Ivorian wars have affected them. This thesis aims to empower survivors to tell the story of how the CDVR was created and how it worked. This involves analysing the support that the CDVR provided to survivors. This support can be the presence of friends, community members, family and loved ones. Additionally, the dissertation examined community support resources available to help survivors.

5.4.4 Criterion 4 (CR-4): CDVR and Truth-Telling

The main goal of restorative justice is to uncover the truth about past atrocities or injustices. This consists of investigating the reasons why atrocities were committed, the perpetrators and the period. The main question we ask in this step is the following: is CDVR able to accurately transcribe the past? In part, this presupposes the ability and willingness of survivors and perpetrators to uncover the truth about the experiences of different conflicts. The perpetrators of the crimes are often the national army, militias, traditional hunters commonly called *dozos* and self-defence groups. Their stories of abuse can help create a re-enactment of the events. The thesis

therefore analyses the potential for healing emotional wounds and building connections with survivors. The design of the CDVR was reviewed. This made it possible to search for elements that encourage the authors to tell the truth about the conflict. Finally, the thesis analysed the truth-seeking capability of CDVR.

5.4.5 Criterion 5 (CR-5): Recognition of Survivors' identities and overcoming denial of injustice

Lack of knowledge leads to frustration. In Côte d'Ivoire, stereotypes of xenophobia and exclusion were exaggerated. This section then seeks to examine the potential of the CDVR to promote the recognition of survivors as envisaged by Axel Honneth. The objective is to consider the capacity of the CDVR to raise public awareness about the history, cultures, contribution, and integration of survivors.

5.4.6 Criterion 6 (CR-6): Restoring Survivors' Dignity and Self-respect

Restoring the dignity of survivors can come from various sources such as hearing and acknowledging their stories of war experiences and damage. CDVR is therefore assessed on its capability to afford a satisfactory recognition. Also, it is evaluated according to its capacity to justify the status of survivors as victims.

5.4.7 Criterion 7 (CR-7): Flexibility of reparations programmes

To meet the needs of the individual, programmes must be flexible. Each victim is different. The programmes should offer several possibilities for victims. For example, in addition to direct mediation (i.e., face-to-face) we must also offer indirect mediation (without meeting). According to research, this approach may be preferable for some victims who do not wish to face the offender. In addition, there is no need for a confrontational meeting for mediation to be effective. Indirect mediation would generate great satisfaction for victims (Aertsen and Peters, 1998) and contribute to their healing (Barlingen, Slump and Tulner, 2000). If the offender does not have enough money to reimburse his victim, one can think of community service carried out for the benefit of the victims (Aertsen, 2000). To assess flexibility of programmes of CDVR, I examine the programmes provided by the CDVR and the mechanisms by which the victims receive them. The meaning of symbolic reparations is to convey a message of dignity and recognition of the victims. This is what sets them apart from social policies and humanitarian aid. The term reparation does not refer only to

financial compensation. CDVR's symbolic reparations, as explored in this research, included non-monetary attempts to symbolically repair damage to victims. The table 3 below presents the stages of the CDVR and evaluation criterion.

Table 3: Stages of the CDVR and evaluation criterion

STAGES	EVALUATION CRITERION
CDVR before its establishment	(CR-1) CDVR as a Negotiated Institution
CDVR during his mandate	(CR-2) CDVR as an Inclusive Process, (CR-3) Focused on the victim and Empowerment in the CDVR's Context (CR-4) CDVR and Truth-Telling.
CDVR after its mandate	(CR-5) Recognition of survivors' identities and overcome the denial of injustice, (CR-6) Restoring Survivors' Dignity and Self-respect, (CR-7) Flexibility of reparation programmes

Source: Author

Conclusion

This chapter introduced the theory of recognition, the theory of change and the evaluation criteria of the CDVR. Recognizing a victim is a very important act. Speaking of victims, it is therefore difficult to define what it is because there is a diversity of definitions. In this research, it is about the recognition of war victims according to international law. The compensation claimed by the victims is not necessarily financial. For some, it is simply a matter of obtaining recognition for what they have suffered. We must simply recognize them as victims. The main objective of the CDVR being peace and reconciliation, it is necessary to know how to achieve this reconciliation. It is in this sense that the theory of change made it possible to use the principles and programs of restorative justice to develop evaluation criteria. The next one allows you to make the evaluation based on the criteria in this chapter.

CHAPTER SIX: IMPLEMENTING THE FRAMEWORK

This chapter presents the appropriate assessment of the Ivorian Truth Commission (CDVR). The chapter examines the extent to which the CDVR, in its process, contributed to promoting peace and reconciliation in Côte d'Ivoire.

To enrich the development of the study, 35 face-to-face (F2F) interviews were conducted as a vital component of the research process. These interviews provided a direct and invaluable insight into the experiences, perceptions, and perspectives of a diverse group of individuals who had a stake in the future of Côte d'Ivoire. The selection process was guided by the intention to capture a wide range of viewpoints from individuals of varying backgrounds, professions, and geographical locations within Côte d'Ivoire. Participants included the governance regime, former commissioners and NGOs and experts.

The governance regime which represents former and current members of the government, former and current members of parliament and senior officers of the army and of the police. The choice of this category is motivated by the fact that the members are decision-makers from Cote d'Ivoire. The second category of people interviewed is the former commissioners who are members of the CDVR, CONARIV and PNCS. Their choice is motivated by the fact that they are active members of the reconciliation process: The last category of people interviewed is the NGOs and experts who represent political parties and their leaders, the representative of victims, the representative of students, civil society, etc. The choice of this category is motivated by the fact that the people interviewed know the suffering and needs of the victims. After transcribing the interviews, a comparative analysis of the interviews of the different categories of people focused was done to better understand the results of the research.

6.1 An overview of the Ivorian commission

This section provides an overview of the CDVR and an analysis of the legal institutions, powers, and committee members. The study also examined the findings and, the recommendations made by the CDVR. Finally, the question of whether the recommendations were made public was raised.

6.1.1 Context of establishment and legal status of the CDVR

As stated in chapter one, the post-electoral crisis has bereaved the Ivorians, thereby leading to immeasurable consequences. Truth Commission was established by ordinance n° 2011-167 of the July 13, 2011, following the post-electoral crisis (from October to November 2011). A decade before, a similar attempt had been made from October 9 to December 18, 2001. A reconciliation forum was organised to put an end to socio-political tensions. This structure was chaired by former Ivorian Prime Minister Seydou Elimane Diarra, and its members were religious and community leaders. The lack of political will contributed to the failure of the reconciliation forum as all political organisations did not find points of convergence to resolve the conflicts between them. The consequence of this failure was materialised eight months later by an offensive of the rebellion of the New Forces (FN) launched in the north of the country towards the capital, Abidjan, in September 2002. This is how the country was divided into two blocks. One block was composed of the north, centre and west. It was under rebellion occupation. The other block comprised the rest of the country. It was under government control for a decade (2002-2011). It is on the strength of this fragile past that the CDVR was established to take up the challenge of consolidating peace. In addition to the already extreme poverty, hundreds of thousands of widows, orphans and disabled people were victims of the massacres. Certainly, although they regained the right to physical life by the very fact of having been saved from war and massacres, these people remained, for the most part, morally and psychologically dead. They needed a reassurance whose determining ingredient is material aid. To try to remedy this sad situation, the Ivorian government had promoted the establishment of transitional justice mechanisms (CDVR, 2014). The Ivorian truth commission, the CDVR was a public institution with a legal personality, and it was created for a limited period. The Dialogue, Truth and Reconciliation Commission was both a series of so-called transitional justice mechanisms and a driving force for dialogue between the populations of Côte d'Ivoire. In accordance with the ordinance which instituted it, its role was to create the conditions for the eradication of violence and human rights violations to achieve reconciliation between Ivorians.

The objectives of the CDVR were to contribute to national reconciliation, which is a long-term process, a work constantly renewed. The mission consisted in highlighting the underlying causes of the Ivorian crisis in order to (i) better understand it, (ii) identify

the victims and perpetrators of human rights violations that have occurred in Côte d'Ivoire in the past, (iii) propose reparations that promote healing injuries suffered by victims, (iv) propose appropriate measures to avoid the repetition of violations and (v) ensure the training of citizens in accordance with human rights and democratic culture.

6.2 Evaluation of the CDVR

This section presents evidence investigate the restorative potential in the design and practices of the CDVR. From the framework in the previous chapter five, seven evaluation criteria (CR) are used to assess the commissions. Criteria one refers to restoring social ties and reconciliation before the establishment of the truth commission. Criteria two to four correspond to restoring social ties and reconciliation during the commission's mandate. Criteria five to seven correspond to restoring social ties following the recommendations of the final report.

6.2.1 Restoring Social Ties and Reconciliation Before the Establishment of the Commission

This section presents suggested evaluation criterion 1 (CR-1) is the CDVR as a Negotiated Institution.

Criterion 1 (CR-1): TRC as a Negotiated Institution

If all stakeholders, including members of government, parliamentarians, politicians, lawyers, civil society, and parties affected by the Ivorian conflicts, had the opportunities to participate in the negotiations of the creation of the CDVR, the commission will be considered as a negotiated institution and can contribute to appeasement.

The early stages of the CDVR design

To reduce these traumas, the CDVR was created in 2011 by the Ivorian government: “Charles Konan Banny was appointed president. There was no prior agreement between the parties before his appointment and the creation of the commission” (Civil Society, PP3). The CDVR was a wish of President Alassane Ouattara, and its mandate was set by order on July 13, 2011, by the President of the Republic. According to Governance GM1, the Commission developed an organization chart which intended to cover Ivorian society in its plurality and be sufficiently decentralized to reach the

most remote localities. It was composed of an executive committee which, under the leadership of President Charles Konan Banny, brought together three vice-presidents representing different religious denominations and traditional chiefdoms, and seven central commissioners representing different regions of the country and the diaspora (Governance, GM1).

According to some *members of civil society* such as PP1, PP2, VR1, the appointment of CDVR members was not transparent because M. Konan Banny, the President of the CDVR was the former regional campaign director of the President of the Republic (Civil Society, PP1; PP2; VR1). This posed a problem because Charles Konan Banny, the president of the CDVR, is a political figure and an actor in the Ivorian crisis. As a result, trust has taken time to establish itself within a certain population group. On paper, the CDVR appears to be a complete mechanism meeting the best standards of transitional justice “toolboxes”.

Some *civil society actors*, including HR1, member of an Ivorian human rights NGO, denounce “that the CDVR suffered from a lack of credibility. The selection of its members was not rigorous, and it was not independent. Civil society has been marginalised by this commission” (civil society, HR1). Several opposition political leaders went in the same direction. One of the political leaders denounces that they were never asked to set up a reconciliation commission (civil society, PP2). Civil Society PP2 adds “I would say that it is perhaps because I was in prison but, since my release from prison, no activist from my political party has informed me that they had been contacted for the establishment of “a reconciliation commission” (Civil Society, PP2).

Additionally, political issues influenced the composition of the central committee. Miran-Guyon thus reports in the book, based on his thesis *Mystical Wars in Côte d’Ivoire*, that President Charles Konan Banny considered the evangelical churches entirely responsible for the crisis which shook the country (Miran-Guyon, 2015). This is why they did not have a representative in this assembly, unlike the Catholics and Muslims. Among the central commissioners, the presence of Didier Drogba caused a sensation, but the famous footballer was unable to influence the CDVR process (Civil society, PP1). It is estimated that the committee was able to benefit from a budget of 15 million euros. “Insufficient”, assert some commissioners to ward off criticism: “This

is the crux of the problem. We did not have enough funds and budget allocations were not flexible.” The members of the commission believe that the budget of \$15 million was insufficient to work on the ground (commissioner, CD1, CD2).

Finally, the creation of the Dialogue, Truth and Reconciliation Commission (CDVR) was heavily influenced by international actors such as the UN and the African Union. As expressed by a former political figure “The involvement of the UN and the African Union was useful to reassure the international community, but it gave the impression that reconciliation was not entirely desired by Ivorians themselves. This weakened the national legitimacy of the CDVR, perceived as an externally imposed initiative” (Civil Society PP5). This statement highlights the tension between the need to meet international expectations and the need for a genuinely homegrown process.

The political journalist interviewed also emphasised the weight of diplomatic pressure: “Given the diplomatic pressure, the country could not emerge from the crisis on its own. Internationalisation imposed a standard model poorly adapted to Ivorian realities” (Civil Society ME2). This testimony reveals a paradox: while international support was seen as essential to break the country’s diplomatic isolation, it also confined the reconciliation process within a universal framework often inspired by other experiences (such as South Africa’s), without sufficiently considering Côte d’Ivoire’s specific social and political realities.

Finally, Civil Society HR3 expressed a critical view of the gap between popular expectations and the institutional form imposed:

“The population mainly wanted peace and justice. But the structure, through an institutional commission, largely stemmed from international requirements, and these external demands produced a commission disconnected from popular expectations”

(Civil Society HR3).

This observation highlights the discrepancy between local aspirations, focused on rapid and tangible justice, and the heavy, institutionalised process primarily designed to satisfy international visibility criteria.

Thus, these testimonies converge to show that, although international influence was decisive in initiating the reconciliation process, it also created a dynamic poorly suited to the Ivorian context. The feeling of a reconciliation “imposed” from the outside limited the CDVR’s national legitimacy and, consequently, its real impact on society.

The TRC organisational operations

Since its installation on September 28, 2011, the CDVR has striven to adopt the texts and create the bodies necessary for its operation. This is how internal regulations were developed, adopted in December 2011, which determine its internal organization (CDVR, 2014).

"The writing of the statutes, the internal regulations, and the creation of the functional bodies of the Commission were only carried out with the members appointed by the President of the Republic and the President of the CDVR. However, to ensure the proper functioning and credibility of the Commission, it is essential to involve all parties. Furthermore, we were not informed in Parliament of such a procedure"

(Governance, MP1).

According to the operational bodies, the president of the CDVR directs and coordinates the activities of the Commission. He is assisted in his work by an executive committee which includes, in addition to the president, the three vice-presidents. The decision-making body of the CDVR is the plenary of commissioners. For the practical execution of the mission, four specialised commissions were created: the Heuristic Commission, the Hearing and Inquiry Commission, the Reparations Commission, and the Memorial Commission. The administration of the CDVR is placed under the responsibility of a secretary general who manages an administrative and financial director and a general director of resources who are all appointed without consultation (CDVR, 2014).

“It is abnormal and sad to note that all parties concerned, including leaders of political parties, rebels and civil society who are concerned about the Ivorian conflicts have not had the opportunity to contribute to the establishment of the CDVR”

(Civil Society, PP4).

6.2.2 Restoring Social Ties and Reconciliation During the Commission's Mandate

This section evaluates the CDVR during its tenure. Three criteria for evaluation are used. Criterion 2 (CR-2) assessed the CDVR as an inclusive process. Criterion 3 (CR-3) assessed the focus on the victim and empowerment in the context of CDVR and Criterion 4 (CR-4) assessed CDVR as a process of truth.

Criterion 2 (CR-2): CDVR as an Inclusive Process

While the previous section focused on the creation and negotiations of the CDVR, this section examines the national and community events of the CDVR, through which it intends to achieve its mandate. The essential objective of this review is to evaluate national and community CDVR events through the restorative justice literature. “This enables parties to work together constructively to envision and achieve a better future” (Llewellyn, 2008, p. 193). Common to CDVR national events is their vision of bringing together all parties, including survivors, government, and civil society, to uncover the truth and learn more about the experiences of the Ivorian population and conflicts. Within the framework of the Ivorian CDVR, national and community demonstrations seem to implement the principle of inclusion.

Inclusion and the CDVR Mandate

Between the period of creation of the truth commission and the submission of its report, TCs in general collect various information, notably on the causes of conflicts and the testimonies of witnesses, victims, and civil society. Thanks to these interactions and the revelation of evidence, the TCs can trace responsibilities and above all define reparation programmes. For TCs to be considered reconciliatory, it is first necessary that victims, witnesses and/or civil society organisations be included in the activities of TCs during their mandate (CR-2). To do this, TCs must reach out to witnesses, victims, and civil society, and confirm that the environment is safe for them to come forward and provide the information requested by the commissions.

Faced with criticism, a former member of the CDVR responds that it only has an “obligation of means, the responsibility for reconciliation falling on the President of the Republic to whom the CDVR report and its recommendations are addressed” (Commissioner, CD3). The first public hearings linked to the violence which ravaged

Côte d'Ivoire between 2000 and 2011 began without being public. The CDVR public hearings began Monday, September 8, 2014, in the morning in Abidjan (RFI, 2014). In the opinion of those interviewed, there was a lot of emotion present during the discussions, as expressed by various participants who emphasised the depth of their feelings regarding the issues at hand. Many respondents shared their personal experiences, highlighting the emotional weight of the topics discussed and how these sentiments played a crucial role in shaping their perspectives. Additionally, some participants noted that the charged atmosphere fostered a sense of urgency and importance in addressing the matters being deliberated. Unfortunately, few people were able to attend this moment because the room was cramped and closed to journalists. According to a journalist, this room could not accommodate more than 70 people and the hearings were not broadcast live on national television. The space rented by the CDVR was difficult to access. But that didn't stop some victims from coming from all over the country. This was the case of Mr. Joseph Tao Ba, a retiree from the World Health Organisation (WHO) whose house was destroyed during the crisis. Worried about the lack of communication, this victim wanted to be sure of being compensated (Civil Society, ME1).

If experts and certain members of civil society say they are satisfied with the start of the hearings, many point to the improvisation of the process. Questioned, Commissioner, CD1, affirmed that the organisation of the hearings was not simple:

“We are not saying that we did everything well, but we did what that we were able to allow this catharsis that the population needed to feel through the facts recounted by the victims, the experts or the perpetrators of the facts. We had the impression that nothing had happened in Côte d'Ivoire, that there were political leaders who were in total denial. People need to see what happened, hear what happened to return to non-repetition”

(Commissioner, CO1).

According to one political leader interviewed, “the mandate of the CDVR was imperfect. The place of the victims was not clear” (Civil Society, PP1). The political leader believes that “the CDVR must give priority to victims. It was supposed to be the victims' house, so the commission failed in its mission to seek the truth. This institution

has carried out work disconnected from social realities” (Civil Society, PP1). According to one member of parlement interviewed, the prefects and sub-prefects are very active in the west despite the lack of resources (Governance, PM2). The UNOCI Civil Affairs Division particularly supports their actions with the stated aim of restoring and strengthening the authority of the State. The parliamentarian affirms that the authority of most traditional leaders in the region is positively supported by the new president, but they denounce the absence of political support for reconciliation: “When we only talk about reconciliation, it is free, but sharing is rare,” the parliamentarian said (Governance, PM2).

Inclusion and TRC events

The CDVR, criticized for its very weak impact by a certain part of the population and victims (ICTJ, 2015), began to hear from certain victims, after two years of trial and error. This activity was the main task assigned to the commission. The first testimonies of people who suffered harm during socio-political events were recorded in eight cities across the country, indicated a member of the PNCS (Commissioner, PN1). “The operation consisted of the identification of the victims, followed by investigations (...) to trace the executioners,” explained Commissioner, CD3. According to a *Civil Society* interviewee, involved with defending human rights, the CDVR has not convinced in two years of activity, due to lack of means, notably political will, and the exclusion of certain parties to the crisis (Civil Society, HR4). Most members of the civil society interviewed unanimously criticize the lack of results and the exclusion of the commission (Civil Society, HR1, HR2, HR3). A member of the civil society assures that the commission “ignored” the victims (Civil Society, VR1). Civil Society VR1 deplored that the victims were not sufficiently heard. For VR1, the CDRV was not created to produce only a report (Civil Society, VR1). “The CDVR had to work for dialogue, the manifestation of the truth and reconciliation. This commission has failed in this mission, it has failed. Civil society was side-lined, the victims were abandoned, while the victims sought the truth and repentance...” (civil society, VR1). Civil Society ST1 called for the continuation of hearings of victims of the Ivorian crisis, as part of the implementation of the CDVR's missions. “We wholeheartedly asked the President of the Republic (Alassane Ouattara) to grant additional time to the CDVR to complete its work of hearing witnesses,” (civil society, ST1) declared.

“Hundreds of thousands of victims were waiting to be heard,” said ST1, who specified that in the department of Daloa (central-west) alone, more than 10,700 people were waiting to be heard by the CDVR when the commission announced the end of the hearing phase for victims of the military-political crisis. “To avoid the feelings of frustration that can arise from failed hearings, we wanted the CDVR to be able to complete its work”

(Civil Society, ST1).

Even if the CDVR excluded many people and organisations from its programme, they organised themselves to carry out personal reconciliation projects. This is the case of the Community reconciliation through the promotion of dialogue and collective action project, an initiative of the Centre for Research and Action for Peace (CERAP), consisting of meeting leaders (community, religious, etc.) to identify young people of all political and religious affiliations likely to play a positive role in restoring peace in each locality. According to the Civil Society HR3, personalised and collective listening sessions were organised. The young people chosen followed a training seminar on issues of citizenship, peaceful conflict management, tolerance (ethnic, political, and religious), etc. Then, everyone was invited to propose joint action projects likely to recreate communication, the desire, and the pleasure of living together (Civil Society, HR3).

CDVR events: challenges to inclusion

The hearings of victims, survivors, and perpetrators of violence as well as the public hearings were the main events through which the members of the CDVR sought to bring the truth to light. The hearings were carried out by members of NGOs and local commissions. The composition of these encountered difficulties as some local notables did not have the literary skills to carry out the work and others were considered biased. Survivors and victims of the violence of the Ivorian crises were not motivated and encouraged to attend national and community events by the CDVR, even though their participation was necessary to “help free minds and pave the way for reconciliation” (Governance, PM2). During the events, several survivors and victims of violence did not have the opportunity to share their stories, experiences, and memories of the Ivorian crises. One of the obstacles to wider participation of survivors and victims of violence in CDVR events was limited knowledge of victims and

perpetrators of violence and limited awareness of the existence of the reconciliation commission and its processes (Governance, PM2). “The Ivorian commission was supposed to research the causes of the various crises, seek the truth, hold hearings, and write a report. What it did in two years, it should have done in the first six months after its creation,” declared a member of civil society (Civil Society, HR3). In addition to the CDVR's low level of outreach to survivors and victims of violence, other issues prevented the full participation of victims and perpetrators of violence. Commissioner CD1 says the Commission's \$15 million budget was insufficient for the CDVR to cover travel and accommodation costs for all survivors wishing to participate in national events (Commissioner, CD1). The issue of casualty, survivor and casualty logistics was first raised before the first national event was held. Many survivors and victims of violence indicated that they “could not afford to attend hearings due to the costs of transportation and accommodation” (Commissioner, CD1). Furthermore, according to a member of civil society, the budget was not used effectively.

“They had the budget. How many trips abroad have commission officials made? The budget was tight, but they could have made better use of it”. (Civil Society, HR4).

Banny, president of the CDVR, was prime minister under the presidency of Gbagbo and advisor to Ouattara during the 2010 presidential campaign. He would exercise a certain influence on the work of the commission. According to Civil Society PP4, the presidency of the commission should not have been occupied by someone with political ambitions (Civil Society PP4). To reinforce what Civil Society PP4 said, Civil Society, HR4 added that

“The commission suffered from a serious problem of dysfunction. Everything is centralised around President Banny, who sought to extend his political influence through the institution. Banny used the commission to promote his own political ambition”

(Civil Society, HR4).

Other members of civil society interviewed drew attention to the fact that the commission was established without broad consultation or participation of civil society groups and victims and that it carried out its work without collaborating with organisations of civil society. Commissioner CD2, however, rejected this accusation.

Despite the promise of Ouattara, head of state and government, to support fair and impartial justice, only Gbagbo sympathisers were indicted until 2024 by the Ivorian justice system. This unjust and biased justice did not encourage broad participation of victims and survivors in national events (Civil Society, HR1). The release of Gbagbo by international justice and his return to the country were judged by many observers as a necessary step towards reconciliation.

CDVR events: perpetrators and exclusion

Violent conflicts involve a wide range of aggressors: men and women, state and non-state actors, local and foreign individuals and organisations, senior officers, and soldiers. Ideally, processes aimed at reconciliation should involve them all. In practice, many will remain beyond the reach of initiatives for healing, truth-telling, justice, and reparation. Abusers may be unknown, on the run, or simply reluctant to participate in reconciliation activities. The participation of perpetrators of violence is one of the key elements of restorative justice and the reconciliation process. However, Commissioner CD1, estimated that the CDVR would encounter difficulties if the attackers were included in the commission and in the process. Commissioner CD1 insists that their participation in the CDVR processes would be an inevitable obstacle to the work of the CDVR (Commissioner, CD1). However, this obstacle is not represented by the legal framework within the TRC operates. According to Commissioner CD1, the exclusion of the attackers was voluntary. Civil Society PP1 is not of the same opinion as the commissioner of the CDVR. Civil Society PP1 believes that if the aggressors were included in the negotiations in Marcoussis, Kléber, Togo, Accra, Pretoria, and Burkina Faso, it would be important to include them in the reconciliation process in Côte d'Ivoire (Civil Society, PP1).

Criterion 3 (CR-3): Focus on the victim and Empowerment in the CDVR's Context

Restorative justice is a process that encourages offenders to accept the consequences of their actions and repair the harm or damage caused by a crime. According to Braithwaite, "victim empowerment is particularly important in cases where the victim experiences structurally systematic domination and can lead to a greater degree of survivor control over justice processes" (2003, p. 87). In the case of the Ivorian crises, survivors were disadvantaged and powerless. Important steps must therefore be taken to restore the balance of power between survivors and perpetrators

of crises. For this to be possible, there must be an assessment of the needs of victims, which is called “victim-centred” in the language of restorative justice and transitional justice. In the context of restorative justice, empowerment could also be understood in another, more macro sense.

CDVR events: empowerment

To assess CDVR’s ability to empower survivors, the study examined the national event hosted by CDVR. Specifically, the study focused on hearings, during which survivors were able to express their stories of experiences during the crises. These hearings are chaired by a CDVR commissioner, who facilitates the process of survivors revealing the truth. CDVR's mandate includes the language of survivor empowerment. According to a national reporter, during the hearing, Survivor empowerment was evident in the presence of survivors' families and friends (Civil Society, ME1). The journalist deplored the low participation of victims in this event (Civil Society, ME1).

Also, community empowerment strategies are needed to enable survivors to cope with the trauma of crises, whether they participate in CDVR (Civil Society, DR1) events. According to Governance, GM1, in 2017, the Ivorian State through the National Social Cohesion Programme (PNCS), placed under the supervision of her ministry, made available to victims of the Ivorian crises, an amount of 2,000 dollars under the form of refundable credit. An individual can request up to \$1,000, while the ceiling for a group or association of victims is set at one million CFA francs (Governance, GM1). The loan received without amendment is repayable within eighteen months, including six months deferred. The objective of this project is to help victims, although having received compensation, to carry out income-generating activities to get them out of precariousness and poverty (Governance, GM1). This programme aims to facilitate the socio-economic integration and reintegration of victims of the various crises that have occurred in Côte d'Ivoire, to improve their living conditions. In total, 110 people benefited from the AGR loan during the period 2017 to 2021. From 2021 to date, 132 new beneficiaries have used this loan (Governance, GM1). Although the Ministry of Health took care of some of the victims and the PNCS granted them a loan, the president of the victims' collective estimates that the number of victims who benefited from this aid is only worth one hundredth of the victims (Civil Society, VR1).

Criterion 4 (CR-4): CDVR and the search for truth

One of the elements that the truth commission emphasises is the need to discover the truth about the past. Knowing the truth about the past can lead to a path of solution and healing. The mandate of the truth commission refers to the healing. Niezen (2017) highlights the importance of telling stories about experiences of war. According to the author, the stories of survivors' respect and honour them (Niezen, 2017). In Côte d'Ivoire, the opportunity for survivors to tell the truth and share their stories within the CDVR mainly arises during public hearings organized by the commission. Only three weeks of hearing were enough for the CDVR to report, through the victims' stories, ten years of violence in Côte d'Ivoire. According to Civil Society VR1, the results of the public hearings are catastrophic.

“We regret to note that the CDVR, contrary to its fundamentals, has succeeded in accentuating the traumatic state of the victims. Which leads us to affirm loudly and clearly that the Truth Dialogue and Reconciliation Commission has failed in its mission”

(Civil Society, VR1).

This interviewee underlines that he asked the CDVR to act alongside the victims to find a solution to the harmful social situation, their critical state of health and the situation of non-schooling of orphans of the crisis. Civil Society VR1, insists that he asked the CDVR to find a solution to their concerns, a solution which could possibly predispose them to eventually meeting their executioners or perhaps granting them pardon (Civil Society, VR1). Indeed, according to the report of the United Nations Peacebuilding Fund (PBF, 2014), the CDVR led the search for the truth by collecting the statements of 72,843 victims in listening centres in 2014. Public hearings on 80 emblematic cases were organised, and the victims were able to benefit from effective protection (PBF, 2014). According to Civil Society VR1, this is not enough.

“We, at the CVCI, already have nearly 2,800 victims. I believe that there are only three or four that were heard by the CDVR during this public hearing. These 80 victims cannot translate into reality the concerns of the 70,000 victims”

(Civil Society, VR1).

Civil Society PP1, claims not to know the criteria on which the CDVR chose the victims.

“What we know, and we say it clearly, is that the CDVR has worked in the service of national and international opinion. It is this imposture of reconciliation that we denounced”

(Civil Society, PP1).

Civil Society VR1 says that a victim's experience during the CDVR hearing was very positive. For him, telling the truth has healing power. This victim was able to recount his ordeal in Bouake, the headquarters of the 2002 rebellion. Civil Society VR1 wonders why the hearings are not extended to all victims (Civil Society, VR1).

6.2.3 Final Report Recommendations: Restoring social ties

This section evaluates the CDVR after the final report, considering the recommendations using five (5) criteria. Criterion 5 (CR-5) made it possible to assess the recognition of the identity of the victims and the overcoming of the denial of injustice. Criterion 6 (CR-6) made it possible to assess the restoration of the dignity of survivors and criterion 7 (CR-7) made it possible to assess the flexibility of reparations programs.

Criterion 5 (CR-5): Overcoming denials of injustice and victim identities

The 2005 Fundamental Principles and Guidelines on the Right to Remedy and Reparation for Victims specify that victim status must be recognised, “whether or not the perpetrator of the violation is identified, arrested, prosecuted, convicted” (page 6). This clarification is very important in a context of massive violations of human rights and international humanitarian law. Concerning the identification of the perpetrator of the crime, we cannot imagine that a victim, for example of a rape, could be stripped of their victim status due to lack of identification, arrest, or conviction of their victim(s). executioners. Should a relative who has found the body of a family member in the forest or on the side of a road, riddled with bullets, first carry out investigations to identify the torturers before being recognised as a victim? How can we recognise torturers during a night-time attack or when they advance with their faces masked? It is obvious that in most violations it is difficult, if not impossible, for the victims or even for the state authorities to identify the perpetrators of these serious violations. As crises

or conflicts take place over a long period of time, investigations are often carried out several years after the violations, which considerably reduces the hopes of finding the perpetrators of the offenses. Therefore, making the identification, arrest, prosecution, and conviction of the perpetrator of the violation a condition before recognizing the victim as such, would have been very detrimental and would have inexorably moved away from this status and the right to reparation, of many victims. Finally, “the 2005 principles” proclaim the recognition of victim status regardless of the relationship that exists between him [the executioner] and the victim (Redress, 2006). The case of child soldiers is a perfect illustration of the relationship that can exist between a victim and their executioner. Very often, these children are forced to coldly murder members of their own family to kill any feeling of pity in them towards their next victims (Amnesty International, 2012). In addition to child soldiers, fathers are also forced to rape their own daughters or sons are forced to rape their mothers or sisters (Moufflet, 2008). These practices aim to inflict great humiliation to psychologically destroy the families of the opposing camp. It is entirely logical that the victims of these torturers for a few moments are recognised as such, despite the family ties that unite them to their direct torturers (Moufflet, 2008). These people who acted under threat to save their lives must themselves be considered victims, the real culprits being those who forced them to commit these despicable acts. It is in this context that the ICC considers child soldiers as victims of war (ICC, 2009). According to the former prosecutor of the Special Court for Sierra Leone (SCSL), CRANE: A child soldier and his victim are both victims, because they are usually placed in these situations beyond their control in armed conflicts (Akakpo, 2012). In the Ivorian crises, child soldiers were recruited by the MPCl rebels in 2002, as well as by the invisible commando in 2010, mainly to play the roles of porters or lookouts. Since children were not considered combatants, they were not considered in the Disarmament, Demobilisation and Reintegration (DDR) program and transformed into real bloodthirsty killers, not hesitating to savagely kill within the population. Several of them were lynched by the population in reprisal. These children are just the product of war, and they have become extremely violent. They have no respect for human life for having witnessed heinous crimes alongside the fighters. These children, pejoratively described as minors in conflict with the law, must be considered as victims of war and solutions must be taken for their reintegration into society. As Côte d'Ivoire has not adopted in its legislation a specific definition of victims of violations of human rights and international humanitarian law,

the government asked us to use international law to determine the status of victims (Civil Society, DR1).

“During a meeting with victims and their relatives in Abobo on April 11, 2015, President Alassane Ouattara expressed his commitment to not leaving any victim or loved one behind, emphasizing that this aims to ensure fair and equitable compensation for everyone.”

(Civil Society, DR1).

Recognition of victim status is very important because it appears to be the sine qua non condition for access to the rights and/or benefits linked to this status. It is because the status of victim is recognised that the person will have the right to assert their case, to be heard or to obtain reparation (Civil Society, DR1). Determining the status of victims is very complex and it is difficult to list all victims in a practical manner. In Côte d'Ivoire, the absence of a law explicitly indicating the categories of people to be considered in the transitional justice process further complicates their recognition and reparations. Indeed, the categorisation of victims by texts makes it possible to provide States and the organisations concerned with an important basis for determining within the population, those people who are entitled to victim status and those who cannot claim it. This categorisation is essential to implement an effective repair system. But this textual recognition of victims' rights is not enough.

Criterion 6 (CR-6): Restoring Survivors' Dignity

Human dignity, as a foundational principle of human existence, embodies the intrinsic worth and equal moral status of all individuals. It is not conferred by society, the state, or any external authority, but rather arises from the mere fact of being human. Philosophically, Immanuel Kant (1996) provides one of the most enduring articulations of human dignity, asserting that it stems from humanity's rational nature and capacity for autonomous moral action. According to Kant, a person must always be treated as an end in themselves and never merely to an end, underscoring the absolute and non-negotiable value of human beings.

This notion of dignity as inherent and inalienable has been echoed and institutionalized in modern legal frameworks. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (United

Nations, 1948) begins by affirming that “all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights,” positioning dignity as the normative cornerstone of international human rights law. From this perspective, human dignity becomes the moral and legal bedrock upon which civil, political, economic, and social rights are constructed.

Moreover, contemporary scholars such as Fiat (2012) extend Kantian thought by emphasizing that to speak of human dignity is to acknowledge an absolute, intrinsic, and inviolable value that cannot be lost, traded, or diminished, even in the face of adversity or legal compromise. This understanding not only prohibits degrading treatment or exploitation but also calls for proactive protection and recognition of each person’s agency and voice within social, legal, and political structures.

In transitional justice contexts, such as post-conflict Côte d’Ivoire, human dignity plays a pivotal role in shaping reparative processes, truth-seeking mechanisms, and collective healing. It demands that victims be recognized not only as passive recipients of justice but as subjects whose suffering and humanity must be acknowledged, respected, and restored.

In the Ivorian context, the principle of human dignity assumes both a philosophical and a socio-political urgency in the aftermath of the violent post-electoral crisis of 2010–2011. During this period, thousands of Ivorians were subjected to serious human rights violations (massacres, arbitrary detentions, sexual violence, forced displacements) resulting not only in physical and material harm but in profound assaults on their dignity. In this landscape, human dignity is not an abstract moral claim but a lived experience that demands recognition, justice, and restoration.

The CDVR, established in 2011, was conceived as a mechanism to help rebuild the fractured national conscience. However, it has been widely criticized for its limited engagement with victims and its lack of tangible outcomes (ICTJ, 2015). In its early years, the CDVR struggled to operationalize a framework that recognized the full human dignity of victims. Testimonies were selectively gathered, reparations mechanisms remained vague, and political pressures diluted its independence. For many, this signalled a failure to truly “see” the victim, not only as a bearer of trauma but as a moral agent deserving of truth, recognition, and participation.

Human dignity in this transitional justice context must be understood as both relational and restorative. It is relational in that it recognizes the victim not merely as a number or statistic, but as a person whose suffering matters within the collective narrative of the nation. It is restorative in that it demands more than symbolic gestures; it requires institutional and societal action to affirm that what was done was wrong, that the victim matters, and that their status as a full human being is upheld. Fiat (2012) reinforces this idea, stating that to speak of the dignity of a man is to grant him an absolute, inalienable, intrinsic value, a concept that transitional justice mechanisms must embody if they are to be meaningful.

Furthermore, in many Ivorian communities, traditional values of dignity (wallow in Dida, for instance) are deeply tied to notions of respect, community inclusion, and collective healing. Thus, efforts to restore dignity must not only be legal or institutional but also cultural and communal. In that sense, failing to give victims a voice or excluding them from national narratives of reconciliation perpetuates the very indignities the CDVR was meant to redress.

Ultimately, in Côte d'Ivoire's post-conflict setting, human dignity must serve as a normative compass guiding both state institutions and civil society towards justice that is not only procedural but profoundly human.

Violations of the right to life in the Ivorian conflicts

The right to life is undoubtedly an essential prerequisite for the realisation of all other fundamental human rights. The European Court of Human Rights has repeatedly recalled in several case law its "supreme value on the scale of human rights at international level" (ECHR, 2001; 2011). It is the responsibility of state authorities to ensure the protection and respect of human rights. In the Barcelona Traction case, the International Court of Justice (ICJ) ruled that this was an "erga Omnes obligation" which is binding on all States without exception (ICJ, 1970). On the question of the Ivorian crisis, there are numerous reports. National and international reports including the reports of the CNE (Gouv, 2012) and the CDVR (Gouv, 2012), several national and international NGOs defending human rights. All these reports lead to the same conclusion: the commission of serious human rights violations by the various protagonists. The most serious human rights violations concern fundamental rights,

such as the right to life and the right to physical integrity and security of the human person. In Côte d'Ivoire, a National Commission of Inquiry (CNE) was created by the President of the Republic, Alassane Ouattara, on July 20, 2011. The role assigned to this Commission was to conduct non-judicial investigations to determine violations human rights and international humanitarian law perpetrated throughout the national territory. The temporal jurisdiction of this Commission covered the post-electoral period beginning on October 31, 2010, and ending on May 15, 2011, inclusive. Several NGOs in Côte d'Ivoire such as Human Right Watch (HRW), Amnesty International, the Ivorian League for Human Rights (LIDHO), the Ivorian Movement for Human Rights (MIDH), Action for Protection of (APDH), the Grouping of Ivorian Human Rights Actors (RAIDH) were thus able to collect numerous testimonies from victims of the post-electoral crisis. The precision of these testimonies and the verification of the information, often based on the observation of the after-effects still visible on the bodies of the witnesses, made it possible to clearly determine the nature of all the violations committed during this period, the places, the dates, the accomplices, and alleged perpetrators. As examples of the very detailed and rich nature of the victims' testimonies, two testimonies among thousands existing, collected by Amnesty International and the RAIDH. The first testimony implicates elements of the Security Operations Command Centre (CECOS), an elite body of the Defence and Security Forces (FDS), (HRW report, 2011). The second testimony points to human rights violations by the Republican Forces of Côte d'Ivoire (FRCI) and the Dozos (traditional Malinké hunters), the armed forces. Indeed, on Monday March 28, 2011, the FRCI with the support of the Dozos carried out a deadly intervention in the capital Guémon (Duekoue). Several villages were ransacked, and the houses burned to the ground (RAIDH report, 2011). From December 2010 to April 2011, young people will set up anarchic roadblocks at the entrances and exits of their neighbourhood to ensure their safety against surprise attacks from the invisible commando. The psychosis of the potential enemy will push these young people to commit despicable killings in front of everyone. Several people will thus be arrested based on their appearance, their clothing habits, their language, their religious regalia, or even their identity document bearing a Malinke-sounding name or nationality of countries in the sub-region. Note that the Ivorian authorities had clearly accused countries like Burkina Faso of complicity with the former rebels. From there the hatred against the nationals of these States was manifest. According to the report of the National Commission of Inquiry

(CNE), violations of the right to life were most significant in the economic capital: Abidjan in the south (1,497 deaths), followed by the west of the country with the regions by Guémon. (Capital: Duekoue with 385 deaths) and Cavally (capital: Bolequin with 289 deaths).

Apart from these three regions, five other regions recorded more than a hundred losses of human life. These are the regions of Gbôkle (capital: Sassandra in the south with 182 deaths), Tonkpi (capital: Man in the west with 180 deaths), Nawa (capital: Soubré in the southwest with 146 deaths), San-Pedro (125 deaths) and Grands Ponts (capital: Dabou, not far from Abidjan with 101 deaths). In total: 3,248 cases of violations of the right to life were recorded by the CNE throughout the Ivorian territory during the post-electoral crisis. These violations are classified by the CNE into four categories: summary executions (2,241 cases), injuries resulting in death (705 cases), torture or ill-treatment resulting in death (296 cases) and deaths during illegal detention. (6 cases). The Human Rights Council, through its resolution 16/25, mandated an international commission of inquiry in Côte d'Ivoire from May 4 to 28, 2011. The mission assigned to this Commission was to investigate the facts and circumstances surrounding the allegations of serious human rights violations perpetrated in Côte d'Ivoire following the presidential election of November 28, 2010, with a view to identifying those responsible for these acts and bring them to justice (HRC, 2011).

The CNE, for its part, has identified twelve types of offenses in this article. These are: torture and ill-treatment (1,354 cases), rape or other sexual assault (196 cases), cruel, inhuman, and degrading treatment (1,135 cases), inhumane conditions of detention (34 cases), detention for political reasons with or without an arrest warrant (112 cases) and other arbitrary or illegal detentions (360 cases). Next come kidnappings (460 cases), forced disappearances (265 cases), kidnappings (391 cases), death threats (2108 cases), illegal searches (549 cases), injuries (1477 cases). In total, 8,441 cases of violations were recorded relating to the right to physical integrity and the right to security of the person. In this second category of serious human rights violations, the South and West of Côte d'Ivoire are the regions which record the most victims. The CNE recorded 3,474 cases in the city of Abidjan, in the Cavally region whose capital is Guiglo 594 cases, in the Guémon region whose capital is Duekoue 527 cases, in

the Nawa region whose capital is San-Pedro 550 cases, in the region of Agneby Tiassa, whose capital is Agboville 501 cases, in the region of Tonkpi, whose capital is Man 386 cases, in the region of Me, whose capital is Adzopé 411 cases, in the Haut-Sassandra region whose capital is Daloa 363 cases and in the Gôh region whose capital is Gagnoa 310 cases. The consistency between the multiple testimonies collected by the various reports from international and national organisations demonstrate without doubt that numerous serious human rights violations were committed on Ivorian territory during the post-electoral period, both by pro-GBAGBO and by pro-GBAGBO. Alassane Forces. Moreover, the non-judicial investigation carried out by the CNE confirms this observation by the NGOs with “1,452 cases of violations of the right to life attributed to pro-GBAGBO forces and 727 cases to the FRCI” (CNE, 2012). Côte d’Ivoire should accept its legal responsibility and apologize unreservedly, in a manner acceptable to most victims. In this regard, the country should restore the dignity of the victims, prosecute those responsible who are still alive, take immediate legislative and administrative measures to adequately compensate the survivors, educate students and the public on this issue and sanction any attempt to defame the victims. Victims or denying the events in question. Some respondents confirmed that Côte d'Ivoire has never presented an official apology to the victims and believe that the State has never recognized its responsibility in the Ivorian crises (Civil Society PP1, Civil Society PP3, Society Civil VR1). In the following paragraph, evidence shows that the State of Côte d'Ivoire did not restore the dignity of the victims through compensation.

Criterion 7 (CR-7): Flexibility of the reparations programme:

The victims' right to reparation is implemented in Côte d'Ivoire through the creation of several structures (CDVR, 2014)). However, many difficulties hinder the success of this process. Several institutions were created by the Ivorian Government to lead the different phases of the reparation process for victims of the Ivorian crises without conclusive results. Among these institutions, CONARIV played a central role, but with a very contested record. One of the organizations set up by the government to take care of victims of wars in Côte d'Ivoire was the Directorate of War Victims (DVG). This was the second major directorate of the Ministry of Veterans and War Victims, created in 2011. The DVG was responsible for designing and implementing the government's reparations policy. Concretely, its role was to identify the victims and determine an

adequate method of reparation. Furthermore, the DVG was responsible for carrying out awareness campaigns on the disadvantages of war among populations with the support of civil society organizations and victims' associations. The DVG actively exercised its activities until November 2012, before experiencing a major halt with the dissolution of the Ministry of Veterans and War Victims. The organisation was finally reinstated after eight months of inactivity at the Ministry of Solidarity in August 2013. The DVG carried out a census of 71,813 victims, the list of which was transmitted to CONARIV in April 2015 (DGV, 2018). Another important body created by the state was the CDVR. This organization benefits from the status of an independent administrative authority, with legal personality and financial autonomy. Its mandate was to seek out the root causes and shed light on the post-election crisis and the various past deadly crises. This research should lead to proposals and recommendations to promote reconciliation and strengthen social cohesion between all populations living in Côte d'Ivoire. On December 15, 2014, the CDVR officially submitted its final report to the President of the Republic, Alassane Ouattara. The CDVR results were mixed and controversial.

Another state structure, the National Commission of Inquiry (CNE) created by presidential decree No. 2011-176 of July 20, 2011, to shed light on the post-electoral violence of 2010-2011. Chaired by the High Magistrate, Ms. Paulette Badjo, the CNE was an independent body, but placed under the authority of the Ministry of Human Rights. Its mission was to conduct non-judicial investigations into violations of human rights and international humanitarian law that occurred in Côte d'Ivoire from the end of October 2010 to May 2011. The CNE carried out its investigations in all regions of Côte d'Ivoire and was able to interview 15,875 people including 13,344 victims in exactly 112 localities. The CNE completed its field investigations in March 2012 and submitted its final report to the President of the Republic on August 8, 2012. The greatest interest of the CNE report lies in the fact that it is the first report of a national body to have also incriminated the supporters of the presidential camp as perpetrators of human rights violations and not only the forces of the ousted president. This impartiality in its investigations has been praised by national and international human rights organizations. On March 24, 2015, the President of the Republic signed Ordinance No. 2015-174 establishing the creation, responsibilities, composition, and operation of CONARIV. Its mission is "to complete the work of the CDVR and to

compensate the victims of the crises that occurred in Côte d'Ivoire" (Frat Mat, 2015). The same decree names Mgr. Paul Simeon Ahouana, 3rd vice-president of the former CDVR, metropolitan archbishop of Bouake, as president of CONARIV.

The establishment of this new Commission represented a real glimmer of hope for the victims of the crises that occurred in Côte d'Ivoire, to obtain compensation for the damage they suffered. On December 15, 2014, during the presentation of the final report of the ex-CDVR, President Alassane Ouattara had already announced the creation in 2015 of a fund with an initial contribution of 10 billion FCFA to compensate the victims. For HR3 member of the Civil Society Convention of Côte d'Ivoire: "It was a relief after several years of waiting, and it was the hope of reparation after serious harm suffered by a population that had left" (Civil Society, HR3). The interviewee continues by affirming that: "CONARIV can contribute to the recognition of the victim's rights to justice, reparations and the guarantee of non-liability" (Civil Society, HR3). Concerning the compensation fund, the decree designates another body which is responsible for the effective execution of compensation and social cohesion, namely the National Social Cohesion Program (PNCS). According to Commissioner CO1, "Reconciliation is vital for any nation that has experienced crises like ours, compensating victims is above all an act of humanity and solidarity" (Commissioner, CO1). Compensation is an element of the right to reparation recognised for victims of violations of human rights and international humanitarian law. This right is one of the four fundamental pillars of transitional justice. However, CONARIV's mission has been subject to numerous challenges. Firstly, the first challenge, for Commissioner CO1, was to be accepted by all actors in civil and political society. Indeed, the method of designation of the latter, namely his appointment by President Alassane Ouattara without any consultation, as was the case for the president of the ex-CDVR, failed in greatly discrediting him as had been its predecessor (Civil Society, VR1). The Catholic Church of Côte d'Ivoire from which he comes took a position on his appointment by dissociating itself from him in a solemn declaration: "The archbishops of Côte d'Ivoire wish to inform the members of the clergy, religious men and women and the faithful lay people that they have not been associated either directly or indirectly by their confrere in this commitment. This is why, in the spirit of canon 285 of the Code of Canon Law of 1983, they wish to clarify that they are not responsible for the acts that he will perform in the exercise of his new office at the head of CONARIV" (Civil Society,

PP4). Then, the second major challenge for CONARIV was the consolidation of the lists of victims of the crises in Côte d'Ivoire. Indeed, several NGOs, victims' associations, structures, or Ministries of State each had their list of victims and CONARIV gave itself a period of 3 months, until June 30, 2015, to cross-check all these lists to obtain a single national list of victims, which will be validated by the President of the Republic before compensation is possible. Civil Society VR1 estimates that the CDVR had counted 72,000 victims, the victims' associations presented 130,000 (Civil Society, VR1). It is in this sense that a member of the PNCS who ensured the effective payment of compensation to victims admits that “there is a problem of lists of victims to be approved. So, we must harmonise all of that. Then, a definition of victim status is necessary before truly setting up the victim care mechanism” (Civil Society, PN1).

A highly contested record

Real hope for the victims was forged around the creation of CONARIV even if it had to face many challenges to fully accomplish its mission. Faced with the large number of victims and the lack of financial means to satisfy all these people, CONARIV had to establish priorities by focusing first on the people most affected.

“CONARIV completed its mission with a very contested assessment due on the one hand to the lack of transparency in its work carried out and on the other hand to the questionable reasons for the rejection of numerous victim compensation files”

(Civil Society, PP6).

CONARIV's mission was to complement the work of the CDVR by researching, identifying, and registering victims and the rights holders of victims not yet registered. It was also up to CONARIV to compile all the lists of victims held by state and non-state organisations, including victims' associations, to arrive, after verification, at the establishment of a single consolidated file. It is from this single file that compensation should be carried out for the victims and the victims' beneficiaries. For the identification of the victims, Civil Society VR1 stated:

“We are all victims, but not all victims are equal. We must accept this reality and reach out to the most vulnerable among us. Considering this priority to be given to the most vulnerable, the work of CONARIV was divided into two main stages: the first stage relating to the creation of the single consolidated file of victims and victims' beneficiaries. As for the second stage, it concerned the compensation of the victims and possibly the restitution of their property”

(Civil Society, DR1).

To date, the CONARIV report has not yet been made public by the authorities. How can we explain this lack of transparency? Does the government have things to hide?

“We therefore rely on the summary provided by the President of the CDVR during the official ceremony for submitting the report to the President of the Republic in April 2016. He stated that CONARIV received 874,055 files during the first stage, of which 316,954 were deemed admissible and validated, while 557,101 were rejected. Among the validated files, approximately 48,240 victims of physical violence (15%) were identified, including cases of injuries, sexual violence, disappearances, and deaths. The largest number of victims, around 268,714, represents cases of material damage (85%).”

(Civil Society, DR1).

How can we explain so many refusals of victims' compensation requests? 64% of claims were refused for various reasons, compared to only 36% of claims accepted. The main reasons for rejection of numerous files by CONARIV are grouped into five points: the existence of duplicates (38.9%), files without supporting documents (36.5%), cases of fraud (12.3%), cases of unreachable victims or witnesses. (10.2%) and incorrectly completed or unusable forms (2.1%) (Civil Society, DR1). Firstly, regarding cases of duplicates, these are certain victims who have registered several times with the same structure or with different state or non-state organisations. These duplicate cases represent the largest number of reasons for rejection. The multiple registrations of victims with different structures can be explained by the fact that a multitude of structures began to draw up lists of victims during the Ivorian crises and as soon as they ended. According to Commissioner CO2, a total of 33 structures submitted lists of victims to CONARIV (Commissioner, CO2). Victims, fearing that their

registration with an organization might not be recognized by the authorities in charge of compensation, chose to act cautiously by registering with multiple structures. Furthermore, the summary of the CONARIV report revealed that 203,342 requests were rejected due to the absence of supporting documents. This reason was the most common basis for the dismissal of victim cases (Commissioner, CO2).

This testimony from a victim from the locality of Duekoue collected by Civil Society, VR1 is quite edifying:

“When CONARIV called the victim, she was asked to send the death certificate of her husband. She stated that she went to the sub-prefecture, where she was informed that this document cost 6,000 FCFA [about 9 euros]. Then, she also had to pay 35,000 FCFA [about 54 euros] to the Guiglo court and appear at a hearing with three witnesses. Additionally, the victim had to cover the transportation costs for the witnesses from Yrouzon to Guiglo to confirm the death of her husband, which amounted to 28,000 FCFA [about 43 euros], not including food and other expenses. In total, this cost her 80,000 FCFA [about 122 euros]. The victim wondered where she was going to find this money to cover all these charges. Unfortunately, she could not prove the death of her husband due to a lack of financial means, and she was not compensated.”

(Civil Society, VR1).

The inadequacy of the forms of reparation adopted by the Ivorian authorities.

Côte d'Ivoire has retained three types of reparation for victims, namely individual reparations (natural or legal persons), community reparations (collective) and symbolic reparations (forgiveness) (Commissioner, PN1). Concerning individual compensation, the commissioner specified that 4,500 people including 3,500 dead and 1,000 injured were considered. Per deceased person, the beneficiaries received the sum of one million FCFA [1,500 euros] and the injured, care vouchers of 150,000 FCFA [230 euros] (Commissioner, PN1). As collective reparations, these consist of the construction and rehabilitation of basic socio-economic infrastructure (health, access to drinking water) and the financing of socio-economic projects in favour of communities, in areas which were greatly affected. These areas are mainly the city of Abidjan and its surroundings, the South-West, the West (Nahibly, Duekoue, Bangolo),

the Centre (Sakassou) and the North (Commissioner, PN1). According to Governance GM2, all these Government actions pursue a clear objective, that of helping “victims to overcome their pain, to silence resentment, to relearn how to live together and to regain cohesion social and peace” (Governance, GM2). Fully financed by the Ivorian state, the initial budget for individual reparations is allocated 20 billion FCFA and is supposed to increase by 10 billion FCFA each year. As for the funds intended to finance collective reparations, they are constituted by the State of Côte d'Ivoire, the UNDP, and NGOs (Governance, GM2). The implementation of reparation measures in favour of victims sometimes imposes difficult choices on States. The satisfaction of all victims is utopian given the large number of victims compared to the very limited means of a State emerging from an armed conflict. For the Secretary General of the United Nations: Difficult decisions must be made, in particular as to who will be among the victims to be compensated, the amount of reparations, the types of damage which will be covered, the terms of compensation quantifying the damage and the criteria to be used to compare and compensate different types of damage and award reparations (UN, 2004). The National Program of the International Centre for Transitional Justice in Côte d'Ivoire (ICJJ) has identified four fundamental pillars to enable a reparations process capable of responding to the serious violations committed in the country. These recommendations are the result of several years of consultation and work with victims' associations, civil society organisations and government structures in Côte d'Ivoire. These four principles are: 1) Prioritise serious violations, 2) Prioritise individuals as victims, 3) Implement reparations programmes that address the consequences of such violations and go beyond 'simple compensation, and 4) develop a clear implementation plan that allows definition of priorities, a budget, and a schedule (ICTJ, 2016). In the implementation of the reparation programmes in Côte d'Ivoire, the third fundamental pillar of the ICTJ's proposals is seriously undermined. According to Civil Society VR1, compensation was almost the only one chosen by the Ivorian authorities to the detriment of the four others, namely restitution, rehabilitation, satisfaction and guarantees of non-repetition of violations (Civil Society, VR1).

The case of *Kepa Urra Guridi v. Spain* (UN, 2005) can be interpreted as a critique on the lack or few programmes of reparation. The Committee against Torture considered irrelevant the Spanish State's argument that there had been no violation since the complainant had received the full compensation (half a million pesetas, i.e.

approximately 3,005 euros) ordered by the judges of first instance. The Committee found a violation of the State's obligation to provide "adequate reparation" in the absence of other remedial measures other than compensation. For the Committee:

"...reparation must cover all the damage suffered by the victim and include, among other measures, restitution, compensation, rehabilitation of the victim as well as measures aimed at guaranteeing the non-repetition of violations".

(UN, 2005 IX-20)

Thus, compensation alone for Ivorian victims is insufficient and should in no case be considered as an act erasing the violations suffered. The reparations process in Côte d'Ivoire has been marred by numerous irregularities which give rise to a general feeling of disappointment among most victims. We can cite among others: the non-participation of these, their long wait, the non-publication of the list of victims, the exclusion of the main victims.

6.3 Complex victimization in the context of national reconciliation

To illustrate the diverse perceptions of complex victimization in the context of national reconciliation in Côte d'Ivoire, individuals were interviewed. These testimonies reflect the complexity of responsibilities and suffering, shedding light on the challenges of achieving lasting national reconciliation. Each of these voices contributes to a collective reflection on how to heal the wounds of the past.

The political leader (Civil Society PP6) emphasises the importance of a nuanced reconciliation. Civil Society PP6 advocates for the recognition of shared responsibilities and stresses the need to move forward together without nurturing past grudges. This viewpoint focuses on collective healing by integrating different forms of suffering.

"Everyone has their share of suffering and sometimes responsibility. Freezing roles fuels grudges and hinders healing. Even among those who took up arms, many did so under pressure. We must move forward together with this reality"

(Civil Society PP).

The human right defender (civil society HR4) criticizes the lack of recognition of complex victimization in dominant narratives. Civil Society HR4 highlights that the frustration caused by the absence of justice can turn victims into perpetrators of violence and emphasizes the importance of going beyond a simplistic view of good and evil for a fairer reconciliation. “Many victims have, through frustration, become actors of violence. To avoid revenge, we must move beyond the manicheanism and understand why some victims become perpetrators” (Civil Society, HR).

Civil Society VR1, citing the words of a former combatant, expresses the duality experienced by those who were forced to take up arms to survive. The testimony of this former combatant relayed by Civil Society VR1 illustrates the difficulty of clearly positioning oneself as either a victim or a perpetrator. According to Civil Society VR1, the victim advocates for the acceptance of contradictions in the process of reconstruction and reconciliation. 'The victim says that they grew up with war. At one point, the victim says they chose between fleeing or fighting. The victim says they regret their actions. The victim says they primarily consider themselves a victim, even if some view them as criminals. The truth is that they are both (Civil Society VR1).

A jurist (Civil Society JU1) speaks about the complexity of the situation on the ground, where the roles of victim and perpetrator often blur. Civil Society JU1 emphasizes the need to accept that everyone, in their own way, has been affected by violence, and that reconciliation depends on this mutual recognition of suffering.

“During the crisis, people were attacked, but some young people also sought revenge. Today, it’s hard to say who started it. What I know is people lost: lives, homes, trust. For peace, they must accept that everyone has been a victim in their own way”

(Civil Society, JU1).

These interviews highlight the diversity of perceptions of complex victimization, revealing how much the reconciliation process in Côte d’Ivoire is marked by contradictions. Each person, depending on their experience, emphasizes the need for collective healing that transcends the fixed roles of victim and perpetrator, focusing instead on understanding the deeper causes of violence and suffering.

6.4 Comparative study of interviews by category

The objective here with this comparative study is to demonstrate the unanimity of personalities and structures external to the CDVR as well as the members of the CDVR on the question of the failure of the Ivorian Truth Commission. In other words, from the leaders of political parties to civil society, through the victims to the members of the CDVR, all recognise and confess that the said commission has no real impact on the Ivorian reconciliation process. Even if CDVR commissioners, notably Commissioner CD1, to ward off the numerous criticisms, use the argument of limited budgetary allocation. Interview evidence shows that both Civil Society PP1 and Civil Society VR1 criticize the CDVR for lack of transparency in its organisation and the appointment of its members. However, the latter are neither from different political sides and were interviewed separately: Civil Society VR1 is an activist and Civil Society PP1 is a political actor. However, they both share the same opinion regarding the appointment of Charles Konan Banny as head of the CDVR by President Alassane Ouattara.

The CDVR's President status as Ouattara's former campaign director raises questions about objectivity and impartiality. The role of the CDVR was to seek evidence about the military-political crisis of 2010. However, as President Ouattara was one of the major actors in this crisis, with Banny as his campaign director, there are conflicts of interest involved. Indeed, there may be incentives to concealment. This is also what civil society actors have criticized, especially Civil Society HR1 who said "the CDVR suffered from a lack of credibility. The selection of its members was not rigorous, and it was not independent" (Civil Society, HR1). Furthermore, this lack of transparency was observed and highlighted by members of the CDVR even if the latter, out of elegance for other reasons, did not use the same terms as HR1. The idea of opacity in the functioning of the CDVR in its functioning can be seen in these remarks:

"The development of its texts and the creation of functional bodies were *only carried out with the named members* of the CDVR while all the parties should be associated. *We have not received the texts in parliament*"

(Governance, MP1).

This testimony indicates that the principle of transparency has not been respected within the CDVR. Governance MP1 was under the direction of supporters of one of the major players in the crisis she was to investigate. While all stakeholders in the crisis, all victims and religious communities should be represented within the said commission, it is political issues that influenced the compositions of the central committee. As Miran-Guyon's report indicates, Banny considered evangelical churches entirely responsible for shaking up the country (Miran-Guyon, 2015). As a result, they did not have a representative on the central committee of the CDVR. Only Muslim and Catholic communities were represented. However, the crisis had also affected evangelical communities, and their victims deserved to have a representative. This would have allowed the guides of these communities to realize the extent of the consequences of their actions or their words. At the end of this, everyone would have contributed to the easing of tensions in Côte d'Ivoire.

Evidence showed that all respondents were unanimous on the lack of transparency within the CDVR, and that not all victims of the crisis were considered in the count and reparations. Indeed, in the opinion of Civil Society PP2 and Civil Society VR1, up to the comments of the members of the CDVR, only one reality emerges. Not all the victims of the post-electoral crisis were considered by the actions of the CDVR. Because according to Civil Society PP2, "Nobody approached my political party to seek its involvement in the creation of the commission." (Civil Society PP2). On the other hand, Civil Society VR1 affirms that not all the victims were considered:

“Not only were the public hearings organised by the CDVR insufficient, but they also resulted in catastrophic outcomes. The CDVR, contrary to its foundational principles, succeeded in exacerbating the trauma of the victims. This leads us to affirm that the Truth and Reconciliation Dialogue Commission has failed in its mission.”

(Civil Society VR1).

Conclusion

Evidence showed that the CDVR methods were not inclusive because not all victims, political actors and civil society were involved. However, other facts such as the insufficiency of the period dedicated to public hearings (3 weeks), the failure to

consider all the declared victims establish the unanimity of political actors, civil society actors and the all the victims on the failure of the CDVR in its mission. The members of the CDVR, although recognising the veracity of all these criticisms, justify this by the insufficiency of the budgetary allocation of the said commission. According to them, “this is the crux of the problem” (Commissioner, CD1). And yet all these criticisms and weaknesses of the CDVR were repeated with CONARIV. Everything therefore suggests that the fundamentals of the CDVR and CONARIV have no support from any political will. So, they could not be highlighted. Because, if the political will was there, these commissions would have been transparent, inclusive, and together the parties would embody the appropriate solutions for progress towards true reconciliation. Each party, faced with the disastrous consequences and in the presence of the victims and the grieving families, would have agreed to the need to pursue reconciliation. Then, all together, they would have exhausted all repair possibilities. Because there is only financial compensation.

CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSION

The research has investigated the function of the Commission for Dialogue, Truth, and Reconciliation (CDVR) in facilitating reconciliation through restorative justice in Côte d'Ivoire. By analysing the commission's framework, methodologies, and results, the study aimed to evaluate its influence on peacebuilding and national unity within a society marked by deep divisions. The results indicate a mix of achievements and limitations, shedding light on the intricate nature of transitional justice in post-conflict environments.

This conclusion encapsulates the principal findings of the research, considering their wider implications for policy, theoretical frameworks, and future studies. It emphasizes the essential role of truth commissions in promoting reconciliation while recognizing the challenges they encounter due to political, institutional, and societal factors. The research asserts that successful reconciliation necessitates a comprehensive strategy that includes truth-telling, reparations, institutional reforms, and ongoing political dedication.

Furthermore, the study enriches the field of transitional justice by providing empirical insights into the CDVR's effects, enhancing theoretical discussions surrounding restorative justice, and suggesting avenues for future research. As Côte d'Ivoire and similar post-conflict countries strive for justice and peace, the insights gained from this study offer important guidance for developing more inclusive and effective reconciliation strategies.

7.1 Transitional Justice in the Ivorian Context: key findings

The creation of the Dialogue, Truth, and Reconciliation Commission (CDVR) in Côte d'Ivoire was a response to the post-electoral violence that occurred between 2010 and 2011, and it is situated within the framework of transitional justice. This approach seeks to confront the remnants of authoritarian rule or violent conflict through four essential components: the pursuit of truth, the accountability of offenders, compensation for victims, and reforms within institutions (Teitel, 2003). In this context, the CDVR aimed to document instances of abuse, restore victims' dignity, and foster national reconciliation. Nevertheless, scholarly evaluations of the process indicate that structural and institutional challenges hinder the effectiveness of this mechanism. The

concluding section of this thesis encapsulates the primary insights derived from the examination of the Ivorian Truth Commission (CDVR) and proposes policy suggestions for future endeavours focused on establishing enduring peace and reconciliation in Côte d'Ivoire and comparable post-conflict environments. This chapter will also consider the study's contributions to the domains of transitional and restorative justice, reflecting on the efficacy, constraints, and lessons gleaned from the CDVR. Additionally, it will explore possible strategies for enhancing the existing reconciliation efforts and offer actionable recommendations for future initiatives.

7.1.1. Truth-seeking efforts were limited

The primary objective of the CDVR was to create a thorough account of the events related to the post-election violence of 2010-2011 through a truth-telling initiative. However, the commission encountered considerable obstacles in fulfilling this objective effectively.

One major issue was the lack of transparency concerning its findings, especially in relation to the final report. While the CDVR gathered testimonies and produced some reports, the full public release of these findings was limited, which hindered the collective ownership of the truth within the national consciousness. Essential information about the violence and its perpetrators was not widely shared, obstructing society's ability to fully engage with and acknowledge the historical events and the associated harm. Many victims, particularly from marginalised communities, felt sidelined in the process due to inadequate representation. The selective nature of the testimonies and the exclusion from hearings diminished the credibility of the truth that was purportedly established. This lack of inclusivity meant that not all perspectives were represented, rendering the truth-seeking endeavour less than comprehensive. The absence of marginalised voices in the discourse further entrenched their sense of political and social alienation. Teitel (2003) argues that the incomplete dissemination of the report diminishes the transparency of the process and hampers the collective appropriation of the truth. Additionally, the criticism surrounding the selection of witnesses and the representativeness of the testimonies, particularly regarding marginalized groups, further undermines the legitimacy of the truth that was claimed to have been established.

7.1.2. The commission lacked independence and political neutrality

The operations of the CDVR were significantly shaped by political dynamics, which compromised its credibility and autonomy in fulfilling its reconciliation mission. Established by the Ivorian government, the commission was subject to the influence of the ruling authority, which played a crucial role in determining its structure and strategic direction. This situation fostered a perception of partiality, as the government-dominated narrative frequently eclipsed the perspectives of opposition factions and marginalized groups. The absence of impartiality raised doubts regarding the objectivity of the commission's conclusions, thereby hindering its potential to promote national cohesion. Various political entities, particularly those aligned with the opposition, perceived the CDVR as a mechanism for targeting certain individuals or groups, while those associated with the government seemed to evade scrutiny. This political exclusion and the perception of bias exacerbated existing divisions within society, complicating the reconciliation efforts further. Consequently, the process was regarded more as a political instrument than as an independent avenue for uncovering the truth.

7.1.3. Reparations and victim support were inadequate

The CDVR proposed various reparative measures, yet their execution proved inadequate, resulting in numerous victims lacking essential support. Although financial reparations were suggested, the processes for funding and distribution faced significant obstacles due to limited resources and administrative inefficiencies. Consequently, many individuals who were assured reparations did not receive them, and those who did often found the compensation insufficient considering their suffering. This inequity in reparations led to heightened frustration and a deeper sense of injustice among the victims.

In addition to financial reparations, the CDVR advocated for psychosocial support, especially for those who had experienced both physical and psychological trauma. Unfortunately, mental health services and psychosocial assistance were either lacking or poorly funded, which hindered victims' access to the necessary care. This shortfall left many individuals emotionally wounded, unable to heal or progress from their traumatic experiences. Furthermore, while symbolic reparations, such as public apologies and memorials, were recommended, their implementation was incomplete.

Such symbolic gestures are vital for restoring dignity to victims and acknowledging their suffering; however, the failure to carry out these reparations or to provide meaningful recognition further estranged victims, who felt their pain was disregarded. De Greiff (2006) argues that without effective follow-up, reparative measures remain merely theoretical and fail in restoring victims' dignity. The uneven distribution of reparations, where some victims received support while others did not, perpetuated a lingering sense of injustice.

7.1.4. Lack of accountability undermined reconciliation

The lack of legal accountability mechanisms allowed many perpetrators of violence to evade justice, perpetuating cycles of impunity in Côte d'Ivoire. Although the CDVR effectively collected testimonies and sought to uncover the truth, it lacked the authority to enforce criminal accountability. The absence of judicial repercussions for those who committed acts of violence, regardless of their political affiliations, further entrenched the notion of impunity. This disconnect between the pursuit of truth and the delivery of justice undermined the commission's credibility, leading the public to question its efficacy. Consequently, the failure to establish legal accountability eroded trust in both the justice system and governmental institutions. In societies emerging from conflict, it is crucial for transitional justice frameworks to incorporate legal proceedings to ensure accountability; without such measures, the reconciliation process may be viewed as superficial, lacking the depth required for genuine national healing.

The CDVR's primary aim was to seek the truth through testimonies and investigations, yet it faced significant challenges, particularly the absence of fair judicial prosecutions. In the realm of transitional justice, judicial accountability is vital for dismantling impunity. However, the CDVR was not granted the authority to compel legal action against those responsible for violations. This limitation further solidified the perception of impunity, especially as judicial actions appeared to target only specific politically affiliated groups. Roht-Arriaza (2005) contends that a truth commission, in the absence of supportive judicial mechanisms, risks endorsing impunity, thereby jeopardizing the reconciliation process.

7.1.5. Community-based reconciliation mechanisms were underutilised

The CDVR predominantly employed top-down strategies for justice and reconciliation, neglecting grassroots initiatives that frequently proved more effective at the community level. Côte d'Ivoire possesses a longstanding tradition of local conflict resolution and traditional justice practices, including the involvement of village elders, tribal councils, and religious leaders who play a crucial role in mediating disputes. Despite the potential of these systems, the CDVR primarily concentrated on national-level processes, leading many local communities to feel that their justice methods were disregarded, even though they could have facilitated more meaningful healing and reconciliation. A more comprehensive integration of these traditional mechanisms could have effectively connected national and local reconciliation efforts. The absence of community-oriented reconciliation programs left numerous victims feeling voiceless within their own communities. Grassroots peacebuilding initiatives, which encourage dialogue and forgiveness between victims and perpetrators in structured environments, are vital for achieving sustainable reconciliation. Unfortunately, these initiatives were frequently overlooked in favour of government-led approaches.

7.1.6. Approach of restorative justice: recognition and reparation

Public acknowledgment of suffering plays a crucial role in the framework of restorative justice. The Commission for the Development of Victims' Rights (CDVR) provided a platform for victims to share their narratives during public hearings, which was instrumental in restoring their dignity. Nonetheless, the initiative faced several criticisms, particularly regarding the inadequate inclusion of victims and a lack of significant symbolic impact. Certain communities felt marginalized from the process, which hindered the overall effectiveness of recognition. Hayner (2011) posits that acknowledging the injustices endured is essential for dismantling the cycle of impunity, yet this recognition must be comprehensive to achieve its intended effect. While recognition is a vital initial step, the absence of tangible reparative actions leaves the restoration of dignity unfulfilled. The CDVR proposed various forms of reparations, financial, symbolic, and psychosocial, to address the harm experienced by victims. However, the execution of these recommendations has been criticized for its inconsistency and inadequacy. The shortfall in funding and the lack of an independent oversight mechanism have impeded the effective implementation of these reparative

measures. De Greiff (2006) argues that without strong follow-up, reparative initiatives remain largely theoretical and fail to genuinely restore victims' dignity. Consequently, some victims received reparations while others did not, perpetuating a lingering sense of injustice.

7.1.7. National reconciliation: Process and challenges

Reconciliation relies on the capacity to construct a collective narrative that encompasses the historical truths. The Commission for the Development of Victims' Rights (CDVR) endeavoured to formulate this narrative by collecting diverse testimonies and suggesting reforms for institutions. Nonetheless, the process has been undermined by certain limitations, including issues of transparency, impartiality, and inclusivity. A significant barrier has been the insufficient dialogue between victims and perpetrators, which has obstructed the development of a genuine forgiveness process. True reconciliation is achievable only when all parties engage in open discussions about their experiences of suffering (Zehr, 2002). The recommendations put forth by the CDVR included institutional reforms designed to avert future violence; however, the lack of follow-up and effective execution of these reforms has curtailed their potential to contribute to the country's long-term stability. An incomplete reform process ultimately fails to foster sustainable change.

Perspectives on Reconciliation and the CDVR

Many respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the CDVR, citing a lack of independence and legal accountability for perpetrators. Others, however, acknowledged that the symbolic acknowledgment of suffering by the state was a step toward healing. The CDVR's public hearings were intended to foster national healing through open testimonies, with some participants finding these hearings cathartic, as they allowed victims to express their pain. Conversely, others viewed them as politically controlled or selective, which diminished their credibility. Many interviewees believed that reconciliation was not achievable without more tangible legal and economic measures.

Concerns About Inclusivity and Economic Justice

A major concern among respondents was whether the CDVR had been truly inclusive in representing all victims and perpetrators. Some argued that certain political and ethnic groups received more attention, while others felt marginalized. The credibility of the commission was questioned, especially regarding perceived biases in selecting testimonies and granting amnesties. Additionally, many victims and civil society members expressed a lack of trust in state institutions, doubting the government's commitment to impartial reconciliation. Economic justice was a key issue, with many victims expressing disappointment over limited or delayed compensation for their losses. The absence of concrete socio-economic reintegration programmes for victims and ex-combatants was highlighted as a significant weakness, with some stakeholders arguing that prioritizing reparations was essential for making reconciliation meaningful.

7.1.8. International influence on the Ivorian Truth Commission

The creation of the CDVR illustrates the complex interplay between national sovereignty and international influence in post-conflict contexts. While international actors such as the UN and the African Union provided crucial support to Côte d'Ivoire's efforts to move beyond the 2010–2011 crisis, their role also introduced tensions regarding the ownership and legitimacy of the reconciliation process. The testimonies collected (chapter 6) suggest that although international pressure helped initiate a necessary institutional response, it also risked alienating local populations by imposing models not fully adapted to Ivorian realities.

As Hayner notes, “truth commissions that emerge under strong international pressure often struggle to gain the full confidence of the society they are meant to serve” (2011, p. 231). This observation resonates strongly with the Ivorian case, where the perception of an externally driven reconciliation process weakened the CDVR's ability to deeply engage the population. Therefore, while international involvement was indispensable for political stabilization, it remains essential to balance external frameworks with genuine national consultations to ensure the legitimacy and effectiveness of transitional justice mechanisms.

7.1.9 Restorative Justice and Complex Victimhood

National reconciliation in Côte d'Ivoire, a crucial process following the political and military violence that scarred the country, hinges on the complexity of victimization and responsibility. This process reveals a diverse array of perceptions, all reflecting the intricate dynamics between victims and perpetrators and how these roles are often ambiguous and intertwined in the context of a prolonged civil war.

The concept of reconciliation, as explored in Chapter 6, emphasizes the need for a nuanced approach that recognizes shared responsibilities. The division between victims and perpetrators can often exacerbate tensions and hinder the healing process. The reconciliation process must therefore move beyond simplistic binary classifications of good and evil, focusing instead on the collective acknowledgment of all forms of suffering and responsibility. Recent works, such as those by Lemoine and Touré (2015), support this view, advocating for a plural reading of historical events to better understand the roots of violence and suffering.

In this context, moving away from a manichean logic is essential. Complex victimization cannot be ignored, as it contradicts official narratives that seek to maintain a clear-cut distinction between victims and perpetrators. Many victims, frustrated by the absence of justice, have, over time, transformed into perpetrators of violence. This cycle, though difficult to break, underscores the importance of a more open and just approach to reconciliation, grounded in an understanding of the deep motivations behind individuals' actions. This aligns with the principles of restorative justice, as discussed by Tutu (1999), which seeks not only to punish wrongdoers but also to address the underlying causes of conflict and promote healing for all parties involved.

Moreover, the duality of the roles of victim and perpetrator becomes evident when considering those who were directly involved in the conflict. Often, individuals were forced into military engagement due to the circumstances of war, torn between survival and guilt. This complexity challenges the traditional concept of justice, questioning whether individuals can be fairly judged without considering the exceptional context in which they acted. The works of Martha Minow (1998) support this perspective, arguing that true justice must account for all the factors that led individuals to engage in violence.

Finally, the boundaries between victims and perpetrators are often fluid, especially in the aftermath of violence. In many communities, acts of vengeance have been committed, complicating the narrative of clear victimization. What becomes indisputable, however, is the shared loss experienced by all: the loss of lives, homes, and trust. This notion of shared suffering is central to the reconciliation process, as it emphasizes the need for mutual recognition of suffering from all parties involved. As Lederach (1997) points out, true reconciliation requires the commitment of everyone involved, based on the recognition of mutual suffering.

These ideas converge around one central theme: reconciliation in Côte d'Ivoire cannot be based on a simplistic, manichean understanding of events. As argued by Lederach (1997) and Minow (1998), an effective reconciliation process must include a nuanced understanding of the roles everyone played and the underlying causes of violence. Reconciliation is not merely about punishing or absolving guilt but about creating a space for mutual recognition of suffering and the acceptance of living together once again. This requires an inclusive and participatory approach, where all voices are heard, and all pains acknowledged, fostering a genuine and empathetic dialogue aimed at rebuilding a shared future.

For lasting reconciliation to be achieved in Côte d'Ivoire, it is essential to transcend divisions and adopt an approach that recognizes the complexity of the roles of victim and perpetrator, as well as the shared suffering. This approach, as outlined in Chapter 6, will strengthen social cohesion and lay the groundwork for true and lasting peace.

7.2 Contributions to transitional justice scholarship

This research makes several key contributions to theoretical, methodical and empirical of transitional justice processes, with a specific focus on the Ivorian context.

7.2.1 Methodological contribution to knowledge

This study significantly contributes to the field of transitional justice by refining methodological strategies that address the complexities of reconciliation in post-conflict settings. Focusing on the Commission for Dialogue, Truth, and Reconciliation (CDVR) in Côte d'Ivoire, the research employs a multifaceted qualitative framework incorporating in-depth interviews, document analysis, and comparative case studies. The insights gained from this research enhance the understanding of the CDVR's

impact on restorative justice and reconciliation efforts. By integrating various methodologies, the study sheds light on the intricacies involved in transitional justice and provides valuable lessons for future initiatives.

The study's major contributions include the triangulation of diverse data sources, contextually rich narrative inquiry, comparative analysis, and a strong emphasis on stakeholder involvement. By integrating primary data, gathered through interviews with policymakers and civil society leaders, with secondary data from official reports, media narratives, and academic literature, the research bolsters the credibility and depth of its conclusions. The triangulation process is essential for cross verifying the collected information and establishing a robust foundation for understanding the complex dynamics inherent in transitional justice (Teitel, 2003). Utilizing multiple data sources is vital for reflecting the diverse realities of post-conflict societies and ensuring that the findings are well-supported.

The research employs a narrative inquiry framework to delve into the personal experiences of those impacted by the conflict. This approach facilitates the collection of detailed individual stories, which are crucial for assessing the effectiveness of truth commissions in restoring dignity and fostering reconciliation. By emphasizing personal narratives, the study highlights the symbolic and emotional aspects of transitional justice that are often overlooked in quantitative analyses. In the context of post-conflict research, narrative inquiry serves as a valuable tool for uncovering victims' subjective experiences, contributing to the formation of a collective memory vital for reconciliation (Zehr, 2002).

A distinctive methodological advantage of this study is its comparative aspect. By contrasting the CDVR with truth commissions in countries like South Africa, Rwanda, and Sierra Leone, the research uncovers shared challenges and innovative strategies. This comparative examination situates the Ivorian situation within a broader international context and highlights the contextual elements affecting the efficacy of transitional justice initiatives. Engaging in comparative analyses in the field of transitional justice enables the identification of best practices while underscoring the relationship between local circumstances and universal justice principles (Roht-Arriaza, 2005).

A fundamental element of the methodology is its commitment to inclusivity. The research framework emphasizes the importance of incorporating perspectives from marginalized individuals, particularly victims and representatives from local communities. This inclusive approach enriches the data collected and aligns with the foundational principles of restorative justice, which prioritize recognition and healing. Employing inclusive methodologies in post-conflict research is crucial to ensure that all affected parties have a voice, ultimately facilitating authentic reconciliation (Roht-Arriaza, 2005).

This study introduces an evaluative framework designed to assess Community-Driven Victim Restoration (CDVR) through the lens of restorative justice. The significance and effectiveness of restorative justice rely on the active participation and involvement of stakeholders in conflict situations, encompassing elements such as inclusion, negotiation, reparation, truth-telling, and restoration. Existing literature has connected restorative practices to various approaches, including mediation between perpetrators and victims, and restorative group consultations (Van Camp & Wemmers, 2011).

Evaluative research on restorative practices indicates that victims who participate in these interventions hold them in high regard (Wemmers & Canuto, 2002; Shapland et al., 2006). Comparative studies show that the restorative model aligns effectively with victims' expectations, even for serious offenses (Braithwaite, 1999). The benefits of engaging in restorative interventions, which have therapeutic advantages, further highlight the importance of victim involvement. For instance, a study by Rugge and Scott (2009) in Canada explored victims' psychological well-being before and after engagement in victim-perpetrator mediation, revealing self-reported improvements in their mental health.

The principles outlined in this research have informed the formulation of the CDVR evaluation criteria implemented in this thesis. By examining the extent of participation and inclusion of stakeholders—whether in negotiation, recognition, or action—this approach provides a framework for assessing the participatory dynamics that a truth commission can foster. This thesis investigates three phases of the CDVR process: the pre-establishment period, the duration of its mandate, and the follow-up on the recommendations presented in the final report. Prior research has evaluated truth

commissions, noting important distinctions based on regional contexts (Hayner, 2002; Robins, 2012; Villa-Vicencio, 2010).

The evaluation framework introduced in this research can serve as a valuable tool for scholars, advocacy organizations, and stakeholders in various countries, aiding them in assessing and guiding the operations of truth commissions. By linking restorative justice principles and practices to the function of a truth commission, the framework enhances the participatory and inclusive nature of the commission's work. This framework also facilitates an analysis of the interplay between restorative justice and reconciliation, prioritizing the needs of victims and holding those involved in the conflicts accountable.

In conclusion, the methodological significance of this study lies in its integration of various qualitative methods, including triangulation, narrative inquiry, and comparative analysis. Collectively, these approaches allow for a detailed examination of the CDVR's influence on reconciliation through restorative justice. This comprehensive methodological framework not only deepens scholarly understanding of transitional justice in Côte d'Ivoire but also provides essential guidance for policymakers and practitioners aiming to develop more effective reconciliation strategies in post-conflict environments. By addressing the limitations of the CDVR and advocating for the integration of restorative justice practices, the study contributes to enhancing the effectiveness of future truth commissions.

7.2.2 Theoretical Contributions to knowledge

This research significantly contributes to the theoretical understanding of transitional justice by integrating the frameworks of transitional justice and restorative justice. By analysing the Commission for Dialogue, Truth, and Reconciliation (CDVR) in Côte d'Ivoire, this study introduces a hybrid model that reconciles the traditionally distinct approaches of judicial accountability and restorative healing. This synthesis provides insights into how effective transitional justice processes should incorporate truth-telling, reparations, and structural reforms to ensure that victims receive the recognition and dignity they rightfully deserve. This introduction highlights the key theoretical advancements made by this research and sets the stage for a deeper exploration of its contributions.

A significant achievement of this study lies in its merging of the transitional and restorative justice frameworks. Conventional transitional justice models primarily emphasize judicial accountability through mechanisms such as criminal prosecutions and institutional reforms, while restorative justice focuses on healing, acknowledgment, and reconciliation. This research highlights how the CDVR serves as a hybrid model, addressing critiques that standalone truth commissions may inadequately provide victims with a sense of justice and closure. By proposing an integrated approach that encompasses truth-telling, reparations, and structural reforms, the research underscores the essential recognition and dignity that victims need to achieve a meaningful sense of justice and closure (Roht-Arriaza, 2005).

Another significant theoretical contribution of this study is its exploration of inclusive truth-seeking. The research critically evaluates how the selection of testimonies and the distribution of the final report impact the formation of collective memory. It argues that for truth commissions to be truly effective, their processes must not only document events but also ensure that their findings are accessible and representative of all affected communities. Building on the insights of scholars like Teitel (2003) and Hayner (2011), the study emphasizes the necessity for truth to be pluralistic and inclusive, promoting genuine reconciliation among diverse groups.

The study enhances theoretical discussions surrounding reparative justice through a detailed examination of reparations. Unlike earlier research that primarily focused on the symbolic dimensions of reparations, this analysis advocates for a comprehensive approach that integrates financial, symbolic, and psychosocial elements. By addressing the shortcomings in the implementation of the CDVR's recommendations, this research argues for a reparations model that acknowledges historical injustices while actively restoring the dignity of victims. This perspective refines existing theories by asserting that effective reparations must be both fair and subject to oversight. Without tangible and just reparations, the restoration of victims' dignity remains inadequate, subsequently hindering the reconciliation process (De Greiff, 2006).

Moreover, this research provides theoretical insights by highlighting the significance of contextual factors and political dynamics within transitional justice frameworks. It posits that the effectiveness of any truth commission or restorative justice initiative is contingent upon its ability to align with local circumstances. This viewpoint critiques

universal models and advocates for a nuanced understanding of justice that considers specific political, cultural, and historical contexts. This aspect builds on the contributions of scholars such as Roht-Arriaza (2005) and Sriram (2012), who underscore the critical role of national context in shaping the outcomes of transitional justice initiatives.

In conclusion, this research presents a diverse array of theoretical contributions that collectively enrich the academic discourse surrounding transitional justice. By merging the principles of transitional and restorative justice, promoting inclusive approaches to truth-seeking, enhancing reparative strategies, and emphasizing the importance of contextual factors, the study provides a comprehensive framework for examining the role of truth commissions, particularly the CDVR, in fostering reconciliation within post-conflict societies. The insights gained from this research offer valuable guidance for the development of more effective and contextually aware reconciliation initiatives, both in Côte d'Ivoire and in similar post-conflict settings around the globe.

7.2.3 Empirical contribution to knowledge

This study provides an empirical examination of the Commission for Dialogue, Truth, and Reconciliation (CDVR) in Côte d'Ivoire, assessing its effectiveness in the context of transitional justice within a complex post-conflict landscape. By analyzing the commission's operational efficiency, the dynamics between justice and reconciliation, and the roles various stakeholders play in achieving the CDVR's objectives, this research enriches the understanding of transitional justice mechanisms following periods of violence and political unrest. The findings highlight significant insights into the challenges and opportunities associated with truth commissions, ultimately offering implications for the future design of similar initiatives in various global contexts.

The research reveals critical insights into how victims of violence and their communities perceive the CDVR's initiatives, introducing a grassroots perspective into the broader discourse on the efficacy of truth commissions. Numerous victims expressed feelings of disconnection from the CDVR's processes, citing limited outreach and perceived bias. While many considered the truth-telling process vital for healing, disappointment regarding the lack of accountability for offenders was common. This frustration was particularly acute among individuals whose cases were

excluded from public hearings or whose testimonies were inadequately integrated into meaningful reforms. Consequently, the capacity of the CDVR to acknowledge and validate victim narratives emerged as a crucial factor in its overall success, while marginalized communities expressed scepticism about the commission's effectiveness.

While several individuals involved in the hearings experienced emotional relief from sharing their stories, this relief was often short-lived in the absence of mental health support. The findings underscore that while truth commissions can play an essential role in publicly acknowledging suffering, they cannot substitute for psychological healing. The integration of mental health services into the operational structures of the CDVR would thus be a necessary enhancement, ensuring that victims receive comprehensive care as they navigate the complexities of their experiences in a post-conflict society.

The study thoroughly examines the institutional factors impacting the effectiveness of the CDVR, particularly considering the political context in which it operated. The findings illustrate that the Ivorian government's stance on transitional justice significantly influenced the commission's impartiality. Many interviewees noted that selective justice practices eroded the CDVR's credibility, as it appeared to target opposition party members while shielding individuals associated with the ruling government. This perceived bias not only compromised the legitimacy of the reconciliation process but also fostered beliefs that justice was politically manipulated, further complicating the commission's mission.

Additionally, the research highlights the role of international entities such as the United Nations (UN), the African Union (AU), and regional organizations like ECOWAS in supporting the CDVR's mandate. However, their ability to effect meaningful change was constrained by their need to balance political stability with the pursuit of accountability. Often, these organizations favoured diplomatic initiatives prioritizing peace and dialogue over the prosecution of offenders. Furthermore, NGOs and civil society groups were instrumental in advocating for victims' rights and promoting transparency within the commission's functions. However, their efforts were frequently hampered by political interference and the government's inclination to dominate the narrative surrounding reconciliation.

The study illustrates how public perceptions of the CDVR were heavily influenced by political affiliations. Supporters of the ruling party generally viewed the CDVR positively, regarding it as a mechanism for restoring peace, while those aligned with opposition sentiments frequently criticized it as biased and ineffective. This dichotomy emphasizes the significant challenges faced in promoting social unity through a transitional justice framework that does not address the fundamental causes of political discord. For lasting reconciliation, reforms and restorative actions must go beyond mere reparations and truth-telling. They must tackle systemic issues that contribute to conflict in the first place.

Moreover, the empirical evidence uncovers notable shortcomings in the truth-telling process, essential for refining future transitional justice initiatives. The CDVR primarily focused on urban elites and prominent cases, neglecting marginalized groups such as rural victims, women, and ethnic minorities. This limited engagement fostered disenfranchisement among these communities, reducing the perceived legitimacy of the commission. Hearings frequently centered on political figures and elite narratives while neglecting the experiences of ordinary citizens. This narrow approach to accountability failed to capture the full extent of the violence experienced, leading many victims to feel that the commission prioritized elite concerns over grassroots issues.

Despite providing a platform for victims to share their experiences, the lack of robust legal measures allowed many perpetrators to evade accountability. The absence of a comprehensive legal framework connecting the truth-telling process to judicial mechanisms hindered the CDVR's ability to deliver substantial justice. This disconnect highlights the necessity for future transitional justice frameworks to establish enforceable legal pathways that ensure justice for victims and accountability for offenders.

The study's insights into restorative justice within the CDVR's objectives reveal a victim-centred approach that is crucial for effective transitional justice. Many victims regarded this model, focusing on healing, truth-telling, and reconciliation, as essential for their recovery journey. However, the lack of tangible reparations and legal accountability left many feeling that the process was inadequate. While the victim-

centered approach amplified marginalized voices, it did not adequately address the structural injustices at play.

The findings of this study offer valuable lessons for transitional justice initiatives worldwide. The successes and failures of the CDVR can inform the design and execution of truth commissions in various post-conflict contexts, particularly those grappling with election-related violence or political turmoil. The research emphasizes that truth commissions alone are insufficient for fostering lasting peace. To effectively address the underlying societal divisions fuelling conflict, institutional reforms must occur concurrently with transitional justice efforts, particularly in electoral, judicial, and land systems.

In conclusion, while the CDVR contributed significantly to truth-telling and symbolic reconciliation in Côte d'Ivoire, its effectiveness was constrained by political bias, inadequate support for victims, and a lack of institutional follow-up. For future transitional justice frameworks to achieve genuine reconciliation and justice for all, they must integrate mechanisms for legal accountability, foster inclusive victim participation, and implement necessary institutional reforms. This study's empirical findings provide crucial insights that can guide the evolution of transitional justice, enhance its efficacy and reach in contexts akin to Côte d'Ivoire.

7.3 The evolving framework of transitional justice

The literature review indicates that over the past three decades, the concept of transitional justice has significantly progressed and broadened its scope beyond mere legal frameworks. In this context, Kora asserts that "transitional justice articulates in an original way a legal corpus with the pragmatic objectives of democratization and pacification" (Kora, 2015, pp. 353). Central to this framework is the dual focus on engaging the public in transitional processes through organized forums for discussion and peacebuilding, alongside the pivotal function of truth commissions, which are tasked with conducting investigations, providing a platform for victims to voice their experiences, and facilitating reconciliation efforts. Concurrently, organizations involved in transitional justice have also transformed, particularly human rights groups that collaborate with victims to address state abuses. Notable entities such as the UN and the International Commission on Human Rights have evolved into transitional justice organisations that advocate for increased victim and citizen participation in

these processes, while also seeking to work in partnership with governmental bodies. This research highlights a notable gap in the existing literature regarding the relationship between the effectiveness of truth commissions and their intended objectives, thereby justifying the need for this study to bridge that gap. Such an investigation is essential for assessing the outcomes, advancements, and shortcomings of these commissions. Consequently, seven evaluation criteria were established to reflect the principles of restorative justice and reconciliation.

7.4 Implications of the research

The research highlights the need for inclusive processes that ensure all segments of society, particularly marginalized communities, are actively represented. By examining the selective nature of the CDVR's testimonies and the limitations in its stakeholder inclusion, the study encourages scholars to develop more nuanced frameworks for inclusivity. This may lead to new theories that better capture the dynamics of collective memory and social healing in heterogeneous societies. Transitional justice must be both context-sensitive and inclusive, ensuring that the voices of all affected groups are represented in the narrative of the past (Teitel (2003).

By employing a multi-method qualitative approach (triangulation of interviews, document analysis, and comparative case studies), the research provides a replicable model for studying complex post-conflict environments. The methodological contribution lies in demonstrating how qualitative data can reveal both the symbolic and practical impacts of truth commissions. This approach enriches the field by offering a robust framework for future empirical studies on transitional justice.

The findings indicate that insufficient and uneven reparations contribute to a lingering sense of injustice. Policy recommendations include:

- Establishing a victim compensation fund with transparent criteria.
- Ensuring that reparations are not solely financial; they should also include psychosocial support and symbolic measures (e.g., public apologies, memorials).
- Creating independent oversight bodies to monitor the implementation of reparative measures.

Equitable and effective reparations are vital not only to compensate for past wrongs but also to restore victims' dignity and promote social healing (De Greiff (2006). The study underscores the necessity of broader institutional reforms to prevent future conflicts. This includes reforming the security and judicial systems to ensure impartiality and prevent abuses, enhancing transparency in governance and improving mechanisms for political accountability and engaging local communities in institutional oversight to build trust in new structures. The research critically examines the role of international actors in influencing transitional justice. For policies to be effective, external support must be carefully balanced with local ownership. Policymakers should ensure that international assistance aligns with local needs and cultural norms rather than imposing external models. International involvement should empower local institutions rather than override them, ensuring that transitional justice processes are both culturally relevant and politically sustainable (Sriram (2012). The empirical findings emphasize that truth-telling and reparations are essential for restoring victims' dignity. Practical initiatives should therefore focus on:

- Creating platforms for open dialogue and community-based reconciliation initiatives.
- Integrating psychosocial support services with legal and financial reparations.
- Ensuring that victims' narratives are preserved and disseminated widely to build a collective memory that supports long-term healing.

For reconciliation to be sustainable, it is crucial that the historical narrative of the conflict is collectively owned. The research points out that the limited dissemination of the CDVR's final report has hindered this process. Future initiatives must ensure that:

- Findings and recommendations are publicly accessible.
- Educational and media programmes incorporate the documented truths of past conflicts to foster a shared national history.

By highlighting both successes and failures in the CDVR process, the study offers practical lessons for community-based reconciliation efforts. Grassroots initiatives, such as local mediation forums and involvement of traditional and religious leaders, can complement formal transitional justice mechanisms, thereby strengthening community resilience. Empowering communities to participate in reconciliation efforts

creates a bottom-up approach to justice that can bridge divides and promote sustainable peace (Hayner (2011)).

The implications of this research extend across theoretical, policy, and practical dimensions. From an academic perspective, it critiques and enhances current models of transitional and restorative justice by promoting hybrid frameworks that are sensitive to specific contexts. In terms of policy, it advocates for the establishment of strong judicial and reparative systems, comprehensive institutional reforms, and a nuanced approach to international involvement. Practically, the research underscores the importance of victim-centred initiatives that aim to restore dignity, cultivate collective memory, and encourage sustainable social healing. Together, these findings not only contribute to scholarly discussions but also offer actionable recommendations for developing more effective transitional justice mechanisms in Côte d'Ivoire and similar post-conflict environments. An effective transitional justice process must integrate truth-telling, reparations, and structural reforms to ensure that victims receive the recognition and dignity they rightfully deserve.

7.5 Limitations of the Study and future research directions

This research is primarily focused on Côte d'Ivoire and the operations of the Commission for Dialogue, Truth, and Reconciliation (CDVR). While the CDVR provides valuable insights into transitional justice in the country, the study's findings may be limited in their applicability to other post-conflict environments due to unique historical, political, and cultural elements. Teitel (2003) emphasizes that the context-dependent nature of transitional justice means that insights derived from one nation may not easily transfer to another without modifications. Additionally, the inherent fluidity of transitional justice processes suggests that the timeframe of this study may only reflect short- to medium-term outcomes, potentially overlooking the complexities and long-term effects of reforms and healing initiatives that could take decades to fully materialize.

The study employs qualitative methodologies, including interviews, narrative analysis, and document reviews, which can provide in-depth understanding but are also susceptible to biases such as selection bias and recall bias. These biases threaten the objectivity of findings and may restrict the generalizability of results. Moreover, the absence of substantial quantitative data means that important relationships—such as

the correlation between reparations and social cohesion—remain unverified, limiting the ability to make broad generalizations or establish causal connections. In addition, critical documents, like detailed follow-up reports on the CDVR's impact, may be inaccessible or incomplete, further diminishing the thoroughness and reliability of the analysis.

The political environment surrounding the CDVR significantly influences its operations. Instances of political interference can create a perception of biased justice, undermining the impartiality of the commission's conclusions. The lack of independent oversight to monitor the execution of CDVR's recommendations presents another significant obstacle. In this absence, it becomes challenging to ascertain whether the commission's efforts have produced lasting institutional changes or meaningful reparations. Furthermore, while efforts were made to include diverse perspectives, the underrepresentation of marginalized groups may skew the understanding of the conflict's repercussions and obstruct the formation of a comprehensive national narrative. To achieve genuinely inclusive transitional justice, it is imperative that all affected voices, especially those from marginalized communities, are acknowledged and integrated into these processes.

Future investigations should compare the CDVR with truth commissions from various post-conflict contexts, such as South Africa, Rwanda, and Sierra Leone. Such comparative studies can identify shared challenges and context-specific elements, contributing to broader theories of transitional justice while emphasizing local differences. Teitel (2003) argues that comparative analyses can highlight both the advantages and limitations of different transitional justice frameworks, assisting in developing adaptable best practices. To effectively monitor how the impacts of transitional justice initiatives evolve over time, it is essential to conduct longitudinal studies that assess social, political, and institutional outcomes over extended periods. Future research should also adopt a mixed-methods strategy, combining qualitative and quantitative data to capture public sentiment, levels of social cohesion, and the effectiveness of reparative measures.

In summary, this study provides valuable insights into the functioning and limitations of the CDVR in Côte d'Ivoire, while also highlighting several areas for further exploration. Future research should employ comparative, longitudinal, and mixed

methods approaches to better understand transitional justice mechanisms and their outcomes. Emphasizing inclusivity, particularly the representation of marginalized voices, and evaluating hybrid justice models are critical for enhancing transitional justice frameworks. These efforts will not only deepen theoretical understanding but also provide practical guidance for designing more effective reconciliation processes in post-conflict environments, ultimately fostering lasting peace and social healing.

7.6 Final remarks

This study investigates the role of the Commission for Dialogue, Truth, and Reconciliation (CDVR) in Côte d'Ivoire, focusing on its initiatives to foster reconciliation and restorative justice in a society recovering from conflict. The CDVR aimed to address the wounds of the past, promote healing, and pave the way for sustainable peace. However, this research uncovers the complexities and limitations of the CDVR's efforts, revealing the challenges that hindered the effectiveness of its mandate. It seeks to provide a critical evaluation of the CDVR's impact on healing, justice, and reconciliation in Côte d'Ivoire, while also contributing to broader discussions in the field of transitional justice.

The empirical findings of this research indicate that although the CDVR made notable strides in facilitating truth-telling and acknowledging victims, its effectiveness was thwarted by structural and political obstacles as well as the narrow scope of its mandate. While victim-centered strategies that create opportunities for victims to share their narratives are essential, the findings also highlight significant shortcomings when these initiatives lack accompanying legal accountability and necessary institutional reforms. Ultimately, the CDVR succeeded in facilitating some healing for certain individuals, but it did not adequately address the fundamental causes of the conflict or fulfill its commitments to justice for all victims, leading to mixed outcomes in promoting enduring peace and reconciliation.

This research makes significant methodological contributions to the field of transitional justice, shedding light on the intricate challenges associated with conducting empirical studies in post-conflict environments. It underscores the importance of adopting multifaceted approaches to comprehend transitional justice mechanisms, emphasizing the necessity to consider political and policy frameworks alongside the local perceptions and lived experiences of victims. These insights can help refine

future research and provide a robust foundation for understanding the dynamics of transitional justice in similar contexts.

The theoretical implications of this study reveal that while restorative justice provides a valuable framework for fostering reconciliation, it cannot serve as a one-size-fits-all solution. The findings underscore the critical need to incorporate structural reforms into transitional justice initiatives, including institutional transformation, economic assistance, and political accountability. Such measures are essential for facilitating authentic and lasting reconciliation, moving beyond mere symbolic actions toward substantive justice and reparations.

Looking ahead, the research advocates for a more critical examination of the limitations inherent in truth commissions. It stresses the importance of developing more inclusive, comprehensive, and integrated transitional justice frameworks that focus on substantial justice rather than symbolic gestures. Future investigations should explore the interplay between restorative and retributive justice and investigate reconciliation processes driven by community engagement, with the aim of cultivating a more holistic approach to post-conflict recovery.

This study emphasizes the intricate nature of reconciliation in post-conflict settings and provides a critical evaluation of the CDVR's efforts to promote justice and healing in Côte d'Ivoire. It advocates for a broader perspective on transitional justice that extends beyond the immediate goals of truth-telling to consider the essential long-term societal changes necessary for preventing future violence and fostering genuine peace. The quest for justice in societies emerging from conflict is inherently complex, influenced by political motivations, historical contexts, and the deeply personal experiences of those affected.

A central theme in the literature on transitional justice is the significance of recognition in the healing process. Recognition encompasses not only acknowledgment of past injustices but also the affirmation of victims' dignity and validation of their experiences. In Côte d'Ivoire, the CDVR sought to create a platform for victims to share their testimonies and for perpetrators to admit their wrongdoings. Nonetheless, the uneven application of justice and the marginalization of certain narratives undermined the

Commission's credibility. When recognition is inconsistently applied, the foundational principles of reconciliation are jeopardized.

Reconciliation is often framed as a moral necessity; however, it is fundamentally a political endeavour that involves negotiations regarding collective memory, accountability, and social dynamics restructuring. The situation in Côte d'Ivoire illustrates how political figures can manipulate reconciliation initiatives to consolidate power rather than promote genuine national healing. The CDVR operated in a context of significant disparities in justice, eroding confidence in the reconciliation process and deepening societal rifts. This reality highlights the need for reconciliation efforts to be rooted in principles of equity and inclusivity, rather than serving as mere rhetorical exercises.

Restoring dignity is a crucial aspect of justice in post-conflict situations, encompassing not only legal accountability but also socio-economic initiatives that empower victims to rebuild their lives. The inadequate provision of meaningful reparations in Côte d'Ivoire exemplifies a prevalent flaw in transitional justice frameworks: the disconnect between truth-telling and material compensation. Many victims felt their pain was acknowledged symbolically, yet their living conditions remained largely unaddressed. This disparity prompts critical inquiries regarding the efficacy of truth commissions as instruments of justice.

Given these constraints, how should we evaluate the effectiveness of the CDVR? When assessed against its stated goals of truth-seeking, justice, and reconciliation, the Commission fell short in several respects. Its failure to administer justice impartially, to offer substantial reparations, and to resist political manipulation suggests that it was, at best, a limited success. Conversely, examining its impact on public discourse surrounding justice reveals that the CDVR played a crucial, albeit flawed, role in shaping Côte d'Ivoire's post-conflict development.

Truth commissions, as evidenced by various contexts, often struggle to deliver complete justice, becoming arenas where multiple historical narratives are debated. In Côte d'Ivoire, the CDVR facilitated essential discussions on accountability and reconciliation, despite its significant shortcomings. While the potential for these discussions to foster long-term peace remains uncertain, they underscore an essential

insight: justice is not a singular event; rather, it is a continuous endeavour that transcends formal commissions and legal processes.

The challenges facing Côte d'Ivoire's reconciliation process expose deeper issues within the realm of transitional justice. The effectiveness of a truth commission is called into question without impartial legal accountability, and achieving reconciliation appears elusive when economic reparations are neglected. Additionally, the significance of recognition diminishes when not all victims are included. These inquiries are relevant not only to Côte d'Ivoire but resonate with all societies transitioning from conflict. The ongoing quest for justice in Côte d'Ivoire does not suggest that meaningful reconciliation is unattainable; instead, it highlights the necessity for innovative strategies that engage directly with the lived experiences of affected communities. For justice to transcend mere symbolism, it must be anchored in policies addressing systemic inequalities, holding all perpetrators accountable, and fostering a national identity that rises above ethnic and political strife. Ultimately, Côte d'Ivoire's journey toward authentic reconciliation depends not only on established formal mechanisms but also on the collective resolve of its citizens and leaders to confront difficult truths, heal historical wounds, and build a shared future grounded in justice and dignity for all.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Positionality Statement

As a researcher with deep personal ties to Côte d'Ivoire, I recognise that my identity, experiences, and cultural background significantly influence my research perspective. Born and raised in Côte d'Ivoire, I have firsthand experiences of the country's socio-political landscape, particularly the complexities surrounding its history of political conflict and transitional justice. Growing up amidst these realities has shaped my understanding of the impact of institutional inequalities and the lived experiences of those affected by them.

My academic background in social sciences has equipped me with theoretical frameworks and analytical tools; however, my lived experiences provide an essential context. I am acutely aware that my positionality as an Ivorian informs my interpretations and may lead to biases in my analysis. To address this, I actively engage in reflexivity, continually questioning how my background may influence my interactions with participants and my interpretations of the data.

To build trust with participants and ensure culturally sensitive engagement, I employed several strategies:

1. Cultural Familiarity: As a member of the community studied, I leveraged my understanding of local customs, language, and social norms to create a rapport with participants. This allowed for more open dialogue and willingness to share personal narratives.

2. Transparent Communication: Upon initiating contact with potential participants, I clearly communicated my background, research objectives, and motivations. By being transparent about my intent and perspective, I aimed to reassure participants of my respect for their stories and experiences.

3. Active Listening: I utilised active listening techniques throughout the interviews, encouraging participants to share their narratives in their own words and emphasizing that their perspectives were central to the research. This fostered a sense of agency, allowing participants to feel valued and respected.

4. Culturally Sensitive Interview Techniques: I adapted my interviewing techniques to align with local customs and communication styles, recognising that certain topics might be sensitive or taboo. This meant being flexible in the questioning approach, allowing for pauses and moments of reflection, and being mindful of non-verbal cues.

5. Feedback Mechanism: I incorporated a feedback mechanism where participants could review how their narratives were represented in the research. This not only emphasised ethical research practices but also reinforced trust, as participants could ensure their voices were accurately portrayed.

6. Ongoing Reflexivity: Throughout the research process, I maintained a reflexive journal where I recorded my thoughts, biases, and emotional responses to the research. This practice enabled me to constantly assess how my identity impacted the research dynamics, ensuring I remained mindful of my positionality.

By employing these culturally sensitive engagement strategies alongside my positionality statement, I aimed to create an ethical and respectful research environment while acknowledging the complexities of my identity as both a researcher and a member of the community. This duality enriches the research process by fostering trust, deepening participant engagement, and ultimately enhancing the integrity and credibility of the findings.

Appendix 2: RESEARCH INFORMATION

Thesis Title:

Evaluation of the Ivorian Truth and Reconciliation Commission through restorative justice

PhD Researcher

Jean WORE ZAKPA

Lead Supervisor

Dr Julie CLARK,

Add. Supervisor

Dr Allan MOORE,

Add. Supervisor

Prof Colin CLARK,

Dear,

We invite you to participate in a research study. This information sheet tells you what this study consists of. You can take the time to read and understand this information to reflect on your participation, and to ask the researcher to explain to you what you did not understand.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study is to provide a deeper understanding of transitional justice in Côte d'Ivoire. This thesis examines the reparative and reconciling potentialities of the design and practices of the National Commission for Reconciliation and Compensation for Victims (CONARIV). The Commission was established as one of the responses aimed at remedying the atrocities and wrongs presented by the various successive Ivorian crises. While the main goals of CONARIV involve uncovering truth and promoting healing and reconciliation, there is a need to critically question its design and activities to better understand its potential to enable Côte d'Ivoire to overcome the trauma and build a just and peaceful future.

Potential benefits

This study could serve as a reference tool for the Ivorian authorities to improve national reconciliation policies.

Subject Participation

We estimate 50 participants to be enrolled in this study. Participants for this study will be composed of political party leaders, government officials, former CDVR staff, CONARIV commissioners, members of victims' associations, victims of injustices, parliamentarians, academics, media staff, religious authorities and civil society organisations. The interview will consist of 12 to 15 questions and will last approximately 30 to 45 minutes. The interview can be conducted in person or over the phone. The time of the in-person interviews will be chosen based on your preferences and the interviews will take place at a location convenient for you. Please note that the in-person interview can be recorded with your permission. During telephone interviews, scheduled at your convenience, the researcher takes written notes.

Potential risks

There is no risk associated with your participation in this interview, that is, the potential harm is not greater than that which one might experience in the normal conduct of daily life.

Cost/compensation/reimbursements

There is no cost and compensation for participating in this study. Any transportation expenses resulting from participation in this study will not be reimbursed by the researcher.

Legal rights - confidentiality

Your privacy as a respondent is highly valued. You have a choice regarding whether your name will appear in the thesis. If you choose the option to keep your responses confidential, your name will **not** appear in the thesis. Instead, in the thesis, you may be identified as "Interview Subject 1, 2, 3," etc. Furthermore, all other information which could

potentially be used to identify you as a respondent, such as dates, times, location of the interview, and personal identifiers, will not be included in the thesis. These data such as this, containing no link to your identity as a respondent, will be stored indefinitely. On the other hand, if you are comfortable with being identified in the thesis

by name, your name will appear in the thesis. The interview data which contains personal identifiers will be kept until completion of the thesis, August 2023, at which point all personal identifiers will be removed and destroyed, and the data will be stored indefinitely.

All data, along with audio tapes and interview transcripts, will be stored in a secure location in the researcher's locked office in J-202 Building at the University of the West of Scotland. Once audio recordings are coded and transcribed, they will be destroyed. Please note that this thesis will become a public document upon its completion. The data will be accessible only by the researcher or the supervisory team. To protect your identity further, the Consent Form will be stored separately from interview data so that no connection can be made between your identity and interview data.

Voluntary Participation and Authorisation

Your decision to participate in this study is complete voluntary. If you decide to not participate in this study, it will not affect the services or benefits to which you are entitled.

Withdrawal from the Study

You are free to withdraw from the study at any time, and /or refrain from answering any questions you prefer to omit, without prejudice or consequence. Your continued participation should be as informed as your initial consent, so you should feel free to ask for clarification or new information throughout your participation.

Authorisation

By signing the consent form, you authorise the use and disclosure of the following information for this research: *"I authorise the use of my records, any observations, and findings found during the course of this study for education, publication and/or presentation"*.

Concerns - complaints

This research has been approved by the University of the West of Scotland/School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee. If you have any concerns or

complaints about this project, you may contact any of the above-named persons or the School Ethics Committees (SEC) at ethicsSofE@uws.ac.uk or +44(0)141 849 4133.

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet. If you agree to participate in this research, we invite you to sign the attached consent form.

Cordially

Jean Zakpa

Appendix 3: RESEARCH INTERVIEW SCHEDULE

Thesis Title:

Evaluation of the Ivorian Truth and Reconciliation Commission through restorative justice

PhD Researcher

Jean WORE ZAKPA

Lead Supervisor

Dr Julie CLARK,

Add. Supervisor

Dr Allan MOORE,

Add. Supervisor

Prof Colin CLARK,

Possible questions to be asked to participants during interviews:

General questions

- 1) What do you know about a TRC in general and the Ivorian TRC in particular?
- 2) What does the concept “restorative justice” mean to you?
- 3) Do you think the Ivorian’s TRC can be considered as restorative?

Before the establishment of the commission

- 1) Did any organisations such as the civil society, the collective of victims or political parties compel the governing to establish the TRC?
- 2) What was the interaction between the potential TRC and these organisations regarding establishment of the TRC?
- 3) Which parties were excluded from the negotiations?

During the process of the commission

- 1) Do you think the commission had access to all the main actors implicated directly/ indirectly in violations? If not, why?
- 2) Did the commission reach out to the victims and take statements from them?
- 3) Did the commission engage an interaction between victims and perpetrators? If not, why?
- 4) Was the atmosphere favourable and safe for the victims to come forward?
- 5) Did the perpetrators acknowledge the harm done to survivors? If so, how?

Final report's recommendations and implementation

- 1) Was the commission's report released after being submitted?
- 2) Was the Commission able to accurately transcribe the past, disclose new information surrounding violations, evidence of violations committed or name the actors involved?
- 3) What do you think of reparations programmes and its accessibility? Do they serve as an adequate form of justice for survivors?
- 4) How does the TRC's design through restorative justice influence the reconciliation?